

**REGULATION AND WASTE: AN INVESTIGATION OF DECISION SUPPORT
FOR THE REMEDIATION OF SOIL POLLUTION IN CHINA**

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Declaration

I confirm that this is my own work and the use of all material from other sources has been properly and fully acknowledged.

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Abstract

The increasing generation of waste causes soil pollution and is a global land degradation issue affecting human health, wildlife and the environment. Making sure sustainable consumption and production is identified as a priority of concern by the United Nations and forms Sustainable Development Goal 12 (SDG 12). Finding effective regulations which can be applied to prevent further soil pollution and assessing its impact or influence in China provided the motivation to study the decision making support to improve efficiency in site remediation and assess new technologies. Dealing with issues for both legacy and preventing new pollution of soil will be key to sustainably managing solid waste to address SDG 12, however a shortage of data available might hinder the sustainable development (SD) in developing countries. China has little experience of issues involving sustainable waste management, soil remediation and managing industrial processes. This hinders the development of the decision-making framework in development projects due to a shortage of comprehensive data collection and detailed analysis. This thesis addresses the knowledge gap with an assessment of the impact of the 2017 waste import ban in China on waste arisings, explores the decision making framework associated with remediation improvements for soil quality. It investigates the potential for the application of sepiolite-based waste as a waste to resource case study for developing countries. The ban leads to price increases in domestic recycling that pushes industries to produce in more formal recycling. The COVID-19 pandemic also shows a significant step to provide sustainable management systems despite an increase in solid wastes' 'fly-tipping'. Growing municipal solid waste (MSW) incineration as a response to increased waste capture would challenge the effect of the net-zero policy on carbon emission in China. A series of parameters applied in decision making for remediation of farmland and construction land were identified from data collected from questionnaire-based engagement with the remediation sector. The most frequently applied materials for stabilization/ solidification are clay minerals during soil remediation. Budget consideration/financing is still the key factor in deciding strategies in the waste management system, the remediation sector, and their operational business model. This is still a challenge for SD in China. The case for the application of sepiolite, combined with other technologies or alone, shows promise for pollution cleanup in contaminated soil from a cost-benefit perspective. In particular, the balance of using primary sepiolite or processing residues to deal with severely contaminated sites within a regional location and the influence of restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Key words: soil pollution, regulation, waste management, China, soil remediation, decision support, sustainable development

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List of Abbreviations

BTEX - Benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and xylenes

CISW - Common industrial solid waste

COVID-19 - Coronavirus Disease 2019

ha - hectare

HSW - Hazardous solid waste

HWM - Hazardous waste management

IPR - Intellectual property rights

ISWM - Industrial solid waste management

MNA - Monitored natural attention

MSWM - Municipal solid waste management

MSW - Municipal solid waste

POPs - Persistent organic pollutants

PRC - People's Republic of China

PTEs - Potentially toxic elements

RQ - Research questions

SD - Sustainable development

SO - Specific objectives

SWMS - Solid waste management system

wt.% - Weight Percentage

Chapter 1 Introduction

This chapter presents the context of this study. It covers the personal research experience, background and the justification for carrying out this research. Research aims, research questions and objectives of the study are presented with the planned contribution of this research and the structure of this thesis.

1.1 Why I study this topic?

Soil contamination in China has been an urgent issue since 2004 when three construction workers were poisoned at Songjiazhuang Subway Station in Beijing (Sohu, 2004). Measures for Special Funds Managements for the Prevention and Control of Heavy Metal Pollution by the Central Government (Caijian [2011] No. 1147) was promulgated in 2011 to start setting the special funds for prevention and control of heavy metal pollution in soil. The distribution of potentially toxic elements in contaminated sediment along the Xiang River in Zhuzhou City shows the accumulation of PTEs in plants that grow on the sediment, and grasshoppers that feed on the plants, revealing potential risk to wildlife and humans from soil/sediment contamination. With increasing waste generation as the Chinese population grew and industrial activity increased from the 1950's, historical soil pollution has been an increasing issue with increased concern to stop new soil pollution and improve the efficiency of remediation. This motivated an interest to explore parameters influencing decision-making in soil remediation and how they impact on the implementation of the remediation.

1.2 Background and justification to the research

The quantity of contaminated land in China is 7.59 million ha that accounts for 8.2% of arable land in China and is contaminated with potentially toxic elements (PTEs) because of human activities, local high natural concentrations background and secondary enrichment in process of soil-formation (China Geological Survey, 2015). The burden of land contamination in China still needs to be assessed. In comparison for Europe there are estimated to be 11.7 million potentially contaminated sites and 2.5 million identified polluted sites as a result of point source contamination (Panagos *et al.*, 2013) stemming from historical industrial development. The soil/land contamination is mainly caused by municipal and industrial wastes (37%), followed by industrial and commercial reasons (33%). Around 60% of soil pollution is due to heavy metals and mineral oil. In terms of budget to manage all polluted sites, the cost is about 6 billion Euros every year (Panagos *et al.*, 2013). Another problem is that often pollution reappears after solidification or immobilization methods are compromised after many years.

Since the reform and opening-up of China in 1978, people's lives have been greatly improved, but the establishment of a corresponding solid waste management system and the concept of environmental protection appeared lag behind economic development and many facilities are only established after soil or agricultural land has been polluted with PTEs, which has poses threat to environment, wild animals and even affected people's lives.

The worldwide generation of solid waste (SW) has been growing massively in recent decades without any sign that it will slow down (Tiseo *et al.*, 2020). The increase is estimated from 2.01 billion tonnes today up to 3.40 billion tons by 2050 annually (Kaza *et al.*, 2018). Among most developing countries, open dumping is the main municipal solid waste (MSW) disposal method, some countries even attempt to use composting and vermicomposting as environmentally friendly approaches because of the low expenditure/cost required for converting waste into applicable forms (Sequeira, Chandrashekar and others, 2015). The growing generation and disposal of solid waste is the result of the following factors: economic growth, rapid urbanisation, growing population, and improvement to human living standards, leading to high resource requirements because of changing lifestyles (Bowen, 2018).

Inappropriate waste management leads to contamination in air, soil, water etc. Soil is the most important medium because the pollution could enter groundwater or air from the contaminated soil or sediment sites, however, it is undervalued in pollution prevention (for new contamination) and control (for old contamination). For example, leachate treatment is critically significant in waste management designing landfill and construction due to potential toxicity and harm to wildlife, human health, and the environment if it is allowed to leak out. In soil remediation, excavated polluted soil is categorized into hazardous and non-hazardous solid waste (HSW) and they will be managed within the waste hierarchy, of which recycling is the most desirable choice and landfill is the least. Therefore, soil remediation and the waste management system are very close to each other.

A lot of mineral deposits have been developed to extract useful materials, for example, the extensive exploitation of metals. In addition, discharges of gas and solid waste, drainage of liquid and overuse of agricultural fertiliser has combined to result in around 2.73 million ha (37%) of arable land being contaminated in Hunan region of central South China alone. Here 6% of total Chinese rice production is supported with only 3% of China being arable land. However, mine tailings also become a rising challenge for the solid waste management system (SWMS) because of increasing demand and pressure from waste landfills and recycling. Furthermore, ineffective and improper disposal of solid waste causes wide spread pollution of natural systems and potential health risks for human and wildlife (Akmal and Jamil, 2021). Recently, extensive programmes on land or soil contamination control and remediation have been initiated in China, however, improved mitigation strategies are

more urgent because of further resource exploitation regions with stricter regulations and environmental policies across the whole country.

The fast-paced development and large-scale applications related to soil remediation in contaminated sites required to address soil pollution in China poses several direct and indirect challenges for practitioners, regulators, and researchers (Shen, Li and Alessi, 2018). Technological methods needed for soil remediation industries have been discussed for future application in China (Chiang and Gu, 2015). Practitioners in industries face all these unanticipated problems and need to be ready to solve them during the life cycle of remediation projects. However, little research has been carried out to understand the challenges or difficulties in target setting, capital guarantees, and marketing products for soil remediation industries that might impede the further development of environmental remediation industries in China.

For the mineral sepiolite, there is a widespread application for rheological and catalytic purposes in industry. With 30% of the world's known reserves are located in China, and of that more than 70% (>20 million t) located in the Hunan region (Wang *et al.*, 2018), its extraction has been an important industrial process. Weathered Marine-sedimentary formations are found in Hunan Province, the deposit consists of sepiolite-palygorskite beds in Permian Qixia (Chihsia) marine carbonate-shale-siliceous formation and it provide material to produce high-quality sepiolite or its purification for business/industrial utilities (Fang, Fang and Yuan, 1988). Waste from this process and purification retain mineralogical characteristics with the potential for use in soil remediation. Tailings are defined as a waste or by-product without benefit and are generated in mining activities, from the purification of ores, and processing in production and some ores deposits that only contain a small amount of valuable minerals that are not suitable for exploitation (Adiansyah *et al.*, 2015).

Waste by-products can be used as amendments for contaminated soils and sediments remediation because of their environmental performance and economic benefits at site and regional scales (Karna *et al.*, 2017). The situation of waste by-product materials for in situ PTEs-polluted soil, land, and sediment remediation and application potential of the waste by-product was reviewed by (Karna *et al.*, 2017). Besides, the appropriateness of the application of waste by-products needs to be understood from an environment and human health perspective by comparing the waste concentrations to the corresponding toxicity of each metal, the actual likelihood of exposure, and the resulting risk (Karna *et al.*, 2017).

However, the research in SWM and soil/sediment remediation mainly concentrates on economic, environmental or social aspects of solid waste management, and the effectiveness of the waste application to keep or immobilize PTEs in soil remediation (Mendoza *et al.*, 2020; Chen *et al.*, 2018). There is less focus on the application of wastes as a component in remediation business, especially

the assessment of decision-making for utilization of wastes for remediation projects in developing countries. There is mounting research on the implementation of regulation internationally, consideration of cost efficiency and potential use of materials in remediation. Prior to 2017 China imported many waste materials as feedstock for primary product production. Therefore, studies of the impact of the waste ban in reducing new pollution, improvement of the efficiency in decision-making in development projects and assessment of potential remediation technology in decision-making will enhance the understanding of the impact of regulation in SWM and land use in China.

1.3 The aim of the research

This thesis aims to find regulation applied to prevent further soil pollution and assess its impact or influence in China, study in decision making support to improve efficiency in site remediation and assess new technologies in dealing with issues in both old and new pollution in soil in China. Developing countries globally must review their waste generation as a warning for the requirement of SD, specifically suitable solid waste management to control waste generation and prevent further soil/land pollution. A triangle description for regulation implemented, efficiency improvement in site remediation and technologies, which can be applied to help with remediation where national data, questionnaire feedback, interview result is available after research. No research was carried out before to state the impact of regulation, getting more details in remediation decision making and targeting sepiolite-based waste's application soil remediation directly.

Sepiolite based waste was shown as a case study as sepiolite reserve is widespread in Hunan province where rice is produced most but most soil is contaminated. The research will boost the ability to achieve SD and provide an guidance for regulations making and assessing current remediation sector infrastructure nationally. The study is based on comparing different treatment methods, technologies options, and regulations that had been considered or applied for soil/sediment contamination treatment by mixed approach of questionnaire and interview.

1.4 The research questions and objectives

The questions to answer in this thesis are detailed below: The research, therefore, analyses the business decision-making process and related parameters that influence the implementation of projects. It studies the interaction of waste management systems, soil remediation and potential application of solid waste as additives for soil remediation. Four research questions (RQ) were developed to achieve the goals of this study along with a series of specific objectives (SO).

RQ. 1: What is the regulation implemented to prevent further soil pollution?

- SO. 1.1: To collect all data and information pertaining to the regulation waste ban in China,

- SO. 1.2: To review the impact of the regulation to SWMS and land use with consideration soil contamination of preventing further soil contamination,

- SO. 1.3: To describe updates of the national standards and regulation for waste management in China.

RQ. 2: Can remediation and waste management businesses be mapped using site distribution and data from the website, online database and questionnaire feedback?

- SO. 2.1: To collect all data and information pertaining to the remediation and waste management businesses in China,

- SO. 2.2: To analyse the SWMS in China with consideration of waste material classification: MSW from cities and suburban areas, industrial solid waste (ISW) from industries and processing, and HW from contaminated sites and industries.

RQ. 3: What can be done to improve the land remediation efficiency and help the projects choose the most suitable remediation scheme?

- SO. 3.1: To develop a decision-making support in soil/sediment with consideration of the analysis of data or information collected in questionnaire and interview,

- SO. 3.2: To investigate the difference between remediation and waste management via budget, techniques and experiences for projects in China,

RQ. 4: Can solid waste be recycled to treat contamination in the remediation business using existing data?

- SO. 4.1: To assess the potential for standards, laws, and regulations updates to consider technologies, such as solidification/stabilization/immobilization, in the treatment/control of environmental hazard and prevention from further pollution,

- SO. 4.2: To quantify the business link between waste management and remediation via sepiolite waste application potential as a case study.

1.5 The original contributions of the research

The three contributions from this research derive from extensive literature review (see Chapter 2 below and its conclusions) and briefly include: evaluating the impact of the increased regulation of waste in China, and of regulatory reform on MSW and technological development needs. Secondly, exploring the decision-making in delivery of remediation projects and the structures of business involved in the sector. Thirdly, the case for re-use of by products from mineral processing to meet the need for large scale remediation of contaminated soils. A specific case study from a local region of China, used as a basis of local resources to deal with local pollution.

Chapter one introduces background information driving the focus of the research. The excessive soil pollution in China after the economic reform and open-up in 1978. The poor regard for environment protection which lagged well behind a focus on economic development. The scrutiny needed in the management of solid waste, minings, the regulations developed and the challenges in preventing further pollution (new pollution) and in treating historical contamination (old pollution). Research questions were developed to focus on three areas of knowledge gap.

1.6 Thesis structure

Figure 1.1 Flow diagram for the structure of the thesis

Chapter 2 Literature review

2.1 Introduction

The previous chapter describes the structure of this thesis and shows background to the research, the aim of this study, and questions and objectives that are significant to achieving the aim of this research. This chapter focuses on a general overview of literature relevant to the thesis topic, focuses on review of key research literature, and highlights those research gaps being filled by this thesis.

Section 2.2 shows the clue or start of the whole research with an overview of soil pollution in China, especially the situation for PTEs; Section 2.3 reveals solid waste management situation in China and the waste ban; section 2.4 explores decision making in the development of a waste management system and contaminated soil remediation; section 2.5 concentrates on possibility of achieving SDG 12 by land space-saving and reducing required landfills through waste application in remediation; section 2.6 describes the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on waste generation and remediation in China; section 2.7 shows summary and conclusion that including key challenges and knowledge gaps. The industry service range consists of waste treatment and waste management, remediation. A description for waste treatment, remediation and industries has not been discussed before and it is normally considered that there is little connection between waste treatment business and remediation business for industries.

2.2 Overview of soil pollution

Soil pollution or land contamination has been acknowledged as a problem in the world during past decades (Huysegoms and Cappuyns, 2017). More than 2.5 million potentially polluted areas/sites existed in Europe and 14% of them are waiting for appropriate remediation (Huysegoms and Cappuyns, 2017). Soil pollution site normally located near industrial/commercial activities, diffusing pollution, waste landfills etc. 3 billion tons of solid waste are produced and 90 million tons of them are hazardous in Europe (Panagos *et al.*, 2013). Mineral oil and PTEs are the main pollutants in European polluted areas and management of these sites are estimated to cost 6 billion euro every year (Panagos *et al.*, 2013; van Liedekerke *et al.*, 2017). Also, polluted sites are still detected daily in Asia (Li *et al.*, 2015). A national general survey on soil pollution was carried out by (MEP and MLR, 2014) in 2014 and the report revealed that 16.1% of soil survey points exceeded China's maximum pollution limits' value in Soil Environmental Quality Standard (GB 15618-1995). An estimated 7.59 million ha of arable land is reported to be contaminated with PTEs, which occupied 8.2% of the investigated arable land (China Geological Survey, 2015).

2.2.1 Soil pollution status in China

In China, rapid economic growth, improvement of living standards, and overconsumption have deteriorated the quality of the environment since the implementation of the Reform and Opening policy in 1978 (Yu *et al.*, 2020) (Yang *et al.*, 2021). Through increased public awareness of environmental problems, much more effort has been made to decrease the impact of pollution. However, soil or land contamination is still poorly perceived by normal citizens as it is only highlighted when they have been directly affected by pollution or they are aware of soil quality tests.

The impact of soil contamination started to draw public attention in 2004, when an incident took place at Songjiazhuang Subway Station in Beijing and three construction workers were poisoned (Sohu, 2004). Between 2013 and 2015, a total of 100 major soil remediation projects were undertaken (28, 40, and 32 each respective year), with farmland restoration only accounting for 10% of the projects (CII, 2016) (Xu *et al.*, 2017). The first soil contamination map was made available to the public in 2016 after public outcry over the discovery of soil contamination in the Changzhou School in 2015, which led to symptoms of eczema and skin inflammation for almost 500 students (IPEA, 2016). To manage the soil contamination at the source, 4500 key industrial enterprises and solid waste treatment and disposal units were identified as priority targets (including 3998 state-controlled pollution sources and 502 non-state-controlled pollution sources with environmental violations), as well as 729 key sector industrial parks, and these were registered on a soil pollution risk source distribution map by the institute of Public and Environmental Affairs of the PRC (IPEA, 2016). Soil pollution is a costly issue that may limit land redevelopment and hamper future construction (Xu *et al.*, 2017) with potential long-term health risks to humans and wildlife. The excavation and direct disposal methods ('dig and dump') are widely used to quickly resolve complex contamination problems as they are low-cost and consist of simple steps but increase the overall cost of the treatment of soil contamination. Public awareness of sustainable environmental management has increasingly discouraged non-sustainable landfill disposal of polluted soil or other solid waste (Eikelboom *et al.*, 2018).

As soil pollution has received wider public attention, the first national soil contamination survey was carried out by the Ministries of Environmental Protection and Land and Resources (MEPC/MLRC, 2014). The results showed that 16% of investigated land (6.3 million km², or two-thirds of China's total land area) was polluted beyond limits of acceptable standards, with 19% of investigated arable land polluted to limits of standards, and 83% of the contaminated sites contained excessive concentrations of potentially toxic elements (MEP/MLR, 2014). National technical guidelines have been implemented since 2014 (MEP, 2014a; MEP, 2014b; MEP, 2014c; MEP, 2014d) and subsequently updated in 2019 (MEE, 2018b; MEE, 2018c; MEE, 2019c; MEE, 2019h). More detailed

standards and regulations have also been implemented to guide soil pollution treatment. Treatment in China has also been based on regulations or limit guidelines from the US and other countries, increasing the diversity of treatment technologies available (Rajendran *et al.*, 2022).

The causes of contamination come from many human activities, such as hazardous solid waste (HSW) being inappropriately sent to landfill and additional potential pollution for soil and even groundwater from landfill leachates (Gautam *et al.*, 2019). New techniques include the application of specialist materials such as carbon nanotubes, composites, and magnetic materials, for example, for mercury removal (Wang *et al.*, 2020). Advances in soil stabilization as a treatment strategy have also produced impressive results with improved engineering properties for treated materials (Xi *et al.*, 2020). Many recycled materials from developed countries have been brought to China to supply raw resources for industrial development; however, improper dismantling of WEEE, and unqualified or illegal smuggling of wastes has resulted in toxic contaminants causing direct and indirect soil pollution (Hook and Reed, 2018).

There are serious environmental contamination and the associated human health issues derived from handling Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) imports. For example, prior to the the waste ban, 70% of the WEEE world-wide was imported by China through various paths. Guiyu Guangdong on the southeast coast of China was the biggest site to deal with electrical waste in China, covering more than 20 years of history in electrical waste recycling. There are fewer than 200 companies approved for e-waste recycling, which means it is impossible to deal with a huge volume of waste in the market. Greenpeace has conducted environmental surveys in Guiyu and surrounding villages since 2005. The test results of these samples consistently show that soil barium (Ba) concentrations in the villages are 20 times that of the background; chromium (Cr) and lead (Pb) content exceeded that of the Chinese standard (Environmental quality standard for soils (GB15618-1995) by >1,800 times and >2,000 times respectively (Xu, 2018).

The mean values of blood lead levels of children in Guiyu were $144.3 \pm 69.3 \mu\text{gL}^{-1}$, while 69.9% of children were considered of high lead burden with values of their blood lead levels exceed $100 \mu\text{gL}^{-1}$ (Liu, 2009). In addition, organic pollutants such as Polybrominated Diphenyl Ethers) are also widely distributed in Guiyu (Leung *et al.*, 2007) (Li *et al.*, 2019). Local water is so contaminated that residents could only rely on tap water from other places or bottled water. A large amount of unreported WEEE may be illegally shipped to developing countries, like China where valuable component materials are recycled inappropriately, impacting directly on human health and the environment (Geeraerts *et al.*, 2015).

2.2.2 Soil contaminated with potentially toxic elements in China

Environmental contamination is a persistent issue bringing more challenges to the health and development of the world (Uddin, 2017). Pollution caused by the excessive presence of potentially toxic elements (PTEs) is one of the common environmental issues and relates to soil, water, sediment, and air. The magnitude of the total release is difficult to accurately estimate given the diverse point and diffuse sources associated with human activity. However, it is reported that an estimated 8.2% of investigated arable land (7.59 million ha) in China is contaminated with PTEs due to (i) high natural concentrations (local geology), (ii) secondary enrichment in soil-forming process and (iii) human activities (China Geological Survey, 2015). The environmental problems caused by PTEs are not only affected by their concentrations but also by the different chemical species present under varying environmental conditions. The persistence of PTEs in the environment is prolonged because of resuspension and circulation in the atmosphere and transfer between terrestrial and aquatic systems (Shotyk *et al.*, 2003). This is particularly true in areas of mining, ore exploitation, and metallurgical activity where in addition to direct soil deposition, rivers and wetlands have been contaminated by the PTEs. In addition to the PTEs content, hazards from PTEs are also affected by environmental conditions. In areas where soil PTEs exceed regulatory standards due to high geological background without human activity, the impact from soil PTEs is relatively low and transfer in the food chain is not significant. It is easier for crops to absorb and accumulate PTEs in soils that have been introduced through human activity, making these sources, in general, more accessible to wider dispersal due to chemical reactivity and bioavailability (China Geological Survey, 2015). With the changes of soil environmental conditions, a high pollution level of soils with PTEs may lead to migration of contaminants into adjacent areas, which consequently generate hazard to the environment and living organisms (Twaróg *et al.*, 2020). High quantities of PTEs existed in the wastewater from mining, chemical processing plants. The contamination was discharged into the environment as stable forms. Where PTE ions are stable in wastewater or other contaminated aqueous environments, they can be ingested and accumulated easily by aquatic and terrestrial organisms as they are not biodegradable, with the potential to threaten human health through transfer in the food chain (Ajao *et al.*, 2020).

In the management of industrial wastewater, attention has been paid to the treatment of PTEs, such as Cu, Zn, Pb, Cd, Hg, As, Cr and Ni (Ihsanullah *et al.*, 2016) as these are the PTEs more strongly influenced by human activity. Many physical, chemical and biological techniques have been applied to remove PTEs from wastewater including chemical precipitation, physical adsorption, electrolysis, biological accumulation, reverse osmosis and ion exchange (Ihsanullah *et al.*, 2016). Adsorption is one of the most viable methods for pollution treatment, owing to its relatively straightforward application, high efficiency and insensitivity to the toxicities of contaminants. Activated carbon is

probably one of the most widely applied adsorbents with many examples of application to remediate contaminated soil (Sörengård *et al.*, 2019), sediment (Rakowska *et al.*, 2014), atmosphere (Huang *et al.*, 2019) and water (Hadi *et al.*, 2015). More novel carbonaceous materials have also been studied for application in land/soil/sediment treatment, including a wide range of nanomaterials (Shahamirifard *et al.*, 2016), such as graphene oxide (Isari *et al.*, 2018; Zhao *et al.*, 2011) and carbon nanotubes (Tofighy and Mohammadi, 2015). However, these systems often require extensive synthesis, purification, and as viable treatment technologies still require further optimization. In pursuit of solutions within the life cycle approach to reduce the environmental impact of technologies, more inexpensive and low-cost materials still need to be sought.

2.3 Solid waste management situation in China

A lot of research has been focused on the solid waste effects or problems to humans, wild animals or the environment. However, much less study has focused on the definition details of the solid waste which is changing with time. Waste is anything that contains scrap effluent or materials or any other unwanted substance from the application, processing or article that needs to be disposed of as broken, abandoned and contaminated.

2.3.1 Defining solid waste and SWMS

Solid waste is composed of MSW, ISW and agricultural waste etc. Solid waste from mining belongs to ISW. For example, a huge amount sepiolite based waste is produced from sepiolite mining and processing. MSW is the solid waste produced from citizens' daily lives or activities that are related to citizens' daily lives, including household waste, hospital waste etc. ISW are consist of mining waste barren rock, mineral processing tailings etc. Agricultural waste are consist of crop straw and livestock excrement. All solid waste might be potentially harmful to human health if they are not disposed of properly. A SWMS aims to manage the major problem of urban and ISW, with the continuing deterioration of the issue due to the increasing consumption all over the world (Adamides *et al.*, 2009). Recently, considerable attention has been paid to the MSW management system or mode in different countries and cities, such as Shanghai in China (Minghua *et al.*, 2009), Ireland (Desmond, 2006) and Greece etc.

2.3.2 Waste management system in China

The waste management system in mainland China includes MSW management, ISW management, and HW management. MSW is defined differently in a degree of complexity. For solid waste management practitioners, the practical or realistic version is favoured. Regardless of the developmental status (developed or developing), the MSW generation is mainly from densely

populated metropolitan regions, especially in inner-city areas, which differ from those generations from suburbs, rural places and small communities (Diaz *et al.*, 2020). The types of technology are available for resource recovery of the organic component consisting converting it into methane (combustible gas), transforming it into compost (soil amendment) and hydrolyzing the cellulosic components into glucose. Though methane production has been used in processing settleable sewage solids, it is not used for the treatment of solid wastes frequently, seldomly used for MSW treatment (Diaz *et al.*, 2020).

MSW management is defined as a system that includes waste generation, collection, selection, classification, transport, processing, storage, and treatment, while solid waste disposal needs to obey principles of health, engineering, economics and other environmental considerations, which also has interacted with the public attitudes (Schübeler, Christen and Wehrle, 1996; Desmond, 2006; Martinez-Sanchez *et al.*, 2017).

Therefore, MSWMS includes all financial, administration, regulations, designing, and engineering characteristics with the steps of solutions/technologies to all challenges of solid waste treatment in municipal regions.

ISW comes from industrial activities and it consists of hazardous, non-hazardous, recyclable, non-recyclable, reusable, and nonreusable solid waste that might be regarded as useless during related products manufacturing (Soliman and Moustafa, 2020; Maczulak, 2010; USEPA, 2011).

HSW is material discarded and it might be harmful or dangerous to human health and the environment because of its properties or characteristics such as reactivity, corrosivity, ignitability and toxicity (Rosenfeld and Feng, 2011). It is generated from facilities and processes including hospitals, factories, discarded electronics, military bases and construction sites (Rosenfeld and Feng, 2011). In China, HSW is listed on the national HW list or defined/identified to be harmful or dangerous following national identification methods, standards or criteria prescribed in the official documents (Li, Xu and Li, 2018). Ineffective poor HSW management is harmful or detrimental to human health, wild lives, and the environment due to its toxic ingredients exposure. Illegal and poor waste management is the main cause of land, sediment, soil, and groundwater pollution in the world (Fazzo *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, more regulations, laws, and departmental rules on HWM have been released and revised in the past five years to improve efficiency of the HWM at local or national levels in China.

Chinese domestic waste production increased rapidly recently, the amount increase in MSW in mainland China from 214 million tons in 2001 to 311 million tons in 2019 with a total increase of 45.3% (a growth of 79.3% for Chinese cities and a decrease of 12.7% for counties, respectively) (MHURD, 2020).

There is no integrated waste management system for all solid waste management in mainland China. There are MSW management, HSW management, ISW management, and recycling solid waste management systems separately.

2.3.3 Waste ban impact globally and situation in China

Waste management is getting more challenging due to increasing waste quantity generated from various paths, such as technology development, population growth, rapid economic increase and overconsumption. In 2016, waste generation is around 2.01 billion tonnes globally and it will go up to 3.4 billion tonnes by 2050 (Kaza *et al.*, 2018). Though before 2017, China had been keeping importing recycled solid waste, which was regularly collected and classified in developed countries, and then used in industries as raw resources for decades. The Chinese government implemented 'a plan to ban entry of foreign waste and reform the administrative system for solid waste import' (Sun, 2019) in July 2017.

The global waste recycling was changed by the waste ban that diverted most amount of solid waste to Southeast Asia countries like Malaysia (Tran, Goto and Matsuda, 2021), which resulted in a sudden increase in waste streams in these new destination countries and serious overloaded conditions, for example, the collapse waste trade in plastic leads to 92.4% of countries being overloaded with the plastic scrap and around 6% of all countries in the world going through over 1.5 times normal annual load of plastic scrap (Li *et al.*, 2021). Though the solid waste management of these new destination countries would finally attain improvement of more capacity to manage more waste import with more construction of new facilities or buildings (Hook and Reed, 2018), it is still a potential health risk as small-scale waste processors will manage the diverted without standards or regulations implemented (Hook and Reed, 2018). As a result, Southeast Asia countries are due to freeze the solid scrap import, which will boost the establishment of the alternative mechanisms to manage the scrap internally for waste producers like the USA, UK, Europe, and Japan etc. (WMR, 2018).

2.3.4 The waste hierarchy

Appropriate solid waste management is a significant prerequisite to develop sustainably for cities (Papargyropoulou *et al.*, 2014), it is a key utility service that the external 'image' of a city and the public health depend on (Wilson *et al.*, 2015). Nowadays, solid waste management is strongly encouraged by rules from the waste hierarchy, a principle applied in waste management, which shows waste management practices' priorities (Van Ewijk and Stegemann, 2016). In an attempt to clarify the literature on various steps that was used as 'waste' prevention, reduction, and recovery, the European Commission's Waste Framework in the latest version of Directive 2008/98/EC

(WFD2008) suggests that technologies on the treatment were made on both ends of life waste and 'waste hierarchy' among all members of European Union (Gharfalkar *et al.*, 2015). Besides, SDG 12 calls for 'Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns' and SDG 12.5 also calls for 'By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse'. How is the waste hierarchy trying to achieve SD of waste management for a country? Reducing material throughput is the suitable decision criterion to attain sustainability as it is easier to measure material flows than material associated environmental impacts (Hinterberger, Luks and Schmidt-Bleek, 1997). Besides,

Concepts of planetary boundaries revealed that the natural system can only provide finite environmental functions and resources, such as fuel gas (Rockström *et al.*, 2009). Production, consumption, and disposal are all associated with environmental impacts with consideration of the planetary boundaries (Van Ewijk and Stegemann, 2016). To reduce material throughput, two essential aspects have been described: the reduction of the waste outputs and the reduction of raw material inputs, which led to a reduction in waste outputs (Van Ewijk and Stegemann, 2016). The waste ban reduced the raw material import for China, does it help reduce the waste outputs and further reduce the environmental impact as the result of the amount decrease in the raw material used, its processing and its product manufacturing? Besides the environmental impact, any other impact on the economy or industry it has in China? Reducing the waste generation or outputs is the only reason for the implementation of the waste ban?

2.4 Can a waste management system develop sustainably?

The great diversity of environment industry development together with the interaction between industries, waste management and remediation lead to their impact to manifest them in different ways (Prasad, de Jesus Alves and Nunes, 2021). Legal regulation encourages industries to invest more money in sustainable contamination remediation and control. To favor the eco-system balance, practical socio-environmental complexity in a different part of the world was described in affirmative propositions. The remediation strategies must consider using waste as a potential resource to apply because of its sustainability and low cost for pollution treatment/land remediation of polluted areas.

The concept of SD has been mentioned, described, and cited for scientific study about the environment in published papers and it also has played a paradigm or positive role in redevelopment (Alvarado-Herrera *et al.*, 2017; Emas, 2015). The concept has been incorporated in national law and regulations of many countries in the world (Luke, 2005; Wu and Guo, 2020). Some industries developed a framework to make sure the sustainable indicators for their sector, such as the mining and minerals industry (Azapagic, 2004). It has also been applied in addressing problems or issues of

business or industries (Amran *et al.*, 2015; Dangelico and Pontrandolfo, 2015), urban development (Yang, Xu and Shi, 2017; Shcherbina, Gorbenkova and Slepnev, 2017), agricultural production (Czyżewski and Smędzik-Ambroży, 2015; Kanter *et al.*, 2018) and a conceptual foundation of circular economy (Corona *et al.*, 2019; Dantas *et al.*, 2021) as a theoretical approach.

2.4.1 Contaminated soil or solid waste?

SDGs 3 calls for 'Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages and SDGs 3.9 calls for 'By 2030, substantially reduce the number of deaths and illnesses from hazardous chemicals and air, water and soil pollution and contamination'. Solid waste can be a contamination source, which might cause a lot of environmental impacts, especially during inappropriate waste management or disposal management of landfills (Kijjanapanich, Annachatre and Lens, 2014). More research has been carried out to assess contamination/pollution of soil in the dumpsite of MSW (Ali *et al.*, 2021). As one part of the SWMS, dumpsites were used to dispose considerable amount of waste, it collects household wastes and industrial wastes, which generate various pollutants and bring negative environmental impact (Singh *et al.*, 2011). Dumpsites could be contamination sources of a wide range of contaminants because of their improper management (Al-Khatib *et al.*, 2015; Kaszubkiewicz, Gałka and Kawałko, 2011). Pollution occurred at dumpsites area and their possible transformation to non-contaminated sites requires regular monitoring or surveillance around dumpsites zone to assess possible health risk of local citizens (Ali *et al.*, 2021).

Some pollution exists in both the contaminated soil and solid waste, or because some polluted soil could only be defined as contaminated waste, which means shared methods are used to deal with both polluted soil and solid waste. Research on bioremediation for contaminated soil or solid waste has been carried out (Dhal *et al.*, 2013). The contaminated soil might be defined as HSW or regular solid waste for off-site HSW landfills or regular landfills because of their high concentration of contamination in soil or qualified concentration of pollution under regulations (Dermatas *et al.*, 2006). The regulatory determination of remediation techniques or requirements for some material that is toxic following regulations, which decide the classification of the material to be HSW or hazardous contaminated sediment/soil (Dermatas *et al.*, 2006). There are essential implications in the disposal methods or strategies of treatment regulations/standards pertaining to the planning, design, implementation, and cost of remediating pollution or materials in polluted sites (Dermatas *et al.*, 2006).

If the content of any hazardous material in the solid waste leachate that is prepared by the method 'HJ/T 299 (Solid waste-Extraction procedure for leaching toxicity-sulphuric acid & nitric acid method, Environmental Protection Industry Standard of PRC)' exceeds the concentration limit value listed in the national standard 'Identification standards for hazardous wastes- Identification for

extraction toxicity (GB 5085.3-2007)' in PRC, the solid waste is determined to be a HSW with leach toxicity characteristics.

2.4.2 Decision making in soil remediation

Among the 1351 soil sites in the 188 solid waste treatment and disposal sites investigated, the contamination concentration of 21.3% of the soil sites exceeded the limits value in Soil Environmental Quality Standard (GB 15618-1995) and most contaminants are inorganic pollution, while organic pollution is serious in waste incineration and landfills (MEP and MLR, 2014). The identification and characterization of ISW in contaminated sites is no longer an academic interest but also an essential consideration to practitioners in remediation sector, as well as government departments and legal organizations for environmental pollution monitoring, management, and remediation. China faces severe soil contamination problems due to industrialization (An *et al.*, 2017). Some persistent organic pollutants (POPs), PTEs and radioactive hazardous wastes entered the soil or groundwater in some provinces of PRC due to inappropriate e-waste management (Li and Achal, 2020), treatment or disposal of the industrial waste (Zhao *et al.*, 2015), leakage of landfills (Liu *et al.*, 2013). The polluted or contaminated land/sediment/soil has caused great threats to wild animals, human health, and the local environment (Mishra *et al.*, 2019). Soil contamination remediation has been paid much more attention because of its urgency and significance (Hu, Sun and Wu, 2019). However, the risk of various strategies or implementation for remediation might bring second contamination or cause more contaminated soil later. To deal with the issue, various technologies/strategies in soil remediation have been studied, developed, and assessed (Yao *et al.*, 2012; Ren *et al.*, 2018).

As mentioned above, various technologies or strategies could be applied in soil pollution treatment. However, various methods used in soil remediation may have various performances that lead to different degree secondary contaminations and it also results in different impacts to society (Ganiyu, Martinez-Huitle and Rodrigo, 2020; Ren *et al.*, 2018; Beames *et al.*, 2014) (Naseri-Rad *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, to choose the most suitable method or strategy from various technologies' alternatives is difficult for the practitioners/stakeholders because of the complexity of contamination and consideration of multi-criteria (Jaskulak, Grobelak and Vandenbulcke, 2020; Cipullo *et al.*, 2019; Naseri-Rad *et al.*, 2020). The consideration of SD is incorporated in deciding the best strategy from various available alternative of technologies for decision-makers/practitioners/stakeholders (Tripathi *et al.*, 2017; Mazarji *et al.*, 2021; Manzardo *et al.*, 2012). To assess sustainability provides implications and understanding to the practitioners to promote the achievement of SD by guiding them to decide best scenario or technology among various alternatives (An *et al.*, 2017). To assess sustainability of techniques applied for soil/sediment/land remediation can compare the sustainability's performance of various methods/technologies and select the best suitable one.

Since the mid-to-late 2000s, a new concept or discipline of 'sustainable remediation' has emerged initially from the international organizations and national departments or institutes, which reflects a realization that economic, environmental, and social impact can be brought in achieving risk-based remediation goals (Rizzo *et al.*, 2016). Recently, these targets were updated in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN, 2015). The 2030 agenda (including 17 SDGs) was established by the United Nations in 2015 to end poverty, and prosperity etc., among them the SDG15 gets involved with an explicit concern over land degradation (UN, 2015). Therefore, to develop appropriate criteria to assess sustainability of methods for soil pollution treatment plays a significant role in choosing the best strategy for soil/sediment/land remediation. In addition, the decision-making process needs all stakeholders involved in the engagement at an appropriate level (Hou and Li, 2018).

Many studies are focusing on various impactors that might affect decision making on the selection of a strategy for soil remediation. For instance, an overview was carried out and the result shows that chemical speciation could be applied as a strategic pathway for decision making in soil remediation of toxic metal contamination because of its significance in risk assessment before decision making (Adamu *et al.*, 2013). The implication indicated that the chemical forms of the PTEs should be generalized as a threshold to apply remediation techniques rather than the total concentrations of PTEs in the environment. A field study was carried out to assess feasibility of technologies to treat contaminated sites impacted by various ethanol contents of gasohol (Steiner *et al.*, 2018). To assess feasible remediation technologies, gasoline-ethanol blends labeled as E25 (ethanol: gasoline is 25:75 v/v) and E10 (ethanol: gasoline is 10:90 v/v) were carried out under nitrate bio-stimulation and natural attenuation and the monitoring period lasted over 11 and 6 years. The results showed that the natural geochemical situations were enough to support the anaerobic biodegradation of ethanol and BTEX (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and xylenes compounds in E10 site, which occurred under reduction processes of nitrate, iron, and sulfate. Nitrate bio-stimulation was carried out to enhance pollutants biodegradation in E25 site, biodegradation rates of BTEX were lower than the biodegradation rate of E10 site under MNA (monitored natural attention), while Ethanol was biodegraded at similar rates in both circumstances. Therefore, MNA provides higher degradation rates than nitrate bio-stimulation for the lower content of ethanol (i.e. 10% v/v) blended with gasohol, which could alleviate ecosystem disturbances and the overall cost of remediation (Steiner *et al.*, 2018). All methods in these studies could be helpful to decide suitable technology for decision-makers from various techniques alternatives for soil/sediment/land remediation. While two more issues need to be highlighted: one is about the categories of soil remediation for their sustainability on basis of land characters of sites, and the other one is about ranking/scoring the factors that contributed to the total criteria. To design a framework applied to assess sustainability of

contaminated site remediation strategies, it involves various multiple criteria in decision-making and that might conflict to each other (Afgan and Graça Carvalho, 2000; Ren *et al.*, 2015; Sarkkinen, Kujala and Gehör, 2019), which can decide most suitable method or strategy for decision-makers to promote SD in site remediation. Besides, deciding the most suitable strategy for soil pollution treatment requires various criteria or factors that includes real conditions, economic consideration, natural resource, environmental, social structure, and experience. A sustainable decision-making support framework is needed for prioritizing the alternative strategies for both soil/sediment/land remediation and solid waste management, and even employing the decision-making technology that considered multiple criteria to achieve the goal of SDGs 12 and SDGs 15.

2.4.3 The problem or challenge for the soil remediation industry in China

China is facing an increasing challenge and pressure from soil quality protection and remediation recently. Urban industrial site pollution led to more than 333 thousand ha of abandoned land annually and the mining pollution results in more than 2 million ha of tailing area/zone that cannot be re-used (Hu *et al.*, 2018). There is a rapid development of remediation though the remediation sector is still at its beginning stage in mainland of China. The remediation industry is learning to deal with challenges such as a small number of large-scale projects (Ma *et al.*, 2016), insufficient regulation and law (Jiang *et al.*, 2022), a vast number of existed polluted sites (Li *et al.*, 2022), limited funding and budget (Yang, 2016; Song *et al.*, 2019), chaotic industry (Hu *et al.*, 2018), lack of sustainability awareness (Zhou *et al.*, 2022) etc.

2.5 Waste application potential in remediation

2.5.1 Sustainable consideration for remediation in China

The SDGs 11 calls for 'making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable'. China has been the second largest economy in the world and its rapid economy growth largely relies on the cost of serious environmental contamination during the past three decades (Sun *et al.*, 2021a). Land/soil pollution cleanup is an emerging business and it is mostly driven by land redevelopment, which may lead to issues ranging from environmental under-protection to over-engineering of remediation. Extraction of various mining has led to vast degraded and damaged areas, which also bring by-product, such as abandoned sepiolite tailings. For remediation business, the contaminants cleaning up processes are soil pollution remediation site projects consists of natural attenuation, composting, landfarming, contained slurry bioreactor, thermal desorption, soil vapour extraction, bioventing, landfilling, incineration and soil washing (Waste, Response and Support, 1997). Soil remediation and recycling can be categorized in an "R5" recovery operation on basis of the European legislative framework (Commission, 2008; Gharfalkar *et al.*, 2015).

The development of sustainable remediation only focused on bioremediation and phytoremediation. Little research was carried out on the research of adoption of sustainable remediation in the industry. To optimize the application of limited nature resources, encourage remediation innovation of techniques, and set up a mature remediation market, the concept of sustainable remediation can be integrated into projects under proper design and cautious implementation. A list of sustainability considerations was shown in table 2.1. Besides, nature-based solutions for polluted land/sediment/soil remediation and redevelopment of treated land in cities were reviewed. The main characteristics of NBS, key technology choices, limitations, and case studies were summarized (Song *et al.*, 2019). Stabilization is one of the nature-based remediation technologies, with social benefit of eliminating waste and improving aesthetics; an economic benefit of enhancing flood control, lower operating expenditure and dust suppression; but it also shows the disadvantage in risks of contaminants release with soil condition status change and time goes (Song *et al.*, 2019).

Table 2.1 List of sustainability considerations (Hou and Al-Tabbaa, 2014).

No.	Sustainability considerations
1	'Reducing site worker's risk'
2	'Minimizing contaminants left behind'
3	'Minimizing local scale secondary environmental impacts (e.g., noise, dust, odour, local air quality, traffic, etc.)'
4	'Using in situ remediation rather than ex situ remediation'
5	'Minimizing waste generation'
6	'Minimizing risk to ecological systems'
7	'Minimize long-term management (e.g., monitoring) requirement'
8	'Reducing life-cycle cost'
9	'Enhancing reuse and recycling'
10	'Encourage public participation and stakeholder involvement'
11	'Using environmentally friendly products'
12	'Minimize energy use, increasing energy efficiency'
13	'Using sustainable energy'
14	'Bring prosperity to disadvantaged community'

2.5.2 A popular technology for remediation in China?

Cement kilns had been the first choice for remediation practices and widely applied for cleanup activities, followed by in-situ solidification/stabilization (S/S) treatment, ex-situ S/S treatment, landfills, and mechanical soil aeration technologies for the remediation market in China (Ma *et al.*, 2018). Cement kiln co-processing of polluted sediment/soil gets excavation and transportation of polluted soil to cement plants where the contaminated soil was applied as alternative raw material and was incinerated into cement clinkers (Yan *et al.*, 2014). However, the co-processing projects have decreased as the specification of procedures/steps for ex-site polluted soil disposal, which identified HSW products such as cement clinkers (MEE, 2019a). The cost of identification is as much as the cost

of some projects for small scale contaminated sites and the identification process also takes several months which leads to project delay (Liang *et al.*, 2022). The delays are costly for developers, undermine their economic viability and decrease the profitability of redevelopment projects (Liang *et al.*, 2022).

A decade long survey was carried out on 150 projects of heavy metal polluted soils treated by stabilization, which showed that 80% and 20% of studied projects were treated by ex-situ S/S and in-situ S/S respectively (Ma *et al.*, 2022). The result also revealed that landfilling was the main strategy among various soil reuse methods to dispose of soil following stabilization and remediation. The re-application or reuse of appropriated treated soil is preferred to landfill as solid waste treatment (Ma *et al.*, 2022). To reduce landfill loads and budget for both remediation and waste disposal nowadays, different regions might own different resources or potential for both PTEs treatment and re-application of solid waste.

2.5.3 How does sepiolite-base waste get involved?

The impact of the waste ban on remediation has led to attention transfer from pure waste management to related remediation, where bad waste management ever resulted in pollution in groundwater and soil. The soil/ sediment is contaminated with various pollutants from the industrial revolution or daily lives (Tang *et al.*, 2008; Ossai *et al.*, 2020; Yuniati, 2018). There is not any proper effects-directed analysis method or treatment method to diagnose or deal with the contaminants until recently because of the characteristics of concealment, accumulation and weak restorability of pollution in soil/sediment (Burgess *et al.*, 2013; Sethi and Gupta, 2020). Organic pollutants (e.g. pesticides, hydrocarbons) and PTEs are two main contaminants for soil pollution, which leads to global environmental issues as a result of rapid industrial development (Lohmann *et al.*, 2007). Both the organic pollutants and PTEs exist in soil simultaneously because of pollutant release from several sources like waste incineration, vehicle exhaust emissions, metal smelting and burning of nature resources, such as coal or oil (Jiang *et al.*, 2015).

For the industrial application of waste in remediation, other remediation procedures physically and chemically eliminate or stop the transfer pathways of contaminants from polluted soil/land to humans, wild animals etc., of which immobilization has been recommended as the best available technique by (EC-European Commission, 2006). The decision of strategies and selection of a proper additive is significant and essential for successful immobilization. Huge production and recycled waste materials from various processing industries might be possible to be applied for immobilization, such as cement powder (Kim *et al.*, 2021), eggshells and oyster shells (Lim *et al.*, 2013). Sepiolite-based waste is the material that is of potential to be applied for immobilization in soil or sediment remediation.

2.6 The impact of pandemic on waste generation and remediation projects in China

The world was affected by a novel coronavirus (COVID-19) that takes the responsibility for a severe respiratory syndrome since December 2019 (Hui *et al.*, 2020). Much efforts has been taken to prevent and control the virus transmission due to the disease severity, high contagiousness, and shortage of safe and effective vaccine (Silva *et al.*, 2021). Measures like home isolation, social distancing, and total city lockdown were taken by the government for reducing infection rate, which largely changed the lifestyles of citizens in China and increase online shopping (Ding *et al.*, 2022) that might result in more delivery packages generated. It has led to a decline of 44% and 43% in money spending on goods and services (Chen, Qian and Wen, 2021) and an increase in medical waste generation (Ye *et al.*, 2022), which might bring the pressure on waste disposal for waste management sector. Under various pressures from declining demand, stagnant production, tight logistics, and unemployment caused by the pandemic, the projects' operation and products processing have been seriously affected in companies, especially urgent for survival of small and medium firms (Sun *et al.*, 2021b; Yuan and Wang, 2019).

In addition, one of the challenges is the finance problem for soil remediation and global efforts for soil remediation still rely on public funding (Lin *et al.*, 2022). Various financing instruments, for example, concessional loans, and climate fund investment, were employed by some jurisdictions in the world, but these are not enough (Lin *et al.*, 2022). Years of development progress has been destroyed by the pandemic that leads to setbacks to all financial sources for SD (Lin *et al.*, 2022). The financial challenge and restriction on the travelling might hinder and even stop processing the carry out of remediation projects.

2.7 Summary and conclusion

The serious soil contaminated site was shown by describing data from soil samples and children's blood lead levels of Guiyu Guangdong, which shows some reason why the ban started. The chapter provides a review that addresses a broad research topic and reveals key challenges for many environmental improvements in developing countries (including China). Key challenges are:

Inadequate research for policy updates and impact on soil pollution in China. This challenge can be addressed by collecting more public information about the policy, which aims to help the government of countries with similar considerations in policy decision making.

Inadequate principle and stakeholder engagement in the industry. This can be overcome with increased collaboration with all stakeholders, particularly decision-makers and practitioners in the business.

Inadequate assessment on the potential of waste recycling. This will be addressed by reviewing the potential of waste recycling and its application in soil pollution treatment. The research efforts such as this thesis may provide the direction needed to carry out SD for industries.

This chapter also shows essential general knowledge gaps which form the themes of the research included in this thesis. SDGs 3.9 calls for 'By 2030, substantially reduce the number of deaths and illnesses from hazardous chemicals and air, water and soil pollution and contamination'. Innovation and resilience will be significant in responding to the SDGs when the Covid-19 pandemic happens.

From the literature review, essential knowledge gaps identified are:

Knowledge Gap 1: Regulation implementation can be changed from the funding support in remediation to 'zero waste' creativity in waste management to deal with land site remediation capital guarantee pressure. However, there is very little research focused on providing knowledge of the impact of waste ban implementation to stop further soil pollution after year's huge financial burden on soil remediation. It was suggested that impact assessment of the solid waste import ban on soil pollution treatment in China.

Knowledge Gap 2: Beside regulation implementation to stop further new soil contamination, remediation efficiency improvement can be attained if more details of decision making could be found. There is little knowledge involving with decision-making and SD consideration in carry out of projects for remediation sector and industries.

Knowledge Gap 3: Hunan province have been paid attention because of its severe soil pollution and production of sepiolite and its waste in China. However, there is little knowledge involving with new technology that can be applied to treat soil contamination, which makes the best use of existing local solid waste for local contamination treatment easily, especially during the pandemic restriction period.

Chapter 3 Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the mixed research approach and describes the key methodological choices in carrying out this study. To deal with the research question, the study focused on soil pollution sector in China, a desk study of waste management policies change to reduce further soil contamination from waste, a questionnaire/interview survey that aims to attain the decision-making support in soil remediation projects and understand the impact of the support on implementation of the projects, and a desk based case study for remediation decision making: sepiolite solid waste application in soil remediation. The chapter also considered the whole research design, rationale for methods used, data collection process, and data analysis techniques. There are four main parts in the chapter. The first part puts forward the research question and provides an overview of its analysis; the second part gives a justification for employing a step-by-step analysis; the third part shows the research design and rationales the research process, the validity and reliability of all collected data; and final part (the previous overview) provides considerations on methodology before continuing to describe research findings in chapter four.

A questionnaire was used to assess the findings in the desk study, collect qualitative and quantitative data to understand decision making support better and answer the related research questions. Interview was applied to cross checking answers in feedbacks of questionnaires from respondents or findings from the desk study and questionnaires. A case study was further discussed potential application of waste in soil remediation and consideration on budget cost efficiency in decision making in remediation projects. The desk study, questionnaire/interview and case study were used to cross checking results and findings of each methods. Questionnaire and interview were carried out to testify or verify questions' design to justify their processes and further carry-out. To improve the credibility of research findings, qualitative and quantitative methods were combined. Results from one method can be illustrated with results from the other method in this research.

3.2 Research hypothesis

Research questions were presented in Chapter 1. Before embarking on the research, my hypothesis were: a, regulation can reduce new pollution though it might have limitations; b, there are decision making parameters in soil remediation which can improve efficiency in projects; c, there is new technology that can be applied to soil remediation if the parameters were under consideration in soil remediation.

3.3 Research design

Research design is the outline or plan to describe the specific details of the pertinent empirical research on basis of the abstract conceptual research problem (Van Wyk, 2012). In other words, it holds all major parts of this research together logically to answer the core questions (Trochim and Donnelly, 2001). It can be regarded as a master plan or guidebook of the research to conduct study steps carried out. A research design shows how the research question will be answered, how knowledge gap will be fixed, the types of data required and the detailed methods applied to do data collection and analysis (Smith, 2003; Johnson, Onwuegbuzie and Turner, 2007).

Moreover, the validity and reliability of research results are determined by a proper decision making on the research approach and design, which are results of the methodology choice made on research objectives and questions (Barriball and While, 1994). Therefore, designing the investigation was an interpretive and descriptive study and results were attained with help of various qualitative and quantitative methods. At beginning, a desk study was carried out on impact of the waste ban because it is the biggest regulation implemented internationally to deal with increasing solid waste generation and reduce further soil contamination (results were shown in Appendix I). Desk study is a better method to know more about updates of regulation and its change and aim for a developing country like China.

Then, a questionnaire (results were shown in Appendix I) was chosen as it helps us understand support in decision making in soil remediation and impact of those parameters in projects quantitatively and qualitatively, with sending questionnaires via social application to employees/staffs or stakeholders who work as policymakers, planning department, consultancy companies, remediation service providers, construction companies, public institutions in remediation sector in China. A lot of information on companies, conferences organizers and forums was collected to assess their potential participation in the questionnaire feedback collection, however, few possibilities to get access to these people because of restriction on traveling for COVID19 consideration. The questionnaire was sent to social applications QQ group or Wechat group that focused on soil remediation as there are more potential participants in social app groups individually, with marketing it in groups to encourage people participation, then share the link to people who might help with marketing in their working circles that related to soil remediation. The questionnaire was updated after suggestions from a group selected for the questionnaire feedback or the group discussion (results were shown in Appendix I).

The interview helps to understand more deeply support in decision making in soil remediation and impact of those parameters in projects quantitatively and qualitatively, with sending questionnaires via social application to employees/staffs or stakeholders who work as policymakers,

planning department, consultancy companies, remediation service providers, construction companies, public institutions in remediation sector in China.

3.4 Selecting the study area

China is a country in East Asia, officially called the PRC. It has the most population of more than 1.4 billion in the world. It is the world's third-largest country with a total area of around 9.6 million square kilometres. Hunan Province is a provincial-level administrative region of the PRC. It is adjacent to Chongqing Province, Guizhou Province to the west, adjacent to Guangdong Province and Guangxi Province to the south, and connected to the south of Hubei Province in the north, with an area of 21,800 square meters. The population is more than 66 million (Wikipedia, 2023).

3.5 The research sample

For fieldwork on interviews and questionnaires, key participants in the remediation sector were identified to include: Politicians (policymakers); Planners; Public institutions whose functions affect remediation; remediation service providers and their users.

3.6 Data collection

Questions were focused on the regulations implemented to prevent further soil pollution and decision making support to improve treatment efficiency for treatment of old contamination and reduce new pollution in site remediation projects. Further detail requested on identifying new technology that can be applied for pollution treatment and make it more cost effective in site remediation and how the waste management system could consider the application of recycled waste to soil remediation. This also advances the aim to discover the influence COVID19 has on SWMS and soil/land remediation.

In the investigation of the data collected from the implemental processes of soil remediation and updates of waste management policy, the research takes a combination of qualitative research methods: desk study, questionnaires, interview, and documents collection and analysis. The combination of methods for data collection and analysis and various perspectives increases the credibility and reliability of this study, allowing for crosschecking the discoveries and conclusions from different angles. The triangulation of methods and data sources helps to enhance the objectivity of the research procedure (Grix, 2004). Decision-making is very sensitive to preconceptions and perspectives of stakeholders or people who get involved in the investigation. To reduce or neutralize the risk of subjectivity, exploring all perspectives and theoretical considerations concerning the data is trying to seek objectivity in the research (Eisner, 1992). Complete objectivity is impossible, however,

he suggests researchers employ methods that reduce personal subjectivity to build their argument to a degree of confidence free from bias as much as possible (Eisner, 1992). The various sources of evidence, information and primary data collected and used in the research should minimize bias and help enhance the validity and credibility of the findings (Bowen, 2009). Three methods applied to data collection (desk study, questionnaire, interview and case study) will be explained and how they support each other to make the research credible and how these methods were employed in the research process will be described.

3.6.1 Desk study

The review was performed using following database or website: literature, official report and regulations etc. in English on Google, Google scholar, Web of Science; or in Chinese on www.baidu.com, www.cnki.net, www.cgvip.com, www.wanfangdata.com.cn etc. The data showed in Fig.4.1 on the 'Main renewable resources imports to the PRC for 2014-2020' is from the 'China's renewable resource recycling industry development reports 2016-2019' (CMC, 2016-2019) and <http://www.intracen.org>. The data showed in Table 4.1-4.2 is also from 'China's renewable resource recycling industry development reports 2016-2019' (CMC, 2016-2019). This data is further analysed and the result is graphed in Fig.4.2. The Fig.4.3 is a picture shot in the countryside of Hetang District, Zhuzhou city during COVID19. The promulgation or revision updates of all policies and regulation on waste management since 1995 has been checked and their frequencies is revealed in Fig.4.4 The amount solid waste produced in a southern city was recorded in incineration plant and their time series analysis is described in Fig.4.5.

Candidate companies were identified from information are collected from the website Qichacha.com and official website (MHURD, 2020) in 2019 before the start of the COVID-19 pandemic. More than five thousand Chinese companies were identified in the soil remediation and waste treatment sector in the first review of the database. These were screened for compliance with permit/certification by the Chinese government to provide a pool of >300 organizations (A process flow chart see Figure 3.1 and Table 5.1). A pilot survey with a draft questionnaire was carried out with a group of three professionals and feedback was incorporated in the final questionnaire, designed following recognized guidelines (Brace, 2018; Saris and Gallhofer, 2014).

Figure 3.1 A summary of the methodology framework for data collection in this study

3.6.2 Questionnaire

The application of a questionnaire in this research collected data from respondents and quantified the information obtained. Questionnaires were used to attain information because of their advantage in fetching data in a structured manner compared to other methods (Linsky, 1975; Silke, 2001). Therefore, questionnaires mainly focused on information collection of polluted soil remediation practices, and commercial decision making for soil contamination treatment projects. The application of a questionnaire was wider ranged, cheaper and quicker as respondents were widely located and neither easily nor readily available. The methodology and general schedule are

shown as below: 1. Prepare a list of remediation industries in China, 2. Design a questionnaire about the feasibility of projects on remediation, 3. Prepare documents for ethical approval, 4. Ethical approval application. There are three forms including an information sheet, a consent form and debrief form and one application form necessary for Ethical approval. The application 9441: An investigation of models used in commercial decision making and influence on the delivery of environmental improvement projects, submission 7769, has been approved by the Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences SEC of University of the West of Scotland on 12th December 2019. There is a questionnaire designed for research and data collection. A trial questionnaire would be used in advance before the study started.

How questionnaires was designed: As part of the questionnaire design, discussions carried out within the project supervisory team and more widely with an individual experienced in industry engagement and collection of company feedback. The first version of questionnaire was designed in Chinese and was reviewed by an expert in the remediation industry with considerable experience delivering remediation projects. The questionnaire was updated and translated into English on basis of his comment and professional words used in British remediation companies and site remediation sector. The questionnaire was updated again after discussion with my supervisors and a college who taught questionnaire design.

A trial questionnaire was applied. In interview with a land quality expert and contaminated land regulator for Inverclyde Council, Scotland who provided very valuable comments on designing of the questionnaire in English, questionnaire improvement and design of an interview guide for contaminated soil remediation. The English questionnaire and interview guide were translated into Chinese. Pilot study of the Chinese questionnaire and interview were carried out with a number of stakeholders experienced in various aspects of the remediation industry. The questionnaire survey was considered robust as the pilot study was carried out with three participants to improve the questionnaire to match study specific objectivities, with all questions of the questionnaire with a full range to reveal or investigate all research problems; all questions are arranged logically appropriate for the soil remediation companies involved (Kern and Jonyniene, 2012; Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2002).

The survey targeted participants to include contractors, equipment providers, regulators, environmental consultants, contaminated site owners, and environmental groups, etc. There are different ways to recruit respondents: 1. to find online special forum or groups where practitioners joined and regularly discussed their questions in their work and information of newest version regulation, 2. to explain the background and focus more often to attract their attention, 3. to invite some respondents who work in this sector by asking help from our common friends who can

introduce me and my research to them, 4. to invite respondents whose colleagues have joined the survey by letting their colleagues invited them to join. 5. Add more personal contacts by searching information from posters of event and conferences about soil remediation and then invite them to join the survey. The questionnaire survey was sent, via an online link with an invitation to various soil remediation specialist groups on the QQ/WeChat social media app, to a group that included practitioners who worked in different Chinese cities, to understand the relationship between soil remediation and waste management in China from their work experience. Before the respondent started to complete the questionnaire, an introduction explained the objective of the survey, how data would be used and how the confidentiality of respondents would be guaranteed. All participants could withdraw from the study any time before submission. To encourage response, the participants were offered a future report and feedback from the survey.

Several studies have previously approached similar groups to explore the application of remediation technologies and decision-making in soil remediation-related practices (Hou et al., 2014; Hou, Al-Tabbaa and Guthrie, 2014; Hou, 2016). However, we addressed the more immediate dynamic pressures on project delivery as directly identified by practitioners, rather than the outcomes of completed projects. The questionnaire was designed to address the following topics: (i) basic information about the respondents, work experience, location of remediation sites, and their company type; (ii) various service types offered by companies and frequency of deployment (including third-party testing services, remediation construction, specialist materials and equipment support); (iii) one example of stabilization and corresponding waste application potential; (iv) regulations applied in various phases of development; (v) factors considered in decision-making for remediation. These latter factors were quite diverse and included issues of funding sources, intellectual property, the review of proposals and the decision-making process, the factors important in the assessment of the success of remediation, commercial activities and competitiveness of businesses and market advantage, target setting, remediation efficiency testing, and ranking of importance of the various factors. Respondents were asked to rank factors in order and were provided with an opportunity to identify any missing issues. Results were assessed based on the proportion of responses. The sample population of all groups together consisted of all stakeholders involved in practical projects and/or decision-making.

How questionnaire information was presented online from the documents:

Step 1: The Wenjuanxing website (<https://www.wjx.cn>) was chosen for the questionnaire survey because there are 212 million questionnaires released and 16.878 billion questionnaire feedbacks collected on that website. It is free and it helps researchers get access to others easier as it supports

people log in the website with two most popular social applications (the WeChat and the QQ) in mainland China.

Step 2: The contents from the information sheet went first then followed by questions. The contents showed the participants that they are free to withdraw the survey any time they want. There is a 'submit' button at the end of online questionnaire. Only by clicking submit can the questionnaire be completed and submitted successfully.

Step 3: Each question was copied from the questionnaire document and pasted on the webpage one by one. Due to the consideration of adaptability, some question content and question format in documents have also been changed to adapt to free online website Wenjuanxing online format. Some questions are connected before and after, and same settings are realized in the online questionnaire.

Step 4: All the setting were finished in the online questionnaire after it was pilot filling-in and modified several times.

Step 5: Many people were invited to fill in and their feeling of filling in were considered. Both the computer version and the mobile version are adjusted, and the approximate time required for filling in is counted. The screenshots of online questionnaire for mobile version and pc version were showed in Appendix.

During the data collection for the research, a participant information sheet information was presented and/or explained to all participants with questionnaire link in QQ group chats and it was also showed at the beginning of online questionnaire. The researcher provided the informed consent form information to all participants to agree to participate in this research by letting all participants who clicked the submission button to submit the feedback at the end of the questionnaire. The participant information sheet and the consent form are showed as Appendices E and F respectively. All contents of questionnaire pc version and phone version were screenshotted and presented as Appendices G-H. A total of 107 valid feedback responses were received including from researchers at university and/or research institutes and staff in different positions in a range of companies in the sector. Participants in the questionnaire were given the opportunity of a follow-up interview in which a total of 13 respondents/companies provided detailed interview feedback.

3.6.3 Interview

3.6.3.1 Method justification

The interview is verbal conversation on a topic between two people with relevant information gathering during the conversation for the objectives of the research (Valenzuela and Shrivastava, 2002). The interviewer can attain in-depth details on the theme as interviews can help with getting the story behind the experience of participants, who might be chosen from respondents as a

follow-up step to the questionnaire method (McNamara, 1999). In the research, various types of interview methods are helpful, such as telephone interviews, social app interviews, personal interviews, and group discussion interviews (Cooper, Schindler and Sun, 2006; Lune and Berg, 2017; Fontana and Frey, 1994).

The personal interview is the dominant technique among the above various mentioned types (Opdenakker, 2006). The verbal and non-verbal cues like participants/interviewees' body language show the degree of discomfort of the interviewee about the questions, with help of which so researchers can tell the level of interest in the theme being discussed during the personal interview (Price, 2004). However, there is a limitation to travelling in China because of the effect of COVID19. Therefore, a telephone interview is used to investigate the soil remediation projects' commercial decision-making in this study by interviewing staff who worked in the industries.

3.6.3.2 Interview significance

First, interview can help verify professional words properly and verify if the translation between English and Mandarin are suitable and correct. Secondly, interview can cross-check answers of feedbacks from respondents and reduce bias in the survey as much as possible. The first interview was carried out with an expert on basis of the proper version of the questionnaire and a simple interview guide. Feedback about the information of regulations, forums, site remediation business was attained on designing of English questionnaire, English questionnaire improvement and interview guide design in contaminated soil remediation sector. The questions in the interview guide were improved on professional words and description etc. after the analyzing and cross-checking the first interview and questionnaire feedback. The interview guide was translated into Mandarin and updated on basis of Chinese remediation sector information and status. It was updated three times after pilot study of the Mandarin questionnaire and interview guide with a number of stakeholders experienced in various aspects of the remediation industry. All formal interviews are semi-structured on the phone calling and some special questions were added in those interviews to cross-checking information attained from feedbacks of questionnaires or gain further ideas and information with consideration of interviewees' background and their answers in their live interview. The expert was a part time student from my college and my supervisor introduced her to me. The first engineer from research and development is responsible for remediation product research development in the company I visited several times before. The second engineer is responsible for remediation project designing and construction in China Machinery International Engineering Design & Research Institute Co., Ltd. and he was introduced to me by a college. The third engineer worked for a remediation company at administration lever after years of working on remediation projects and site remediation

and he then moved to a university post and was introduced to me by another college who also worked in the engineering company.

3.6.3.3 Interview completion

After the preparation phase was guidance and advice from (Bryman and Cramer, 2012) about the interview technique employed in data collection during the preparation phase. First of all, prepare the interview guide according to the research target or questions; Secondly, avoid double or multiple barrelled questions; thirdly, identify the possible interview subjects, themes and respondents from a given population; fourthly, decide on the recording mode in the interview (video recording, notetaking or both); the last but not the least, to seek permission from interviewees for recording or notetaking and arrange a suitable time for the interviewees (Bryman and Cramer, 2012).

Based on the targets set in this study and advice from (Bryman and Cramer, 2012), interview schedules were designed for different participants to deal with issues specific to their respective roles in working experiences for remediation industries. All interview schedules were semi-structured so all participants have some latitude to pursue what they cared about or considered details relevant while assuring all questions of the researcher were adequately answered. The interview schedules were divided into different sections dealing with various issues in remediation.

3.6.4 Case study

Contaminated soil polluted with PTEs and sepiolite-based waste were chosen as a case study to understand potential of a typical treatment technology to deal with soil pollution. 'Heavy metal, potentially toxic element', 'wastewater, soil', 'sepiolite, sepiolite based, modified sepiolite, pure sepiolite' were key words applied in database. Sepiolite application in soil remediation was reviewed and we identified 150 sepiolite-based literature reports and patents from databases (Web of Science, United States Patent and Trademark Office (<https://www.uspto.gov>)), Chinese Patent database (<http://www.soopat.com/>) for application in the treatment of water or soil contaminated by PTEs. The software Nvivo12 and Microsoft Office 2010 Excel are applied to analyze those data and interpret results.

3.6.5 Documents data sources

Documents data source mainly collected data through literature and documentary views from sources such as government departments announcement or reports, journal publications, university records, self-reports and authors' websites (Koziol and Arthur, 2011). Literature studies and the documentary view were used to collect secondary information or data in this study.

The literature review aims to describe what had been known before the research was carried out (Walsh and Downe, 2005). The background and context of the study were provided in the chapter 2

of this thesis, which focused on soil pollution status in China, soil contaminated with potentially toxic elements in China, the original concept of SWMS including the definition, history, policy and characteristics of MSWM, ISWM and HWM; waste management policy and policies' updates in China; Interaction effect of the waste management system and policy; remediation definition, remediation business or industrial application of waste in remediation; sepiolite introduction and its waste potential application. The literature review was largely concluded from academic articles, published official announcements and reports through content analysis and a documentary view of the materials collected.

3.7 Data analysis

Data analysis is an important task to evaluate the accuracy and complete exploitation of data obtained (Brandt and Brandt, 1998). To be specific, data analysis is the process to describe, illustrate, condense and evaluate data systematically with statistical or logical techniques (Gong and Richman, 1995; Savenye and Robinson, 2013; Bello *et al.*, 2016). In the analysis process, data integrity is essential for its accurateness and appropriateness (Gersten *et al.*, 2005). To analyse all possible kinds of data about its integrity is not encouraged on basis of the rule thumb concerning data analysis (Van Gog *et al.*, 2008).

This research aims to answer: what is the regulation implemented to prevent further soil pollution? What decision making support are to improve treatment efficiency in old contamination treatment and reduce new pollution in site remediation projects with more consideration in decision making? If so, any new technology that can be applied for pollution treatment and make it more cost effective in site remediation? Considering waste management policies (GOSC, 2018), the application of abandoned mining sepiolite or sepiolite processing scrap is a potential trend for industrial application in the world because of limited landfill space and restrictions on incineration. What is the project decision-making support that affects soil remediation projects' steps in the mainland of China, what forms it is, and why?

Therefore, the data analysis was based on the specific research objectives of this study. The question of this research was: What is the regulation implemented to prevent further soil pollution? Can remediation and waste management businesses be mapped using site distribution and data from questionnaire feedback? What is the direct link between remediation, waste management and business in China and are the current regulations for remediation aligned with waste management and business? Can solid waste be recycled to treat contamination in the remediation business using existing data?

The research investigates the regulation implemented to reduce new pollution in China; how remediation businesses do the decisions making in projects and how to use waste to remediate pollution; how sepiolite based waste could be used as a potential resource. The research, therefore, analyses the decision-making support and related parameters that have an influence on the implementation of projects and interaction of soil remediation and potential application of solid waste as additives to soil remediation.

3.7.1 Documents

The source of information concerning the waste ban of governments and changes in policies is the documentation generated by the official department. The documents or information analysed in the research includes various government official documents or records, such as policies, reports and statistics from government bodies in the waste management system sector or related departments and it also comprises non-governmental documents, such as institutional reports, conference reports/programs and digital documents. Besides, the work of other researchers, like public reports, academic journal papers and newspaper articles show different views from a different angle on the same phenomenon (Coffey, 2014). Document analysis takes into account not only texts but also images (results were shown in Appendix I and published papers were shown in Appendix II).

3.8 Summary and conclusion

This chapter has described the research methods applied in this thesis and justified the main decisions made during the research process. It clarified the details of choices that reflects content of research question and make research specific objectives more achievable.

The next chapter shows the results and analysis of three research specific objectives: to collect data and information reported pertaining to the regulation waste ban in literature and official documents in China (SO. 1.1), to review the impact of the regulation waste ban to SWMS and land use with consideration of soil contamination of preventing further soil contamination (SO. 1.2) and to describe updates of the national standards and regulation for waste management in China (SO. 1.3). The results and analysis of research objective SO. 1.1 - SO. 3.1, SO. 3.2 - SO. 4.2 are shown in chapters 5 and 6 respectively.

Chapter 4 Regulation implemented to prevent further soil pollution

4.1 Introduction

The previous chapter describes all methods employed to achieve the aim of this research. This chapter analyzed all related data collected from online reports related to waste management associated with the waste ban (all data from reports and official website were shown in Appendix I). The result showed various changes in waste import in the run-up to the ban. Results showed that the practice of landfill mining is a choice to reduce landfill space demands. It could bring more opportunities if technological advances in waste re-processing were accelerated. There are frequent updates of major policies related to waste and the environment since 1991, well before the waste import ban was announced in 2017. The frequency of updates or revisions of major policies shows a higher level of activity from 2015 onwards. Results also indicated that the pandemic provides some dynamic evidence of the response of the waste management system. The post-pandemic recovery should provide an opportunity to establish more resilient, sustainable management systems in the future.

More recently, due to the prominence of reports on the Chinese 'waste ban' and increasing debates on 'zero waste' cities all over the world, more attention has been paid to waste management system projects and their operation in mainland China, policy changes give another a boost to the rapid growth of waste management system.

4.2 Changes in waste import in the run-up to the ban

As shown in Fig. 4.1, the import of iron and steel scrap and non-ferrous metal scrap both show a consistent decrease from 2014 to 2016, with a slight increase from 2016 to 2017, but then a significant decrease of 42.2% and 30.5% respectively in 2018. The import amount of iron and steel scrap are 18.4×10^4 kilo-tons, 2.7×10^4 kilo-tons in 2019 and 2020 respectively (Intracen, 2021), with decrease of 86.3% and 85.3% compared to previous year. While the import amount of non-ferrous metal scrap is 294.9×10^4 kilo-tons, 198.6×10^4 kilo-tons in 2019 and 2020 respectively, with decrease of 26.2% and 32.7% compared to previous year (<http://www.intracen.org>). The waste plastic shows a relatively gentle decrease of over 30% from 2014 to 2017 with a reduction in import of more than 99% in 2018 (583.0×10^4 kilo-tons to 5.0×10^4 kilo-tons), then almost zero in 2019 and 2020. The waste paper imports increase slightly from 2014 to 2015, then decline slowly from 2015 to 2017 with a more than 33.8% reduction in 2018, then decline again from 2018 to 2020 with reduction of 35.7% and 37.05% compared with those in the previous year respectively. For the import of iron and steel scrap, non-ferrous metal scrap and waste paper, there are still permitted licenses application for

companies to import higher standard during next two years until 1st January 2021 when the Ministry of Ecology and Environment of the People’s Republic of China stopped acceptance and permission of permitted license application (MEE, 2018a; MEE, 2020a).

Figure 4.1 Main renewable resources imports to the PRC for 2014-2020 (CMC, 2016-2019, <http://www.intracen.org>) (Data is shown in Appendix I)

It should be noted that the ban on import was not introduced suddenly, rather increasingly strict pollution prevention measures have been implemented since 1996 (Sun, 2019). The import of waste plastic reveals the biggest reduction from 2014 to 2020 with a complete import ban on 1st January 2021 according to (MEE, 2020a). Besides, in order to control plastic pollution, an ambitious five-year plan was released on 18th January 2020 to ban or restrict the production, sales and use of environmentally unfriendly plastic in Chinese national level (State Council, 2020), which means that regular plastic need will be cut by 2025 in the whole country. The import amount of iron and steel scrap and waste paper were categorised in ‘Catalogue of Restricted Import Solid Wastes that Can Be Used as Raw Materials’ (MEE, 2019b), as no licences are being issued in 2021, these products are banned at the moment, however it should be noted that import licences may be permitted in the future. The import of non-ferrous metal scrap, higher standard copper containing waste, and aluminium containing waste continues at the moment (July 2021).

4.3 Reasons why the ban started

One reason for increasingly stringent regulation is the increasing amount of municipal waste from daily domestic life generated for recycling. The waste arisings (mass) of materials commonly recycled for the period 2014-2018 is shown in Table 4.1 with data presented by value in Table 4.2 below.

Table 4.1 The amount of main categories of recyclable waste recovered in PRC between 2014 and 2018 (unit: $\times 10^6$ tons).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original material can be found at <https://jc.wanfangdata.com.cn> and <https://xueshu.baidu.com>

Table 4.2 Main categories of recyclable waste generated in PRC and value of recovered material between 2014 and 2018 (unit: billion Yuan).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original material can be found at <https://jc.wanfangdata.com.cn> and <https://xueshu.baidu.com>

From Table 4.1, it is apparent that whilst the internal recyclable waste is still substantial the reduction in imported materials has impacted on waste paper associated industrial activity indicated a shortage from 2018. Iron and steel scrap showed an increase from 2015 to 2018, with the similar trend for iron and steel scrap of large iron and steel enterprises while the iron and steel from other industries indicated a decrease in the supply chain since 2017.

In addition, the economic development is another reason to promote the ban implemented. For example, the import of plastic wastes is a method to mitigate the shortage of resources in China with the plastic wastes is utilized as secondary material from the mid-1990s to early 2010s when economic development was increased and raw materials demand was soaring thanks to Chinese opening-up policy (Shi *et al.*, 2021). Enterprises that engaged in solid waste recycling had been offered tax refund since 1995 by Chinese government for economic reasons (Shi *et al.*, 2021). However, with the development of the Chinese economy the governmental budget to deal with land, water and air pollution increased; the pressure and costs of environmental remediation has continually increased for the Chinese Government and has exceeded the benefit of waste importation, therefore resulting in the promulgation of the import ban in 2017.

There are only a few companies that get involved in the domestic waste recycling market due to the low revenue streams of domestic recycling, the high cost of wages, the chaotic situation of the domestic waste management system and the challenge of cheaper 'secondary resource' material from waste import. As shown in Fig.4.2, prices of main categories of recyclable waste generated in

PRC all increased from 2016 to 2018 that might stimulate improvement of the domestic recycling. The import ban is a strategy partially to encourage more people to get themselves involved with the domestic recycling and partially to invest more research and development money within waste recycling industries.

Figure 4.2 Prices of main categories of recyclable waste generated in PRC before and after the ban (unit: Yuan/t)

4.4 The status of landfill mining in China

Many formal landfill sites were already full in advance of the introduction of new waste import laws. This created significant pressure on the waste management sector for the Chinese Government. A catastrophic landslide event occurred in Shenzhen city, China in 2015 because of over filling of the landfill, injured 17 people and killed at least 73 people with an estimated total economic loss of more than 0.13 billion USD (Yang *et al.*, 2017). To solve the problems of high cost and limited land to develop a new landfill, landfill mining provides an opportunity to relieve the pressure (Zhou *et al.*, 2015). The import ban aims to reduce the amount of solid waste entering the country therefore decreasing the quantity of waste going to landfills, enhancing the environmental footprint and protecting human health. However, landfill mining brings new challenges as the nature of the waste within old landfill sites may be problematic to handle. For instance, excavated plastic bags have impurities even after normal cleaning techniques, this will hinder effective recycling of aged plastic

wastes or their use within energy from waste processes such as hydrogenation, gasification and pyrolysis (Zhou *et al.*, 2014). A further threat may be the most practical processing method of landfill mining plastic wastes is incineration or being treated as residue-derived fuels for energy recovery (Zhou *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) accounts for 5% of material besides soils (87%) and plastics (2.1%) in the excavated landfills (Hölzle, 2019), which also shows potential problem because of energy consumption as well as emissions resulting from operations, such as excavation, processing and transportation in landfill mining. A report in 2013 shows that about 1 billion tonnes of CDW are generated in China annually, which was five times the amount of municipal solid waste produced in China the same year; the reused and recycled CDW was only 5% (Duan and Li, 2016). Landfill space is reducing rapidly and emissions from previously disposed wastes increase (Lee *et al.*, 2020), which might lead to higher cost of landfill and more illegal dumping of domestic CDW showed as Fig.4.3.

Figure 4.3 Increased illegal dumping of domestic Construction and Demolition Wastes during COVID19

Though the negative impact form landfill mining might have impeded the original aim of the waste ban, however, the landfill mining would be a choice to save space for landfills of the younger generations, especially for those in big cities where urbanisation expands fast. Moreover, landfill mining could bring more opportunities rather than tricky problem to deal with when related technologies develops well enough to satisfy various requirements in processing.

4.5 The dynamics of domestic policies in China

There are frequent updates of major policies related to waste and the environment since 1991 well before the waste import ban was announced in 2017. As shown in Figure 4.4, the frequency of updates or revisions of major policies shows higher level of activity from 2015 onwards. It includes major policy changes related to environmental issues and reflects broader changes in formal environmental regulation intensity (Zhang *et al.*, 2021), which shows significant cross regional variation in regulation of emission to air, water and re use of wastes. The disposal of waste is still dominated by landfill although combustion has increased and more regulations and policies are being adopted to encourage a more circular economy. The 'Green Fence' policy has been implemented since 2013 to restrict copper scrap imports to mainland China and the impact of the policy on Circular Economy has been assessed and shows that China still has to pay more attention to domestic recycling industry and keep the import of high-quality copper scrap, which could provide China a transition to a more circular economy on copper in future (Dong *et al.*, 2020). To reduce the source of waste, an Announcement on matters related to the ban on the import of solid waste totally was issued on 24th November 2020 by the Ministry of Ecology and Environment (MEE, 2020a). It has been implemented since 1st January 2021.

There is increased attention on the transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources that not only reduces China's carbon footprint reduction, but also leads to reduction of waste generation and whilst maximising recycling of various waste as secondary carbon raw material, which is the pilot study to develop zero waste cities (GOSC, 2018). There are "11+5" cities and regions labelled as zero waste construction pilot city or region all together in 2018 on basis of Chinese administrative division, including eleven cities: Shenzhen city, Xining city and so on; one new district: state-level Xiong'an new area in Hebei province; one development zone: Beijing Economic and Technological Development Area; one international cooperative: Sino-Singapore Tianjin Eco-City, one county: Guangze county of Fujian province; one county-level city: Ruijin county-level city of Jiangxi province (Sohu, 2019). Xining city is the only city located in northwest China and the biggest area among all pilot cities. The accumulative budgeted investment for 26 "non-waste cities" construction projects in Xining city is nearly 0.646 billion US dollar. There are 10 solid waste utilization and disposal chains formed within Xining City. The structure of traditional industries such as chemical industry and refining is optimized to promote industrial recycling, resource utilization and ecological development, with a reduction of 7.5% on energy consumption per unit of GDP compared to last year.

In terms of agriculture, five production bases are built in the implementation of the agricultural and livestock product quality and safety assurance project and it occupied 57,730 ha, including the national green food raw material (broad bean) standardized production base for broad bean and potato in Huangzhong District and Datong County, respectively. Through using alternative

technologies such as using organic fertilizers, crop rotation and improved irrigation, there has been a reduction of 43,000 ha of land that has been treated with chemical fertilizers and pesticides. In this model, 630,000 acres of chemical fertilizers and pesticides have been reduced and 77,000 tons of organic fertilizers have been subsidized to increase efficiency in 2020. The use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides in 2020 was reduced by 41.9% and 32.9% respectively compared with those of 2018. In addition, "Enterprise recycling, farmer participation, government Supervision and market promotion" agricultural film recycling system is also built in Xining city with the recycling rate of agricultural film more than 90%. For citizens daily life, the domestic waste classification in Xining city covers classification covers a total of 304,000 households with a recycling rate of 37% on domestic waste, including more than 1,300 tons of waste involves in plastic, textile, metal, paper, electronic products and other recyclables and perishable waste that enter the recyclable and non-hazardous disposal network separately.

Land use policy is further impacted by recent plans to develop zero waste cities (Lee *et al.*, 2020): large amount of land will be used more efficient due to less industrial solid waste exposure. Through the establishment of green waste-free cells in society, promotion and guidance of the concept of waste-free is vigorously promoted to form consensus of waste-free for citizens. According to the investigation conducted by the Qinghai Provincial Social Situation and Civil Investigation Center, the popularization rate of publicity, education and training for the construction of a "waste-free city" in Xining City is 85.34%. The satisfaction degree of the construction effect of the "waste-free city" was 83.02% for the public. The construction of green cells consists of green post, green restaurants, green mines, and green buildings etc.

In addition, more regulations and policies have been promulgated all the time since 1995 to restrict the waste import properly, which shows that Chinese government has set a basic regulation frame all the time and is trying to build a better recycling or waste management system over time.

Figure 4.4 Frequencies of revisions to national laws and regulations in the PRC (1991-2020)

Figure 4.5 Time series analysis of the amount solid waste produced in a southern city of the PRC (2016-2020)

4.6 Challenges and opportunities for waste management companies

The life cycle cost of recycled paper manufacturing in China has been assessed (Li *et al.*, 2020). A ban on unsorted recovered paper was announced in 2018 and the import quota for recovered paper has been tightened, leading to a dramatic drop in the amount imported recovered paper (Li *et al.*, 2020). As the recovered paper is a key raw material for the recycled papermaking industry, alternatives (e.g. straw, imported wood pulp and imported deinked pulp) are now being assessed to deal with the decrease in feedstock. The results indicated that imported deinked pulp might be the trend for the recycled papermaking industry in China with a growth in price of the domestic recovered paper (Li *et al.*, 2020). This change might bring additional research and development of potential alternatives in the future to satisfy the increasing need of imported recycled material due to the waste import ban.

The environmental impact on the life cycle of used polyethylene terephthalate (PET) was also analysed under many post-ban scenarios (Ren *et al.*, 2020). The result shows that the absence of imported used PET in China leads to an increase in virgin PET fibre production using manufacturing processes that are based on carbon-intensive coal. This brings an additional environmental impact because of the higher air pollution emissions from production (Ren *et al.*, 2020). The treatment of air pollution may become new challenges, however, improving local PET recycling rate and searching for production alternatives are emerging new opportunities.

There are recycled commodities which may be sold at a cheaper price to downstream companies because of higher quality compared to domestic products. Without importing waste material, the costs of downstream companies would increase because they cannot use cheaper recycled-items directly or they need to find an alternative source. However, with more initiatives available to boost collection and recycling businesses (Zuo *et al.*, 2020), there are now opportunities for people to start new, or adapt current, businesses in different way and bring new jobs.

Businesses who deal with waste still need a significant and consistent supply of waste materials, which pushes the domestic waste recycling companies to move their attention to domestic waste as an alternative, for example, domestic copper scrap recycling and application (Dong *et al.*, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2019). Some of the larger companies may survive after small businesses fail: the trash ban is a threat to the existence of small companies, however, it can be an opportunity for a big company to enlarge and update its technology (Zhang, 2020a). Some companies will change their processing to higher efficiency and value to survive, for example, developing a new idea to apply the recycled resource. It may even force companies to consider product recycling at the design stage, such as extended producer responsibility (EPR) (Zhang, 2020b). Therefore instead of just disposing of

the waste directly and paying fees to get the raw recycled waste material directly from abroad, companies are pushed to design products which consider new waste sorting and recycling methods.

For waste management companies in Southeast Asian countries, an increase in solid waste import after the China import ban is now a threat to business sustainability from the potential imposition of similar restrictions by their governments. There is no detailed data covering company failure as a result of the ban and the number of jobs lost which is quite important for national-society. However, it seems that some Southeast Asian countries have tightened their restrictions by announcing statements or revoking their imports licences on local companies that process plastic waste or e-waste (WMR, 2018).

For companies in mainland China, technologies such as the Beidou navigation system, the Internet of Things, Internet and Artificial Intelligence etc. are applied by Yixun Intelligent Environmental Sanitation System to manage the whole process of people, truck, materials, machine involved in environmental sanitation management in real-time. It can help design environmental sanitation management models rationally, improve the quality of sanitation operations, reducing environmental operation costs and assessing the effectiveness of the management through data (Gov.CN, 2019). It is a new start and possibility for structure of domestic waste management system thanks to the involvement of the Internet and the big data. Whilst some information has been derived from structural changes of the global waste trade network (Pu *et al.*, 2019; Tran *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2020), and mechanisms of response (Tan *et al.*, 2018), 'Big data' application for the waste management systems could be a potential bright path for transition of domestic companies.

4.7 Impact of the COVID19 pandemic on waste management system

The global pandemic has influenced the production and management of various industrial sector, in terms of waste to recycling generation of end-of-life vehicles were stopped because of the shutdown of companies upstream and there was an insufficient supply of raw materials for many manufacturing companies. While for domestic WEEE, there is a consequential increase in generation of e-waste due to increasing utilization of electrical and electronic devices for online teaching or work from home during the pandemic or post COVID 19 in a developing country (Adejumo and Oluduro, 2021). In terms of waste to energy, for example waste incineration for power generation (business), the closure of restaurants and service companies leads to the amount of food collection and volume of transport in some cities or regions was only 25%~33% of pre-pandemic levels of pre-pandemic levels due to lockdown and social restrictions. On the other hand, the pandemic caused an increase in medical waste due to increased production of protective materials (masks, gowns etc). The more complicated situation poses a potential challenge for waste management system because of shortage

of raw materials for manufacture, restricted traffic, infection risk, higher cost. In addition, large-scale sanitation and disinfection work during the pandemic increased company operating costs such as labour, machinery, materials, and transportation (Finance, 2020). However, there is research that shows the less industrial wastes generated because of less production and exports due to reduced demand during the shutdown (Maliszewska, 2020). More waste has been sent directly to incineration in order to reduce the risk of infection, resulting the over-working of incineration equipment in some cities and regions. Besides, there is also impact of the extended construction period, increased investment and secondary urban environmental protection issues on projects under construction of waste incineration for power generation. According to the current local control levels, the construction period has been impacted with an average of 55 days. The overlapped processing period is longer because of the lagging impact of materials, equipment, logistics, and other supply chains. In addition, the investment will also increase due to the following three reasons: (i) the increase in the cost of personnel, machinery, and materials of the project, (ii) the increase in the cost of capital, and (iii) the loss of operating income caused by the delay in commissioning (Finance, 2020). Higher cost and lower income bring a dilemma for investors and construction of waste incineration in future: it is a difficult decision to make about the treatment of the municipal solid waste and medical waste separately or not during the tough time for waste management system in pandemic.

All municipal solid waste from a southern city were weighted and transported to the waste incineration power plant to generate electricity. The data in figure 4.5, show the annual average and detailed monthly amounts of solid waste produced in a southern city between 2016 and 2020. As a yearly average, a slight increase in 2019 from roughly comparable levels in 2016-2018 in enhanced in 2020. However, the detailed monthly variation is also informative. In general, there is a big drop in the amount of solid waste produced in February because of the lockdown (coming into effect early in 2020 in China) and people returning to their hometown for the Spring Festival. Pre-pandemic, variation across the year tends to show decrease in amounts over the popular summer holiday months, picking up particularly in early autumn festivals. For 2020 this variation is suppressed and a steady increase in waste generation is seen as restrictions on movement maintain a constant population in the city and consumption rates of produce increase along with increased disposal of PPE. Changes in annual average waste production prior to the pandemic are less easy to rationalise and the dip from 2016 to 2018 and increase from 2018 to 2020 may be partly attributed to waste import ban and further restrictions.

The pandemic actually brings more problem for waste management system than before, especially after the waste ban and a series of related regulations and policies acted. However, it also

gives a clue to the world that how quickly the waste management system can respond particularly post pandemic will be an important step to establishing sustainable management systems in future.

4.8 Summary and conclusion

To deal with the pressure and economy costs, the first one is to reduce the possibility of pollution generation with research on the waste ban implementation, waste management system and landfill mining. The second one is to know more about the industry and improve the waste application.

This chapter was written to fulfil RQ. 1: What is the regulation implemented to prevent further soil pollution in China? The first objective (SO.1.1) of this chapter was to collect all data and information pertaining to the waste ban in China. This was completed by reviewing literature and collecting data from official reports, regulations, and local governmental departments. Individual reports with published data were useful to know the annual amount of waste import recently, however, this study was the first one to provide a direction for the local industries of solid waste management to survive and develop in China.

The second objective (SO. 1.2) of this chapter was to review the impact of regulation to SWMS and land use with consideration soil contamination of preventing further soil contamination. This was completed by reviewing the impact of the ban on the range of imported waste and domestically generated materials. The pictures were taken in the countryside of the Hetang District, Zhuzhou city during COVID 19. The amount of solid waste produced in a southern city in China was recorded for the main disposal route (an incineration plant) and their time series analysis has been finished. A fundamental lack of detailed data pertaining to the amount or quantities of broken industries or company failure as the result of the implementation of the waste ban and the number of jobs lost was additionally highlighted.

The third objective (SO. 1.3) of this chapter was to describe updates of the national standards and regulation for waste management and trend for waste collection and classification in China. The introduction or revision updates of all policies and regulations on waste management since 1995 in China have been reviewed and the graph for the frequency of updates of national standards and regulation of China was drawn after the data collection and statistics analysis of regulation updates. The supplementary material shows the pictures of waste management on waste collection and classification that were taken in the center of Zhuzhou city and Guangzhou city in 2022 (as shown in pictures of Zhuzhou / Guangzhou Cities in Appendix)

The findings of this study correlate with papers published by other researchers in the world which recognize that the waste ban was not introduced suddenly. It reveals that rather increasingly strict pollution prevention measures have been implemented since 1996. The study also highlights that the

import ban is a strategy partially to encourage more people to get themselves involved with domestic recycling and partially to invest more research and development money within waste recycling industries. It reveals that the Chinese government has set a basic regulation frame all the time and is trying to build better recycling or waste management system over time. Instead of disposing of the waste and buying the raw recycled waste material from abroad directly, companies are pushed to update their paths of getting materials and designing products with the consideration of new waste sorting, classification, and recycling. The results showed that the costs and pressure of environmental remediation have increased and even exceeded the benefit of waste import. Some serious environmental contaminations showed that handling or importing Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment has led to the associated human health issues.

This chapter fulfilled RQ.1: What is the regulation implemented to prevent further soil pollution? The next chapter addresses RQ.2: Can remediation and waste management business be mapped using site distribution and data from the website, online database and questionnaire feedback? and RQ.3: What can be done to improve the land remediation efficiency and help the projects choose the most suitable remediation scheme and all decision were made reasonable?

Chapter 5 Decision making support to improve the efficiency of land remediation

5.1 Introduction

The previous chapter answered RQ. 1: What is the policy implemented to prevent further soil pollution in China? The impact of the waste ban with respect to waste management in China was discussed by reviewing the solid waste management status of PRC before the implementation of the national legislation. The status of landfill mining, and the dynamics of domestic policies before and after the promulgation of the ban were reviewed. The rebound of the waste ban may have stimulated in the short term negative impacts on local environments both in China and internationally. The concept of 'zero waste cities' brings new hope to improve SWMS of PRC. This chapter will address the RQ.2: 'Can remediation and waste management businesses be mapped using site distribution and data from the website, online database and questionnaire feedback?' SO. 2.1: 'To collect all data and information pertaining to the remediation and waste management businesses in China.' was achieved by desk study on candidate companies through searching all related website, and then deciding to collect information from the website Qichacha.com and official website (available at <http://www.mohurd.gov.cn/>). SO. 2.2: 'To analyse the SWMS in China with consideration of waste material classification: MSW from cities and suburban areas, industrial solid waste (ISW) from industries and processing, and HW from contaminated sites and industries.' was achieved via an interrogation of the SWMS in China. The old treatment method of solid waste is outdated and leaves people under pressure of history legacy pollutants' management and associated contamination in the environment. Zero waste cities' pilot study is presented on the update to deal with increasing various waste generation.

This chapter also address the RQ. 3: 'What can be done to improve the land remediation efficiency and help the projects choose the most suitable remediation scheme?' The research question was answered via questionnaire and interview feedback analysis. SO. 3.1: 'To develop a decision-making support in soil/sediment with consideration of the analysis of data or information collected in questionnaire and interview', results show that soil remediation scheme decision-making is determined by remediation target value of 75.7% , land use nature (for purpose of farming, building or fishing) of 69.16%. Existing construction means and technology was the most strongly agreed factor that affects the advantage of the company on soil remediation. Factors' importance ranking in commercial decision making for soil remediation are remediation target value > capital guarantee > existing technology and means. Site background/ history investigation is the most important factor in delivering remediation on-site. Agricultural soil remediation is a long-term project that is normally

based on national and local government levels to ensure food safety with long term safety considerations. It is normally large scale. While contaminated site remediation for construction usually is of a smaller scale and shorter project construction period compared to agricultural land remediation.

5.2 Regulations Applied

Some regulations are specifically focused on the application or development of treated polluted agricultural land and land for construction, such as Soil Environmental Quality: Risk Control Standard for Soil Contamination of Development land (GB36600-2018) and Soil Environmental Quality: Risk Control Standard for Soil Contamination of Agricultural Land (GB15618-2018).

A big change from treatment to management is that attention is being paid to management of contaminated industrial or mining sites on the basis of Measures for the Soil Environment Management of Industrial and Mining Land (for Trial Implementation)'. Many regulations have begun to be implemented since 2014 (Li *et al.*, 2015), so more domestic regulations can be adopted by practitioners, and the corresponding regulatory system is more comprehensive. There are still some special pollutants in project construction and US laws and regulations could be used as references for specific values if none can be found in Chinese regulations. As shown in Figure 5.1, the technical guidelines for risk assessment of soil contamination of land for construction (HJ 25.3-2019) had the highest percentage of 35% application in the risk assessment phase among all relevant regulations. This emphasizes the importance of legal compliance in the risk assessment phase. Most contaminated sites have legacy pollution and are occupied by state companies. Consequently, treatment is the responsibility of the government.

Risk assessment plays a significant role in driving the remediation process firms (Chen *et al.*, 2016; Hou *et al.*, 2017; Luo *et al.*, 2015), and the guidelines are predominantly used to evaluate methods for risk assessment of treatment projects (Ma *et al.*, 2018). However, more detailed options for each guideline are provided (MEE, 2018b; MEE, 2018c; MEE, 2019c; MEE, 2019d; MEE, 2019e; MEE, 2019f; MEE, 2019g; MEE, 2019h) and locally focused standards were highlighted by the survey respondents as being applied in the risk assessment phase only, or were used repeatedly across the entire project delivery. For all regulations, the “risk assessment phase only” had the lowest category of application and generic guidelines and local standards were both significant components of the decision-making process across project lifetimes.

A significant proportion of respondents (69–83%) highlighted listed guidelines or standards, with 35% of respondents choosing the Technical Guidelines for Risk Assessment of Soil Contamination of Land for Construction (HJ 25.3-2019) for the risk assessment phase only, as other guidelines address

risk control. However, 41–64% of respondents used all regulations, laws, and standards repeatedly in the entire project decision-making period, including both the Law of the People’s Republic of China on Prevention and Control of Soil Contamination (LPRCPCSC) and the Soil Environmental Quality Risk Control Standard for Soil Contamination of Development Land (GB36600-2018) in the case of new problems or risk arising once the project had started. The second- and the third-biggest percentages of 62% and 61% related to use of Measures for the Soil Environment Management of Contaminated Land (MEP No.42) and Notice of the State Council on Issuing the Action Plan for Soil Pollution Prevention and Control (SC issued [2016] 31), respectively.

Figure 5.1 Frequency of use (%) for each relevant regulation / standard for different phases of remediation projects

The feedback described a trend in decision-making where prevention, management, and control of soil contamination were of the same or even more significance compared to clean-up of contaminants. Around 60% of respondents used the Technical Guidelines for Soil Remediation of Land for Construction (HJ 25.4-2019). This is a comprehensive description of the soil remediation process that involves decision-making to select remediation models, screening of remediation

technology, developing a remediation plan. The Terms of Risk Control and Remediation of Soil Contamination of Land for Construction (HJ 682-2019) were also used by 60% of respondents because they can be used for the definition of terms, checking, and translating related guidelines from other countries such as the USA or UK.

'Zero waste cities' are emerging from the current Chinese urbanization process and this aspiration is also mentioned as an innovative method to gain funding support to help prevent further soil contamination. The methods for control of soil remediation in the Measures for Funds Management of Soil Pollution Prevention and Control ((2021) Ministry of Finance of the People's Republic of China No. 42) (Available at: http://bj.mof.gov.cn/ztd/czysig/zcfg/202108/t20210802_3742309.htm (accessed on 1 July 2022)) were promulgated and became effective on 2 June 2021. These regulations mention the point *'Carrying out the construction of 'zero waste cities' achieved practical results as a method to prevent and control contamination'* for the first time since the launch of government funding for the remediation of soil pollution in 2011. The process revealed that the final goal of soil remediation is waste control and sustainable management, and the overall reduction of environmental pollution.

5.3 Solid Waste Management

During the process of remediation and treatment of land contamination, contaminated soil would be classified as solid waste if it was disposed of or utilized in any of the following methods: (a) landfill; (b) incineration; (c) co-processing in cement kilns; (d) production of bricks, tiles, road construction materials, and other building materials. The contaminated soil used as soil after remediation is not managed as solid waste (Identification Standards for Solid Wastes General rules of PRC (GB34330-2017)). The polluted soil needs to be identified and evidence provided to show it meets or does not meet hazardous waste criteria after being identified as solid waste. If ex situ remediation is used and contaminated soil is transported, the approval process for transportation of polluted soil should be based on the Law of the People's Republic of China on Prevention and Control of Soil Contamination 41, which demands: "If the remediation construction company transfers contaminated soil that is not hazardous waste, the company needs to formulate a transportation plan, and submit the report that consists of the transportation time, method, route and quantity of contaminated soil, destination of transportation, and final disposal measures to the ecological environment authorities of the site and corresponding receiving site in advance". If the remediation construction company transports polluted soil that meets hazardous waste criteria, the company should obey the in Law of the People's Republic of China on the Prevention and Control of Environmental Pollution by Solid Waste.

If the leaching test applied to any hazardous material, prepared in accordance with the method HJ/T 299 (Solid Waste-Extraction Procedure for Leaching Toxicity—Sulfuric Acid and Nitric Acid Method. Environmental Protection Industry Standard of PRC) exceeds the concentration limit value listed in the national standard Identification Standards for Hazardous Wastes—Identification for Extraction Toxicity (GB 5085.3-2007) in PRC, the solid waste is determined to be hazardous waste with leachate toxicity characteristics. The contaminated soil could be treated as inert solid waste if the concentration of pollutants in the leachate does not exceed limit value in the national standard.

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5.2 Amount of municipal solid waste collected, transported, and rendered harmless (treated) for the PRC in 1980-2020 (all annual data are collected from the National Bureau of Statistics of PRC, Available at: <http://www.stats.gov.cn/tjsj/ndsj/>) (accessed on 1 July 2022)

As shown in Figure 5.2, the total MSW generation has been growing over the past four decades. To be specific, the annual amount of MSW generation in China has increased eightfold from >30 Mt in 1980 to >240 Mt in 2019. When considering the volume of waste treated to meet harmless criteria (which means the solid waste was disposed of by methods such as landfilling, incineration, and composting) for MSW, this increase was one hundredfold, from >2 Mt in 1980 to >240 Mt in 2019 (MHURD, 2020). There was an abrupt decrease of the total MSW generation in 2006 and thereafter followed by an increase again, which might be attributed to the new certification standard adopted for landfill amounts in domestic MSW treatment since 2006 (MHURD, 2020). The quantity of treated MSW (including sanitary landfill, incineration, and composting) started to increase in 1991 and grew quickly from 2007 to 2018, with gaps between the quantity of MSW generated and quantity of MSW

treated (harmless) becoming smaller, which shows the increased amount of treatment taking place in the sector.

The waste ban in China started because of the illegal smuggling of hazardous waste (Sun, 2019), which increased the economic burden on the sector because of the increased need to remediate.

As shown in Fig.4, according to data from (China Statistical Yearbooks, 2021), the amount of CISW management generated in China was > 3800 Mt in 2017. The generation of CISW in 2002 had increased by 66% compared with the amount in 1989 with continual growth (Huang *et al.*, 2006). As shown in Fig.4, the generation of CISW in 2009 had increased steadily by > 100% compared with the amount in 2003. Then, there was a rapid increase of > 18% in 2010 and a sharp growth of > 30% in 2011 compared with the data in the previous year. The generation of CISW is steady from 2011 to 2015, with a small drop of 5.46% in 2016 and a sudden increase of 25.08% in 2017 compared with the previous year. The reason for the huge growth of CISW in 2011 was the Promotion Plan for Promoting the Development of Recycled Non-Ferrous Metal Industry, which involves upgrading equipment related to the non-ferrous metal industry. Type of equipment that do not meet the regulatory requirements are being eliminated, improving the recycling system, and reducing environmental pollution.

For the CISW management system, the ban on importation of secondary resources in 2017 was not introduced suddenly and it is one step of policy to increase strict pollution prevention measures implemented since 1996 (Sun, 2019). The production of HSW has increased slowly since 2000 to 2010, with huge growth in 2011 and a little drop in 2013 after a steady amount of 3400 Mt HSW generated in 2012, then a sharp increase from 2014 to 2017. The reason for the growth of HSW in 2011 was that the Twelfth Five-Year Plan for the Comprehensive Prevention and Control of Heavy Metal Pollution was formally approved by the State Council, which lists soil contaminated with potentially toxic elements as HSW and this has led to increases in the amount of HSW recorded.

As shown in Fig.3, the disposal rate of MSW in mainland China has kept increasing from 53% in 2006 to more than 99% in 2019 (data for treated waste (harmless) is not comparable with data in past years because the new standard has been adopted in municipal waste landfill sites since 2006). The disposal methods include landfill, incineration, and composting. While as shown in Fig.4, the disposal rate of CISW increased from 18% in 2003 to 28% in 2006, later with the rate remaining around 24% from 2007 to 2017. The disposal rate of HSW in mainland China is relatively stable between 20% to 30% from 2011 to 2016. The results reveal that the disposal rate of CISW and HSW is still quite low compared to disposal rate of MSW. The reason is that the treatment of CISW and HSW consists of their disposal, utilized, discharge of solid waste in this year, and leave some storage (carry over) for next year (Tang, Wang and Choi, 2006). The disposal of CISW and HSW is just a minor

part of the treatment, the utilization and discharge were not considered because of complicated calculation. The disposal consists of the disposed part in this year and disposed CISW stored in previous years. While the treatment of MSW was finished every year and there is no carry over for next year (Tang, Wang and Choi, 2006).

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Figure 5.3 Amount of industrial solid waste generated and disposed of PRC in 2003-2017 and their disposal rate (All annual data are collected from the National Bureau of Statistics of PRC <http://www.stats.gov.cn/tjsj./ndsj/>) (accessed on 1 July 2022)

5.4 General Status of Remediation Industries in China

The 319 companies responding to this study are distributed in 28 Chinese cities and Provinces, with most of them located in areas with serious soil pollution levels, such as central China (Hunan province, Hubei province, and Sichuan province), Northeast China (Liaoning province), and economically developed areas (with higher consumption behavior and higher solid waste generation compared to other areas in China) including the east coast (Jiangsu Province, Zhejiang Province and Fujian Province) and southern China (Guangdong Province). Among these companies, 138 companies (43%), focus on the business of both solid waste treatment and soil/land remediation. As shown in Table 5.1, for companies that either dealt with business of solid waste treatment or business of soil/land remediation, the highest number of companies is 58 in Hunan Province, followed by Jiangsu (41), Guangdong (32), Sichuan (24), Beijing (18), Hubei (17) and Liaoning (12), with a total of 202 companies accounting for more than 60% of the total number in this study.

Among them, 100 companies focused on solid waste treatment and 81 companies only focused on soil/land remediation. As shown in Table 5.1, for the solid waste treatment, the highest number of waste treatment companies was 52 in Hunan Province, followed by Jiangsu (29), Guangdong (22), Sichuan (20), Beijing (14), Hubei (12), Fujian (9), and Hebei (9). For the soil remediation, the highest number of soil remediation companies was 51 in Hunan Province, followed by Jiangsu (31), Guangdong (22), Hubei (13), Sichuan (11), Liaoning (10), Beijing (8), and Zhejiang (8). For all locations, East China had the highest frequency of companies (47), followed by Central China (24) and South China (22). East China is much more developed than Central and Southwest China. The citizens are relatively wealthy and business growth is higher and significant soil pollution from past development activity is present. The distribution of remediation projects mainly focused on economically developing zones and regions with the highest levels of contamination.

Table 5.1 Companies that deal with solid waste treatment and/or soil remediation in China.

Areas of China	Provinces or cities ¹	Either ²	SWT only	S/LR only	Both ³
North China	Beijing	18	14	8	4
	Tianjin	6	3	5	2
	Hebei province	10	9	5	4
	Shanxi province	10	7	5	2
	Inner Mongolia	1	1	0	0
Southwest China	Sichuan province	24	20	11	7
	Yunnan province	7	5	4	2
	Chongqing	7	4	5	2
	Tibet	1	1	1	1
	Guizhou province	2	2	1	1
Central China	Hunan Province	58	52	51	45
	Hubei Province	17	12	13	8
	Henan province	10	6	6	2
	Anhui province	6	4	5	3
	Jiangxi province	5	3	3	1
Northeast China	Heilongjiang province	2	2	1	1
	Liaoning province	12	7	10	5
	Jilin province	1	0	1	0
East coast China	Shandong province	8	6	5	3
	Shanghai	7	2	6	1
	Fujian province	10	9	5	4
	Jiangsu province	41	29	31	19
Northwest China	Zhejiang province	10	7	8	5
	Shaanxi province	7	6	2	1
	Xinjiang province	2	2	2	2
Southeast China	Gansu province	1	0	1	0
	Guangdong province	32	22	22	12
	Guangxi province	4	3	2	1
Total	28	319	238	219	138

¹ Only provinces or cities with data are listed in the table. Note: SWT refers to companies that deal with solid waste treatment; S/LR refers to companies that deal with soil/land remediation; ² either refers to companies that either deal with solid waste treatment or soil/land remediation; ³ both refers to companies that deal with both solid waste treatment and soil/land remediation.

Soil remediation is regarded as a step that government cannot ignore (Li *et al.*, 2017) and it is beneficial for environmental quality and the daily lives of all stakeholders; however, it is a great financial burden, as seen in other regions of the world (Hills, 2021). The impact on costs for the government and land developers may indirectly bring secondary pollution to the surrounding environment and citizens through incomplete treatment processes (Hou and Li, 2017). Although it brings potential opportunities for business growth (Rajabi *et al.*, 2021), it does not create tangible products and associated services, such as site investigation, risk assessment, etc., need to be more cost effective, which might impede the sustainable development of soil remediation industries. This is found to generate excessive price competition and verification processes are much more sensitive to costs and even fraudulent reporting. This makes the verification of remediation more complicated

and results in less reliable closure of contamination treatment. All these things mean that remediation status in the market might be confusing, and more regulations focused on prevention of over remediation and consideration that it is unnecessary because of high costs.

Basic information on the age, gender, education, and work experience of respondents are shown in Table 5.2. More than 90% of respondents were younger than 45 years and the age distribution shows that most respondents were 26–35 years or early career professionals. This may be due to the sector being established when pollution became a ‘hot topic’ after the introduction of soil regulations of the Action Plan for Prevention and Control of Soil Pollution (Hu *et al.*, 2018; Li *et al.*, 2019) and interest from professionals working in construction and environmental risk assessment. The gender distribution reveals that the proportion of males is four times that of females in the soil remediation industry, which is similar to that in the general civil engineering sector, traditionally involving multiple site work and physical work activity. More than 89% of people had less than 7 years’ work experience with more than 99% having at least a Bachelor’s or 3 year college degree. This emerging remediation industry has a young and well-educated workforce with huge potential. Education distribution reveals those with a higher education background are more focused on environmental science, environmental engineering, etc., rather than traditional engineering subjects, such as civil or process engineering.

Technical service companies, private enterprises, and state-owned businesses ranked the first, second, and third among various types of enterprises, with percentages of 45%, 24%, and 12%, respectively. The percentages of various types of enterprises shows most jobs focused on providing technical service in China, while in consultancies, planning consultancy was the most common service provided, with a percentage of 37%. Third-party testing, construction, and contracting services had similar percentages of 19%, 18%, and 16% among various services provided. The most common service was consultancy and planning consultancy carried out by technical service companies, private enterprises, and state-owned businesses. The percentages of various types of service provided by companies shows that work experience was a significant factor, as a lot of work needs to be carried out in the risk assessment phase before construction.

Table 5.2 Statistics for (unordered) categorical variables on basis of the data from responses from 107 participants in online survey of remediation sector.

Independent variable		Distribution (%)
Age	16-25 years	10 (9.35)
	26-35 years	77 (71.96)
	36-45 years	10 (9.35)
	46-55 years	4 (3.74)
	56-65 years	6 (5.61)
	66 years and above	0 (0)
Gender	Male	86 (80.37)
	Female	19 (17.76)
	Other	2 (1.87)
Education	High School Graduate or technical School	0 (0)
	Bachelor's or 3-Year College Degree	47 (43.93)
	Doctor's Degree	48 (44.86)
	Master's Degree	11 (10.28)
	Other	1 (0.93)
Working years	3 years	60 (56.07)
	4-6 years	36 (33.64)
	7-9 years	6 (5.61)
	10-12 years	4 (3.74)
	13 years	1 (0.93)

5.5 Professional Materials, Equipment and Approaches

When attributing sources of funding for remediation, local government funds were highlighted by 67% of practitioners, with national special-purpose funds and businesses that were responsible for pollution (58% and 60%, respectively) being identified as being responsible for funding remediation activities. Only 40% and 13% highlighted land developers and third-party sponsors, respectively. Most contaminated sites are occupied by the state because of historical industrial development, with often unregulated activities. The old industries closed or moved out of the city center, leaving many contaminated sites that need to be remediated for use for residential construction or other public buildings. Land developers funded the remediation, which occurs much more frequently in developed cities rather than in small undeveloped cities as residential buildings are more popular in bigger cities because of the large population and better awareness and education in developed areas.

The application of remediation technologies in companies surveyed includes a range of bespoke and specialist tools. When assessing the role of intellectual property rights (IPR) in companies, patents on processes/tools were the most significant, with 40% of respondents identifying these. Other IPR protection included trade secrets (18%), copyrights and trademarks, both at 13%, which means that combining research and development with marketing for business development is a

strong driver (the patent number could be shown on promotional materials, while trade secrets are an opaque long-term control on technology). Although trade secrets also imply competitive advantage, a company applying for a patent could see a fee reduction from the State Intellectual Property Office, as well as being more transparent in identifying the approach being used.

Typical steps for site investigation play a key role in remediation and the results show that solidification/stabilization, landfill, and chemical oxidation/reduction technology are more popular than phytoremediation, bioremediation, and plant–microbial remediation. The more rapid physical/chemical treatment as opposed to more long-term slow biotechnology is not as popular with industries in China. Absorbents are the most popular approach for professional materials provided by industries, and drilling and piling equipment is one of the more popular types of equipment applied in site development.

5.6 Decision Making Support

Decision-making in soil remediation projects was determined by remediation target value (76%), the nature of land use (for purpose of growing crops or building or fishing) of 69%, expert judgement (65%), specific rules and regulations (50%), government conditions (45%), and enterprise investment (29%).

Existing construction methods and appropriate technology were highlighted as the most common factor affecting the competitive advantage of the company in the soil remediation sector. New product / equipment development ranked as the second for ‘strongly agreed’ with both service / product price changes and market position third. Existing construction means and technology, and service / product price changes ranked first and second in the ‘agreed’ group. The most important considerations for setting remedial targets included future land usage, the availability of national and industrial standards, and specific government conditions, respectively. Government planning and capital budgeting ranked along with technical means and payback period as the highest priorities in the survey ‘agreed’ group for target setting in remediation.

For verification of the success of remediation, the most important factors considered were the data on the frequency of testing, checkup, and acceptance (validation data), project delivery and completion, and the wider socioeconomic benefits from remediation. All four factors were highlighted by more than 83% of respondents to verify success of remediation programs. As shown in Fig.5, factors important in commercial decision making for soil remediation are remediation target value > capital guarantee > existing technology and means.

Figure 5.4 Importance of specific project factors in commercial decision making for site remediation projects

In addition to the main driving factors and historical development of the site, importance was also given to wider public opinion, corporate environmental awareness, and experience/company track record (past performance of similar projects). Additional drivers included the past and future land use scenarios in commercial decision.

Remediation of agricultural soil is a long-term project that is normally based at national and local government level to ensure food safety over the long-term. It is typically a large-scale, regional activity and often includes a combination of agents and agricultural production. One example highlighted in the consultation was to consider crop use. In planting corn in less contaminated

shallow layers of soil, food safety was preserved, but changing to planting sorghum introduced a higher-risk land use due to deeper rooting and exposure to more contaminated soil. If the contaminated site was used for construction after remediation, the project was smaller scale with a much shorter project construction period compared to remediation of agricultural land. The approaches to agricultural land included treatment along with appropriate crop production, working at a larger scale and over a longer project remediation cycle. In terms of the capital guarantee, the risk of the budget was generally assessed in the feasibility research phase of the project. The choice of methods applied for the treatment could be decided with the consideration of the budget.

5.7 Case study—Application of Sepiolite Tailing for Remediation

Modified and activated sepiolite materials are commonly applied as soil conditioners, pesticide carriers, or soil amendments (Song *et al.*, 2021). Hunan Province has extensive contamination from potentially toxic elements caused by excessive base metal mining and industrial production activity (Delang, 2017), and produces a range of sepiolite mineral products which has resulted in a wide range of associated by-product materials (Song *et al.*, 2021). The opportunity for their utilization was explored in part of the questionnaire, highlighting the potential of sepiolite for soil stabilization and later vegetable growth.

The questionnaire results show 48% of respondents had experience with soil stabilization or solidification, and of this >13% was specifically using sepiolite-derived materials (as shown in Fig. 5.5). Here, 57% used sepiolite composite/modified products, with 26% and 17% of respondents using raw sepiolite mining and processing by-products, respectively. Among all materials applied in solidification, 35% of respondents and 20% of respondents used clay minerals and other minerals, respectively. During the respondents who applied clay minerals, 36% respondents used sepiolite based materials during the stabilization. The use of chemical treatment-based remediation (29% of respondents) compared to biological (11% of respondents) suggests the former application may be a better choice due to the speed of treatment and relative ease of validation.

Figure 5.5 Percent of people has experience of sepiolite for solidification or stabilization

5.8 Commercial Consideration

Interview results revealed that >45% of interviewees were in companies involved in both remediation and solid waste treatment. Discussion included the potential for soil treatment and solid waste disposal for most hazardous materials. Challenges of post-remediation testing were highlighted and the source of long-term funding for monitoring. The potential for cross-subsidy from MSW handling fees and costs of remediation was considered as unsustainable due to the high volume of soil needing to be remediated. Other opportunities include the potential of energy generation from waste. However, the commercial model for waste handling in China is still at a very early stage of development.

5.9 Summary and conclusion

This chapter addressed and fulfilled RQ. 2: 'Can remediation and waste management business be mapped using site distribution and data from the website, online database and questionnaire feedback?' SO. 2.1: 'To collect all data and information pertaining to the remediation and waste management businesses in China.' The site distribution and data of remediation and waste

management business were shown in Table 5.1. SO. 2.2: 'To analyse the SWMS in China with consideration of waste material classification: MSW from cities and suburban areas, industrial solid waste (ISW) from industries and processing, and HW from contaminated sites and industries', data from official documents and copies of feedback from the questionnaire are collected and analyzed. The amount of MSW collected, transported, and rendered harmless treated of PRC in 1980-2019 was described in figure 5.2. The amount of ISW generated and disposed of PRC in 2003-2017 and their disposal rate was described in figure 5.3. The challenges, institutional arrangements and characteristics of services in the implementation of existing MSW management, HSW management, ISW management and recycling SWMS etc. in mainland China were investigated.

The results showed that those characteristics have key impact to the interaction between the SWMS and policy in industries. The analysis of these features helps to understand the reason why old problems exist and the origins of current practices in China, and to what degree the problems could be solved properly.

This chapter also addressed RQ.3: 'What can be done to improve the land remediation efficiency and help the projects choose the most suitable remediation scheme and all decision were made reasonable?'. SO. 3.1: 'To develop decision-making support in soil/sediment with consideration of analysis on data or information collected in the questionnaire and interview' was fulfilled via analyzing the data collected from the questionnaire feedbacks and interviews. The results of project cost, the factors that affect the advantage of the company on soil remediation and the factors in verifying the success of remediation are shown and discussed in this chapter. Decision-making factors that were affected by commercial decision making in consideration of the successful implementation of projects. The impact of the shortage of contamination on ecology and long-term monitoring of remediation needs to be considered by remediation practitioners. Development of solid waste management and background of remediation business was investigated for policymaking and fulfilment of 'Dual Carbon Target'.

Chapter 6 New technologies for soil pollution treatment -sepiolite-based waste application

6.1 Introduction

A case study for remediation decision-making: sepiolite solid waste application in soil remediation. Sepiolite was chosen as a case study because China hosts one of the major sepiolite reserves in China and deposits of Hunan province have provided raw materials for purification of high-quality sepiolite products for industrial application. It also links strongly to current practice in the remediation sector (see results from questionnaire investigation presented in Chapter 5), Hunan province is famous for their PTEs pollution in soil and sepiolite could be applied in this sector to reduce or stop second contamination of polluted soil long-distance transportation in China.

The previous chapter addressed and fulfilled RQ.2: 'Can remediation and waste management business be mapped using site distribution and data from the website, online database and questionnaire feedback?' The questionnaires and interviews were carried out to collect information and data on remediation industries and practitioners. The result showed that waste ban implementation in China and the Covid attacks have impacted the waste management system of solid waste, policies and soil remediation businesses in China that provide different forms of problems and possibilities, which in turn have improved the solid waste management reforms and remediation business decision making support or companies screening for better schemes in distinct ways. To address new trends in the remediation sector, with the emphasis on the waste application in remediation as a sustainable or wide-ranging strategy in the world. This chapter will address SO. 3.2: To investigate the difference between remediation and waste management via budget, techniques and experiences for projects in China' This chapter also addresses RQ. 4:'Can solid waste be recycled to treat contamination in remediation business using existing data?' This chapter addresses the research question via primary specific objectives. SO. 4.1: 'To assess the potential for standards, laws, and regulations updates to consider technologies, such as solidification/stabilization/immobilization, in the treatment/control of environmental hazard and prevention from further pollution' was addressed by discussing the reason or potential of sepiolite based waste applied in remediation projects, which describes the main sepiolite distribution in China and finally give a case study of sepiolite tailing application for remediation.

SO. 4.2: 'To quantify the business link between waste management and remediation via sepiolite waste application potential as a case study' was achieved with the application of an alternative to

The word cloud picture (Fig. 6.1) is produced by software Nvivo12 with an analysis of key content of combinations of materials. Figures 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4 are produced from Microsoft Office 2010 Excel by frequencies analysis to all additives of combinations of materials. All of them get checked if they (natural sepiolite, modified sepiolite, sepiolite tailings) are used as an additive to combine other additives for PTEs treatment in water, soil, land, sludge. There are published papers and patents (English abstract from different countries) in the database Web of Science. Only published patents and licensed patents are shown in the US patent office (in English) and Chinese patent database (in Chinese). A patent is only counted as one though this one might be published and licensed in more than one document.

To synthesize a large amount of literature and patents published on sepiolite, a word cloud picture has been prepared (Fig. 6.1). Figures 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4 describe the results in more detail.

Figure 6.2 Variation of additives in sepiolite-based composites (in literature reports 1864–2018)

Figure 6.3 Variation of additives in sepiolite-based composites (in literature reports 1864–2018)

Figure 6.4 Variation of additives in sepiolite-based composites (in literature reports 1864–2018)

A total of 10 materials appear with the frequency of application between 16 and 140 times used in the formation of composites with sepiolite, followed by lime (31), bentonite (27), chitosan based (25), zeolite based (25), activated carbon (20), modified sepiolite (19), calcium source (19) and straw based (18) (Fig. 2). We identified 16 materials with a frequency of application between 10 and 16,

the highest being fly ash (15), followed by phosphate-based (14), modified iron or iron (13), while potassium-based, polyacrylamide, clay mineral, water and humic acid showed the same frequency (12), followed by starch, biochar, calcium-magnesium phosphate, diatomite and cellulose-based (11), montmorillonite, kaolin and shell (10) (Fig. 3). There are 24 materials in the frequencies of 5 - 9, with the highest frequency is silica-based (9), followed by humate-based (7), while carbonate-based, limestone, peat and polyvinyl alcohol-based were at the same frequency (8), followed by fruit peel, urea and Zn sulfate (6), charcoal-based, aluminium-based, ammonium sulfate, vermiculite, manure, alumina, cattle manure biochar, ferrous sulfate, glass beads, sodium alginate, cement, gamma-alumina, seaweed, palygorskite and polyethylene glycol (5). In addition, the frequencies of 1 - 4 from all other kinds of materials are included in the other figure (Fig. 6.4).

Fly ash or coal fly ash is an industrial by-product generated from the combustion of coal for thermal power generation and other combustion activities (Ahmaruzzaman, 2010). In addition, bottom ash and lagooned ash are formed during the combustion of coal. Bottom ash shows a similar phase, particle morphology and chemical composition with fly ash though the unburnt coal component and proportion of amorphous particle is greater than that of fly ash. Lagooned ash shows an intermediate, particle morphology and phase between fly ash and bottom ash (Vassilev, 1992). There are mainly two classes of fly ash, class F contains more than 8% CaO and class C contains less than 8% CaO. Both contain various oxides Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , Na_2O , MgO , MnO , P_2O_5 and TiO_2 . Other elements (Cu, Pb, Cd, Cr) and radioactive isotopes (^{232}Th , ^{238}U , ^{40}K) can also be found in some fly ash (Wang *et al.*, 2020).

Emissions and accumulation of fly ash not only occupy land, but also cause serious pollution to the environment and poses a disposal challenge (Ochedi *et al.*, 2020). However, fly ash is also a resource that can be widely applied in the fields of construction materials, road sub-base, mine backfill etc. (Ahmaruzzaman, 2010), and fly ash also shows a promising ability as a heterogeneous catalyst to oxidize aqueous Na_2S solution (Mallik and Chaudhuri, 1999) or sorbent to remove various air pollution (Ahmaruzzaman and Gupta, 2012; Ochedi *et al.*, 2020). Fly ash is utilized as a constituent of mixtures for solidification/stabilization technologies because of its low-cost, good pozzolanic properties, which helps with solid waste disposal and coping with potential stress of its large generation and accumulation in an economically beneficial way (Terzano *et al.*, 2005).

The influence of fly ash on properties of sepiolite is carried out by adding fly ash to the sepiolite with 2%, 4% and 6% by weight (Joseph and Angel, 2020). The results showed that the pH of the mixture is decreased with a content increase in fly ash. The specific gravity and the Atterberg limit of the mixture showed a negative trend with an additional increase in fly ash. The mechanical standard compaction test results revealed a slight increase in the maximum dry density and a decrease in the

optimum moisture content with an increase percentage of fly ash in the mixture. The strength and permeability of the mixture were improved up to 4% of the fly ash content, after that they showed a decrease in trend. The maximum values of strength and permeability of the sepiolite were reached at 4% addition of fly ash (Joseph and Angel, 2020).

All of the sepiolite-based material additives might have a good effect on water treatment which is recyclable and low cost. They are much safer and cheaper to be added in soil but could still be more difficult to control the amount of sepiolite-based material and combined ratio because of various soil background comparing with other soil remediation methods.

6.3 Economic constraints for the application of sepiolite in remediation

6.3.1 Direct project cost and period of treatment

In the research of potential for ensuring the safety of production of rice planted in Cd-polluted soil by using sepiolite and humic acid, the production was studied using *Oryza sativa* L. (Jia-33) in which the accumulation of Cd with different weights of additives (including humic acid at 0.750, 2.250, 3.750, 5.250, 7.500 t/ha; or sepiolite at 2.250, 6.750, 11.250, 15.750, 22.500 t/ha, or combination of humic acid and sepiolite at 0.375 + 1.125, 1.125 + 3.375, 1.875 + 5.625, 2.625 + 7.875, 3.750 + 11.250 t/ha) was assessed (Xie *et al.*, 2018). Results showed that applications of humic acid are at 5.250 t/ha, or sepiolite at 6.750 t/ha or a combination of humic acid at 1.125 t/ha and sepiolite at 3.375 t/ha leads to that Cd content of polished rice were 0.171 ± 0.01 mg/kg, 0.184 ± 0.01 mg/kg, and 0.181 ± 0.01 mg/kg, respectively, lowering than the Cd limit 0.2 mg/kg defined in the National Food Safety Standard (GB 2762-2012) of the PRC. The material purchase prices were 197.59 \$/t of humic acid, 112.91 \$/t of sepiolite, which means that the corresponding cost of applications of 5.250 t/ha humic acid, 6.750 t/ha sepiolite, the combination of 1.125 t/ha humic acid and 3.375 t/ha sepiolite were 1037.34, 762.13 and 433.99 \$/ha, respectively (Xie *et al.*, 2018).

Research has shown that Cd passivated by the soil amendment calcium-magnesium phosphate and lime starts to re-release from the fourth year, which revealed that the passivation effect could last for 3 years (Jiang *et al.*, 2017). This is much better than more intrusive stabilization methods such as lime/cement as soil function is preserved to some extent. Regardless of human resource and in terms of the cost of the materials, the lowest cost for the combination of humic acid at 1.125 t/ha and sepiolite at 3.375 t/ha with the average annual cost is about 144.66 \$/ha. This further illustrates the potential of low accumulation strains of rice combined with the application of the sepiolite to meet agricultural safety standards (Xie *et al.*, 2018).

6.3.2 Remediation potential for contaminated land

Sepiolite is applied as amendments or immobilizers for remediation of soils contaminated with PTEs. The remediation efficiency and function of sepiolite on the remediation Pb and Cd-polluted farmland have been verified with field studies by Zhan *et al.* (2019). The pH value of soils increased by 1.67 after the application of sepiolite, whereas the CaCl₂-extractable concentration of Cd and the exchangeable concentration of Pb in soils decreased by 63.4% and 21.5%, respectively. The results indicated that immobilization mechanisms for the sepiolite may be complex, which not only involved with surface adsorption due to high specific surface but also involved with a high ion-exchange capacity of sepiolite (Zhan *et al.*, 2019).

Sepiolite materials alone or in a combination with other materials such as limestone/bentonite/calcium carbonate can significantly cut down the content of Cd in brown rice, regardless of its application in a field study or pot trials (Sun *et al.*; 2016a,b; Wu *et al.*, 2016; Li *et al.*, 2020). For instance, when sepiolite combined with low Cd-accumulating cultivar rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) in field experiment, the concentration of Cd in brown rice of low Cd-accumulating cultivar rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) from the control group was 0.72 mg/kg, while the concentration of Cd in brown rice of the cultivar rice from the experimental group was 0.18mg/kg, which is lower than that of the maximum amount level proposed as “Maximum Levers of Pollutants in Foods” standard (GB 2762-2012) in the Chinese national standard and the Codex Alimentarius Commission (CAC 153-1995) requirement in the World Health Organization (WHO) (Liang *et al.*, 2014).

However, there are differences in remediation effects of sepiolite-based amendment on soil polluted with Cd, Pb. For example, a 3-year in situ experiment was carried out in a paddy soil around a mine of southern Hunan, China (Wu *et al.*, 2016). The combined amendment (LS, limestone and sepiolite) was applied in order of 0, 2, 4 and 8 g/kg (w/w) and rice were subsequently planted in 2012 (first season), 2013 (second season) and 2014 (third season). The results showed that the pH values of soils increased significantly in all three seasons and the ranking of enhancement was as follows: the first season > the second season > the third season. Experiment results indicated that the effect of the LS on reducing exchangeable Pb and Cd content of soil ranked as follows: the first season (97.6–99.8%) > the second season (80.7–97.7%) > the third season (32.6–97.7%) for Pb and the first season (88.3–98.9%) > the second season (28.3–88.0%) > the third season (8.3–71.4%) for Cd, respectively. It showed that the effects were persistent on soil exchangeable Cd concentration but gradually decreased with time on soil exchangeable Pb concentration, which implied that LS was more suitable for Cd than Pb contaminated soil in long-term remediation (Wu *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, a 2-year consecutive experiment was conducted on immobilization effect of sepiolite alone by Liang *et al.* (2016), which revealed that immobilization effect is maintained seen in the decrease in Cd content

of the rice, 0.025 M HCl extractable Cd content of paddy soil and the soil exchangeable Cd in the second year without any additional amendment.

6.4 Economic impacts and project risk

In China, contaminated land is identified by the government or local authority. Typically, several contamination treatment enterprises will compete via tender to secure a pollution treatment project. Once a firm is appointed, a feasibility report for soil remediation is required for the company to obtain final approval from the relevant authority. The specific details of the project are then decided; this involves a comparison of remediation technologies and methods. The project would be carried out after the approval is granted; then immediate or long-term monitoring of contamination treatment results would be arranged based on the design.

To use sepiolite for the treatment of land contamination by PTEs will increase the value or quality of the land and its potential possibility for reuse commercial purpose, create more space for residential development in the area, increasing employment in land remediation and redevelopment, which bring more local tax revenues (Song *et al.*, 2019). With the development of society and new knowledge gained by individuals, the choice of methodology for soil remediation could be combined with positive interactions with neighborhoods, for example through community center development as part of the remediation, which can satisfy the social and economic needs of different stakeholders. This would support the harmonious integration of new solutions for contamination treatment within surrounding communities and lead to a more sustainable local economy (Dagenhart *et al.*, 2006).

When remediation projects involved some related risk, the regular lifestyle might be impacted, affecting local traffic movement, environmental degradation during project implementation, or for workers' safety during the remediation period and even neighbor nuisance complaints. Recent studies of a farmland remediation project (Xu *et al.*, 2019) showed that by adopting species sensitivity distribution models with joint probability curves, a different conclusion was reached related to ecological risk assessment results compared to that of the traditional methods. The conclusion revealed that Cr indicated the highest risk at 84.3% that presents an 84.3% probability for 5% of the species to exceed NOEC/LOECs (maximum no-effect concentration and the lowest effective concentration) in Zhuzhou City (Xu *et al.*, 2019). This study showed that the soil ecological risk of exposure to PTEs is underestimated by traditional methods and prioritizing ecosystem protection could be considered for PTEs contaminated land treatment (Xu *et al.*, 2019). However, in the site where sepiolite-based material is applied, microbial community diversity and soil enzymatic activities showed that soil metabolic function is a certain degree recovered and sepiolite application is environmentally friendly (Sun *et al.*, 2016b).

Ultimately sepiolite, its modified forms and components of the recovered waste provides remediation capability by immobilizing contaminants and restricting migration in the aqueous phase. This reduces food chain transfer and may be enhanced by combining with various additives. However, when considering the complex characteristics of the soil, the effectiveness and durability of sepiolite-based materials could be decreased with low pH (Chen *et al.*, 2020), releasing pollution and making PTEs bio-accessible to crops and even increase the risk to humans. Constant changes in soil environment and soil quality will continue to present new challenges to application amount control of products and monitoring by environmental laboratories. The use of sepiolite as an additive for soil remediation may require additional testing that has not included within regulatory methods.

6.5 Summary and conclusion

This chapter addressed RQ. 4: 'Can solid waste be recycled to treat contamination in remediation business using existing data?' and revealed the steps of key waste in considered materials pond and its application details. It explores the main representative materials (slag ash) in the solid waste management sector in China; sepiolite based solid waste regular managed technologies; distribution of sepiolite in China; a detailed case study of sepiolite tailing application for remediation.

SO. 4.1: 'To assess the potential for standards, laws, and regulations updates to consider technologies, such as solidification/stabilization/immobilization, in the treatment/control of environmental hazard and prevention from further pollution' was completed by assessing the status of sepiolite in China and local regulations that promoted the development of sepiolite mining, research and development of sepiolite based products, and further considering the processing byproduct of sepiolite or mining in the waste management sector. SO. 4.2: 'To quantify the business link between waste management and remediation via sepiolite waste application potential as a case study' was achieved with the selection of sepiolite as a case study to verify the feasibility of application of solid waste in the cleanup of contaminated sediment, soil or land. The findings showed that characteristics of waste (huge amount of mining tailings, porous fibrous structure of sepiolite, low sepiolite purity which limits various casual applications or incineration directly) had made the waste possible to be an alternative of raw materials imported.

This chapter additionally addressed RQ.3: 'What can be done to improve the land remediation efficiency and help the projects choose the most suitable remediation scheme and all decision were made reasonable?' SO. 3.2: 'To investigate the difference between remediation and waste management via budget, techniques, and experiences for projects in China' was fulfilled by identification on the reduction of landfill space or cost, the cost efficiency of the waste, safer application in the environment, and its capacity to absorb the PTEs to influence industrial decisions.

The results explained the financial reasons such as the cost it saved as waste for landfills and potential benefit attained in the remediation business.

This chapter presented one example that described the potential of solid waste that can be successfully applied or reused to treat the contamination/pollution in land or soil. Further recommendations for further study will be presented in the next chapter.

Chapter 7 Conclusions, contributions and recommendations

7.1 Introduction

Chapter 1 presented a background to the research and described all issues being investigated. Chapter 1 also set out the research context, 4 research questions, and 9 specific objectives in the outline of the research. Chapter 1 additionally described the main contribution, structure of this research. Chapter 2 revealed a literature review of the research topic with published literatures on the research topic, specific objectives and research questions. Chapter 2 also presented the research core/theme of this research. Chapter 3 described the various method used to answer research questions and solved related research specific objectives. It additionally showed the justification for the selection of methods. Chapter 4 displayed waste management policies and assessed the interaction effect pertaining to the waste management system and policy change. Chapter 4 also investigated the relationship between waste management and remediation sector. Chapter 4 insisted that economy growth and cities' expansion led to the upgrades of the SWMS in China. Chapter 5 analyzed the SWMS due to the interaction effect between solid waste management and remediation found in chapter 4. Chapter 5 further introduced support for soil remediation business which is a result of data analysis of copies of questionnaire feedback and interview. Chapter 6 further explored the detail of the triangle description for the development of the remediation business and waste management industries. Chapter 6 discussed the remediation business - waste application in remediation and assessed the sepiolite-based waste potential in remediation projects. The whole thesis structure is shown in Figure 1.1 in chapter 1. The description for waste management, soil remediation and business were shown in Figure 7.1.

This chapter will present conclusions, contributions, and recommendations on the overall implications of the study.

7.2 Conclusions

7.2.1 Research contribution

This study made several contributions to acknowledging the world with wider policy relevance, new remediation status in China and technical advance in remediation sector. These comprise:

Wider policy relevance

- a. Lessons could be learned for those countries who might consider taking similar action to import ban and face similar trouble later in that way after the import ban implementation

through discussion on challenges and opportunities for waste management companies in China.

- b. The pandemic brings more challenges to the SWMS than before. It gives a clue to the world that how quickly the SWMS can respond particularly post-pandemic will be an important step to establishing sustainable management systems.
- c. A perspective on issues that impaired the positive impact of the waste ban in a domestic context under consideration of landfill mining situation, urbanization, and policy change.

New information on remediation status in China

- a. The remediation business has been researched from practitioners' opinions in China providing a data set of remediation status since the start of the remediation.
- b. Remediation distribution maps have been generated for China, including areas without any site description before.
- c. A triangular description for relationship between waste management, remediation, and industries was developed which can be applied for future discussion in industries, especially in the aspect of regulation designing, related research methods, and development of industries.

Technical advance in remediation sector

- a. A new method of sepiolite-based waste application for contaminated soil or land remediation was developed which is applicable in remediation industries where budget is a significant parameter in decision making in projects.
- b. The recycling and application potential of solid waste generated was reviewed or assessed to deal with pollution problems in Hunan Province, which reduces the landfill space requirement for both waste and contaminated soil and increases the economic life cycle of the waste.

7.2.2 Description for waste management, soil remediation and industries

Figure 7.1 Description for waste management, soil remediation and industries in the thesis

7.2.3 The research limitations and recommendations

This study investigates Chinese soil remediation industrial staff in questionnaire and interview, which is of its particular characteristics because of developing country background where there are large populations, various climates and complex regional characteristics. Budget concerns, regulations/laws and governmental administrations in this sector also play a distinctive role in decision-making for processes of soil remediation. The study of policies change impact on waste management system and the review of sepiolite waste application potential could not cover all aspects and possibilities, such as various scales of land in waste application. For all the above reasons, this research limited its analysis on basis of the national SWMS, which might not represent all areas in the country. Limitations arise from decisions of methods and human analysis paths during the research progress. Although decisions are made after much consideration of picking the most suitable method or analysis path to attain the best research outputs, each decision of new consideration and new parameters continually create limitations which are significant to acknowledge and discuss.

Wider data relevance

The research focuses on the combination of theory and research in the collection of literature and materials. It mainly organizes the relevant statistical data and relevant papers/literature published on the official website of the government and the China Statistics Yearbooks of Statistics of China. It

also discusses the upgrading of the SWMS through a comparative analysis of the methods. However, it is impossible to compare and analyze all data from all countries around the world due to the limitation of time for the research and the length of the thesis. Further research could be carried on investigation and analysis of data corresponding to solid waste management from more countries.

Legislative implementation

There is shortage of detailed analyses of the companies that ceased trading or of the rise in unemployment in the sector due to the waste ban, which suggests strongly that future study on a pilot study on the companies which is going to address any negative impact that needs to be included in policymaking or implementation. The result of the research shows the emergence of 'zero waste city' and 'big data' applications in waste management system. Further research on the consideration of advantages and disadvantages of implementation in the big scale policy 'zero waste city' and 'big data' application needs to be included as urgent priorities.

Technical advance in remediation sector

There is no long-term post-project monitoring on efficiency, such as long-term monitoring of PTEs' solidification and stabilization in remediation projects for Chinese status. Another weakness is the shortage of fundamental research on the effect of contaminants to animal existence, human health, and the biosphere around the polluted sites. The results suggest strongly that more research on contaminants' effect to the existence/survival of animals, human health, and the environment around the contaminated sites, which will help practitioners deal with project risk assessment during the whole project progress. Proposals for change in post-project monitoring need to be included to address the potential future effect of contaminants on human healthy after construction completion of buildings. More investigation is needed to clarify the appropriate scale of land application, the development of technology to meet that and the potential for regulation change to allow stabilization and immobilization of the environmental hazard. Besides, a more sophisticated Scientometrics analysis could be finished after the introduction of software tools to assess trajectories and relationship fields, which would provide knowledge maps and research intelligence.

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Appendix I

Data for Fig. 4.1 and Fig. 4.2 in main thesis:

Main renewable resources imports to the PRC for 2014-2020 (CMC, 2016-2019, <http://www.intracen.org>)

Main renewable resources imports to the PRC (Unit: 10 kilo-tons)								
No.	Types	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
1	Iron and steel scraps	256.0	233.0	216.1	232.3	134.3	18.4	2.7
2	Nonferrous metal scraps	618.1	576.7	527.5	574.3	399.4	294.9	198.6
3	Waste plastics	825.4	735.4	734.7	582.9	5.1	0.1	0.0
4	Waste paper	2752.0	2928.0	2849.8	2571.7	1702.5	1094.5	689.3
5	Total	4055.9	4104.0	3990.5	3593.6	1985.7	1219.2	763.5

Ps: 1. Importation of nonferrous metal scraps refer to aluminum-containing scrap, copper-containing scrap, and zinc-containing scrap; 2. When calculating the total amount, the amount of imported non-ferrous metal scrap is converted by 36%.

Prices of main categories of recyclable waste generated in PRC before and after the ban (unit: Yuan/t)

Prices before and after the ban (unit: Yuan/t)						
No.	Waste type	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
1	Iron and steel scraps	2050.03	1379.97	1350.03	1749.99	1844.90
2	Nonferrous metal scraps	16600.25	15931.51	19519.74	19521.13	19800.00
3	Waste plastics	5500.00	4500.00	5100.11	6386.89	6500.00
4	Waste paper	1393.98	1330.09	1500.10	1849.95	1954.47
5	Used tires	1600.00	1296.81	1396.04	1449.70	1460.94
6	WEEE	2496.82	2250.00	2579.23	3344.92	3500.00
7	Waste glass	300.58	250.59	260.47	300.00	350.00
8	Waste battery (except lead acid)	19800.00	18500.00	20666.67	20722.22	22157.89

Data for Fig. 4.4 in main thesis:

Frequencies of revisions to national laws and regulations in the PRC (1991-2020)

Year	Frequency of laws and regulations updated
1991	1
1996	2
2001	2
2005	1
2008	1
2009	1
2011	2
2013	1
2015	3
2016	1
2017	4
2018	1
2019	1
2020	2

Data for Fig. 4.5 in main thesis:

Time series analysis of the amount solid waste produced in a southern city of the PRC (2016-2020)

Amount and average amount generated of solid waste in South city ($\times 10^6$kg)											
Month Year	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	Jun.	Jul.	Aug.	Sep.	Oct.	Nov.
2020	37.92	23.72	36.98	40.00	42.77	42.46	42.88	40.56	41.55	44.06	41.36
2020A	39.48	39.48	39.48	39.48	39.48	39.48	39.48	39.48	39.48	39.48	39.48
2019	25.78	29.41	41.74	41.53	33.37	32.96	26.07	39.25	38.53	41.12	38.64
2019A	35.31	35.31	35.31	35.31	35.31	35.31	35.31	35.31	35.31	35.31	35.31
2018	27.35	28.40	36.49	20.93	38.30	22.81	24.97	16.10	22.79	38.43	32.77
2018A	27.32	27.32	27.32	27.32	27.32	27.32	27.32	27.32	27.32	27.32	27.32
2017	30.62	25.25	31.55	35.32	35.57	25.23	29.08	26.14	33.63	34.71	34.33
2017A	30.18	30.18	30.18	30.18	30.18	30.18	30.18	30.18	30.18	30.18	30.18
2016	31.55	27.90	35.90	30.64	33.90	33.47	31.15	24.16	31.09	34.03	29.41
2016A	31.35	31.35	31.35	31.35	31.35	31.35	31.35	31.35	31.35	31.35	31.35

Data for Fig. 5.1 in main thesis: (Q16&Q17 in questionnaire)

Q16&17: What is stage in project do you think the following remediation-related standards / regulations are used?

Frequency of use (%) for each relevant regulation / standard for different phases of remediation projects

Laws or regulations Choice	HJ 25.1- 2019	HJ 25.2- 2019	HJ 25.3- 2019	HJ 25.4- 2019	HJ 25.5- 2018	HJ 25.6- 2019	HJ 964- 2018	HJ 682- 2019	MEPA 【 2017】 No. 72
Never	7	9	9	8	7	6	19	4	9
Use in the risk assessment phase	30	26	37	23	27	25	30	4	26
Use repeatedly in the entire project decision	59	61	49	64	60	63	44	21	57
N/A	11	11	12	12	13	13	14	6	15

Laws or regulations Choice	LPRCPCSC	SC 【2016】 31	MEP No. 42	MSEMIML	HJ/T 166-2004	GB 15618- 2018	GB 36600- 2018	Local standard s	Others
Never	8	9	9	13	8	9	7	8	15
Use in the risk assessment phase	15	17	17	22	27	22	19	23	15
Use repeatedly in the entire project decision	69	65	66	56	57	61	69	61	30
N/A	15	16	15	16	15	15	12	15	47

Data for Fig. 5.2 in main thesis:

Frequency of use (%) for each relevant regulation / standard for different phases of remediation projects Amount of municipal solid waste collected, transported, and rendered harmless (treated) for the PRC in 1980-2020 (all annual data are collected from the National Bureau of Statistics of PRC, Available at: <http://www.stats.gov.cn/tjsj./ndsj/> (accessed on 1 July 2022).

Year	Quantity of Collected and Transported (Million ton)	Quantity of Harmlessly Treated (Million ton)	Collected and Transported	Harmlessly Treated	Disposal Rate of Municipal Solid Wastes (%)
1980	3132	215	31.32	2.15	6.86
1981	2606	162	26.06	1.62	6.22
1982	3125	190	31.25	1.9	6.08
1983	3452	243	34.52	2.43	7.04
1984	3757	188	37.57	1.88	5.00
1985	4477	232	44.77	2.32	5.18
1986	5009	70	50.09	0.7	1.40
1987	5398	54	53.98	0.54	1.00
1988	5751	75	57.51	0.75	1.30
1989	6292	111	62.92	1.11	1.76
1990	6767	212	67.67	2.12	3.13
1991	7636	1239	76.36	12.39	16.23
1992	8262	2829	82.62	28.29	34.24
1993	8791	3945	87.91	39.45	44.88
1994	9952	4782	99.52	47.82	48.05
1995	10671	6014	106.71	60.14	56.36
1996	10825	5568	108.25	55.68	51.44
1997	10982	6292	109.82	62.92	57.29
1998	11302	6783	113.02	67.83	60.02
1999	11415	7232	114.15	72.32	63.36
2000	11819	7255	118.19	72.55	61.38
2001	13470	7840	134.7	78.4	58.20
2002	13650	7404	136.5	74.04	54.24
2003	14857	7545	148.57	75.45	50.78
2004	15509	8089	155.09	80.89	52.16
2005	15577	8051	155.77	80.51	51.69
2006	14841	7873	148.41	78.73	53.05
2007	15215	9438	152.15	94.38	62.03
2008	15438	10307	154.38	103.07	66.76

Year	Quantity of Collected and Transported (Million ton)	Quantity of Harmlessly Treated (Million ton)	Collected and Transported	Harmlessly Treated	Disposal Rate of Municipal Solid Wastes (%)
2009	15734	11220	157.34	112.2	71.31
2010	15805	12318	158.05	123.18	77.94
2011	16395	13090	163.95	130.9	79.84
2012	17081	14490	170.81	144.9	84.83
2013	17239	15394	172.39	153.94	89.30
2014	17860	16394	178.6	163.94	91.79
2015	19142	18013	191.42	180.13	94.10
2016	20362	19674	203.62	196.74	96.62
2017	21521	21034	215.21	210.34	97.74
2018	22802	22565	228.02	225.65	98.96
2019	24206	24013	242.06	240.13	99.20
2020	23512	23452	235.12	234.52	99.74

Data for Fig. 5.3 in main thesis:

Amount of industrial solid waste generated and disposed of PRC in 2003-2017 and their disposal rate (All annual data are collected from the National Bureau of Statistics of PRC

<http://www.stats.gov.cn/tjsj./ndsj/>) (accessed on 1 July 2022).

Year	Common Industrial Solid Wastes Generated (MT)	Common Industrial Solid Wastes Treated and Disposed (MT)	Disposal Rate of Industrial Solid Wastes (%)
2003	1004.28	177.51	17.68
2004	1200.30	266.35	22.19
2005	1344.49	312.59	23.25
2006	1515.41	428.83	28.30
2007	1756.32	413.50	23.54
2008	1901.27	482.91	25.40
2009	2039.43	474.88	23.28
2010	2409.44	572.64	23.77
2011	3227.72	704.65	21.83
2012	3290.44	707.45	21.50
2013	3277.02	829.69	25.32
2014	3256.20	803.88	24.69
2015	3270.79	730.34	22.33
2016	3092.10	655.22	21.19
2017	3315.92	797.98	24.07
2018	3315.92	797.98	24.07
2019	3867.51	943.16	24.39
2020	3675.46	917.49	24.96

Data for Fig. 5.4 in main thesis: (Q26 in questionnaire)

Q26: In the site remediation project, please use 1, 2, 3 to rank the following factors to rank their importance in project business decision making?

Importance of specific project factors in commercial decision making for site remediation projects

Ranking \ Factors	Remediation target value	Capital guarantee	Existing technology and means
1	41	37	19
2	30	25	35
3	23	29	38
Empty	13	16	15
Score	3	2	1
Importance of factor	1.93	1.78	1.54

Data for Fig. 5.5 in main thesis: (Q14 in questionnaire)

Q14: Do you have experience of applying sepiolite-based material in soil stabilization?

Percent of people has experience of sepiolite for solidification or stabilization

Yes	14	13.08%
No	91	85.05%
Not sure	2	1.87%
Sum	107	100.00%

Data for Fig. 6.1 in main thesis:

A picture of word cloud to show materials associated with sepiolite treatment for treatment of PTEs contamination

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
1	Chuxiong Deng, Jiajun Wen, Zhongwu Lia,, Ninglin Luo, Mei Huang, Ren Yang	2018	10.1016/j.ecoenv. 2018.08.019	combined use of sepiolite and dehydrated sludge as a repair agent to passivate heavy metals
2	YOU Q	2018	CN108640345-A	a sewage inlet (1), protective casing (2), activated carbon fixing groove (3), detachable activated carbon filter (4) and sepiolite adsorbent (5), where outer wall of the lower end of the sewage inlet is fixedly provided with a protective casing. The side wall of the protective casing is fixedly provided with an activated carbon fixing groove, and the inner cavity of the activated carbon fixing groove is provided with a detachable activated carbon filter.
3	YAO Y, CHEN H, TIAN W, ZHANG J	2018	CN107699244-A	35-48 wt. % straws, 15-25 wt. % sewage sludge, 12-16 wt. % bentonite, 5-10 wt. % vermiculite, 6-12 wt. % maifan stone, 10-15 wt. % attapulgite clay, 8-12 wt. % sepiolite, 5-10 wt. % mica stone, 2-5 wt. % starch, 1.5-2.8 wt. % sulfate, 3-6 wt. % willow, 4-8 wt. % chayote, 2-3 wt. % Swiss cheese plant and 8-14 wt. % tea residue.
4	UNANNOUNCED I	2018	CN107699243-A	bamboo charcoal, zeolite, sepiolite, cattle manure biochar, Houttuynia cordata root powder and lime, mixed and added into lead-contaminated soil
5	CAO X	2018	CN107673457-A	5-10 wt. % nano-montmorillonite, 5-15 wt. % nano-sepiolite, 10-25 wt. % nano-serpentine, 20-35 wt. % polyaluminum chloride and 15-30 wt. % polyacrylamide.
6	CHEN J, PAN Y, SONG W	2018	CN107619665-A	30-45 wt. % diatomaceous earth, 15-18 wt. % fly ash, 10-14 wt. % wollastonite, 4-5 wt. % sepiolite, 2-3 wt. % carboxymethyl starch, 4-5 wt. % calcium magnesium phosphate, 4-5 wt. % starch phosphate monoester, 2-3 wt. % trimethylsilyl phosphate, 1.5-1.8 wt. % bornyl isovalerate, 1-1.5 wt. % potassium carbonate and 0.5-1 wt. % 4-guanidinobutyric acid.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials

No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
7	LIU X, SHI X, LIU Y, SHAO L, ZHANG Y	2018	CN107603632-A	maifanite, calcium source, sepiolite, iron powder, humic acid, calcium magnesium phosphate fertilizer and biochar. The calcium source is calcium hydroxide or oxide. The iron powder is of 10-40 um particle size. The maifanite, sepiolite and calcium source is of 150-400 mesh particle size. The calcium magnesium phosphate fertilizer, biochar and humic acid are of 1-2 mm particle size.
8	ZOU L, LIU Y	2018	CN107597840-A	the stabilizer comprises 40-60 wt. %, lime, 30-50 wt. % sepiolite and 5-10 wt. % calcium dihydrogen phosphate.
9	LI C	2018	CN107583622-A	50-100 wt. % fish powder, 30-80 wt. % sepiolite, 20-80 wt. % kaolin, 10-20 wt. % bagasse powder, 2-12 wt. % zeolite, 1-10 wt. % straw powder, and 1-8 wt. % diatomite, enzymatic fermenting, and mixing.
10	CHEN T	2017	CN107469785-A	10-20 wt. % active carbon, 8-20 wt. % cement, 5-10 wt. % sodium chloride, 5-15 wt. % lime, 6-18 wt. % sodium carbonate, 3-8 wt. % chitosan, 7-18 wt. % modified sepiolite powder, 1-5 wt. % sodium hydroxide and 1-5 wt. % hollow glass beads.
11	CHEN T	2017	CN107469786-A	10-20 wt. % activated carbon, 8-20 wt. % modified activated carbon silicon micro-powder, 5-10 wt. % sodium chloride, 5-15 wt. % lime, 6-18 wt. % n-butyl borate, 3-8 wt. % chitosan, 7-18 wt. % modified sepiolite powder, 1-5 wt. % sodium hydroxide (caustic soda) and 1-5 wt. % hollow glass beads.
12	ZENG S, SHI Y, WU K, ZHENG F	2017	CN107473847-A	2-25 wt. % abamectin, 8-19 wt. % ammonium sulfate, 4-19 wt. % sodium nitrate, 3-20 wt. % potassium phosphate, 11-20 wt. % sugarcane powder, 1-5 wt. % sepiolite, 1-4 wt. % sweet potato powder, 5-16 wt. % vulcanizing bacterial agent, 6-14 wt. % nitrogen-fixing bacterial agent, 2-13 wt. % nitrifying bacterial agent, 8-19 wt. % Alternanthera philoxeroides powder, 5-12 wt. % honeysuckle straw powder, 12-23 wt. % beet powder, 3-8 wt. % ammonium molybdate, 4-15 wt. % Firmiana simplex powder and 33-55 wt. % water.
13	LIU L, ZHANG N, LU X, FAN R	2017	CN107384433-A	30 wt. % peanut shell, 15 wt. % red pine needle, 10 wt. % sepiolite, 10 wt. % fly ash, 5 wt. % chitosan, 3 wt. % sodium metasilicate pentahydrate, 0.4 wt. % sodium tripolyphosphate, 0.1 wt. % choline chloride, 1.2 wt. % microbial inoculum and 0.05 wt. % calcium oxide.
14	SUN Z, HOU H, WEI Y, MA J, LIN X, ZHAO S	2017	CN107350281-A	1-6 wt. % clay mineral, 1-5 wt. % biochar, and 1-3 wt. % humic acid. The clay mineral is sepiolite, zeolite, serpentine, talc, attapulgite, olivine, and/or bentonite.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
15	ZHOU F, ZHANG Y, HE Y, LV H, FENG G	2017	CN107311791-A	it comprises clay mineral material 25-30 wt. % modified sepiolite, 5-8 wt. % modified attapulgite and 0.7-1.0 wt. % modified bentonite; organic material comprising 20-25 wt. % fermented organic waste, 8-12 wt. % biochar mixed material and 10-15 wt. % tea stem; precipitating agent comprising 0.8-1.0 wt. % heavy metal precipitating agent and the fertilizer 15-20 wt. % calcium magnesium phosphate fertilizer.
16	ZHU B, ZOU J, ZHANG H, SUI Y, XU H	2017	CN107282628-A	3-9 wt. %. complex microbial inoculum, 40-60 wt. % peat, 30-50 wt. % straw powder, 3-5 wt. % cake powder, 0.1-0.3 wt. % quicklime, 0.2-0.4 wt. % dipotassium hydrogen phosphate, 0.5-1.5 wt. % ammonium sulfate, 20-40 wt. % diatomite, 20-40 wt. % humic acid, 20-40 wt. % zeolite, 5-15 wt. % activated carbon, 1-3 wt. % sepiolite, and 1-3 wt. % chitosan.
17	DENG R, SHAO R, TANG Z, HOU B, REN B, JIN C	2017	CN107262037-A	(i) getting activated carbon raw material and crushing, (ii) getting sepiolite, continuously stirring, filtering, washing repeatedly and then drying, (iii) getting the sepiolite powder B, sodium alginate and water mixed sufficiently, followed with hydrothermal carbonization, (iv) mixing ethylene glycol with deionized water, and then sonicating, (v) The next steps are stirring, sonicating, mixing uniformly, washing, drying, grinding, heating, insulating and cooling slowly .
18	JIANG Q, LV S	2017	CN107267151-A	10-40 wt.% silicate cement clinker, 10-30 wt.% dolomite, 20-30 wt.% limestone, 5-15 wt.% sepiolite, 1-10 wt.% zeolite, 1-10 wt.% bentonite, 1-10 wt.% activated carbon and 3-8 wt.% iron ore.
19	CHEN B, HUANG Y, WANG P	2017	CN107090292-A	40-60 wt.% raw lime, 20-35 wt.% sepiolite, 10-25 wt.% kaolin, 1-15 wt.% calcium-magnesium phosphate and 5-25 wt.% palygorskite powder.
20	FENG Z	2017	CN107055724-A	10-15 wt.% activated carbon, 32-43 wt.% corn starch, 10-20 wt.% sepiolite, 0.1-0.5 wt.% sodium hydroxide, 0.1-0.5 wt.% amino trimethylene phosphonic acid, 1-5 wt.% polyaspartic acid, 20-50 wt.% polyaluminum chloride, 3-8 wt.% diatomite, 20-30 wt.% chitosan, 10-20 wt.% polyaspartic acid, 15-20 wt.% crosslinked rectorite, 3-6 wt.% graphene nanolayer composite, 15-20 wt.% sulfates, 10-30 wt.% zeolite, 30-50 wt.% deionized water and 10-15 wt.% polyacrylamide.
21	FANG L, WANG C, WANG J, YAN D, ZHANG Q	2017	CN106947488-A	50-70 wt.% diatomite, 20- 30 wt.% lime stone, 15-20 wt.% potassium dihydrogen phosphate, 8-20 wt.% zeolite, 4-11 wt.% plant ash, 3-7 wt.% potassium sulfate, 7-12 wt.% peat, 3 -9 wt.% weathered coal, 4-8 wt.% sepiolite, 12-20 wt.% insecticide and 15-25 wt.% herbicide.
22	WANG X, CHEN M, ZHANG J, LIU G, LI X, YU G	2017	CN106903150-A	10-385 wt.% modified sepiolite tailings, 1-80 wt.% modified zeolite, 1-5 wt.% hyposulfite, 10-20 wt.% nano iron powder and 45-60 wt.% quicklime.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
23	ZHANG Z	2017	CN106883855-A	30-40 wt.% bentonite, 180-220 wt.% attapulgite, 30-40 wt.% carbide slag, 30-40 wt.% straw, 20-30 wt.% diatomite, 10-15 wt.% phosphorus-based compound mixture, 20-30 wt.% mushroom residue, 10-15 wt.% sepiolite, 10-15 wt.% sulfur-based compound mixture, 10-15 wt.% iron powder and 2-8 wt.% shell powder.
24	CHEN W, WANG Q, CHEN Y, ZHANG J, HU H	2017	CN106800933-A	It contains component (A) and component (B). In the component (A), composition shows a mass ratio of montmorillonite: diatomite: illite: ferrous sulfate at 0.4-2.1:0.8-2.3:0.2-1.6:0.5-2.5:0.6-2.2. In the component (B), composition shows a mass ratio of contains periclase: calcite: calcium-magnesium phosphate fertilizer: plant ash: calcium hydroxide at 0.2-1.1:0.4-1.6:0.5-1.5:0.3-1.1:0.4-2.6.
25	WANG L	2017	CN106745694-A	5-10 wt.% bisphenol A type polycarbonate, 20-25 wt.% activated zeolite powder, 5-10 wt.% rosin modified straw powder, 2-4 wt.% chlorinated polyethylene rubber, 3-6 wt.% aromatic-modified terpene resin, 2-4 wt.% microcrystalline cellulose, 1-2 wt.% nano sepiolite compound powder, 1-2 wt.% crospovidone, 0.5-1 wt.% hexamethylmelamine hexaether, 0.5-1 wt.% dipentaerythritol hexaacrylate, 0.02-0.05 wt.% zirconium oxide and 0.3-0.5 wt.% disodium laureth sulfosuccinate.
26	ZHANG C	2017	CN106745447-A	40-60 wt.% granite, 10-20 wt.% peridotite, 10-20 wt.% basalt, 15-25 wt.% clay mineral, 8-16 wt.% chitosan, 11-23 wt.% activated carbon, 14-26 wt.% epoxy resin, 7-13 wt.% montmorillonite, 10-18 wt.% sepiolite, 9-15 wt.% alginic acid, 15-25 wt.% potassium alum, 6-14 wt.% gelatin, 5-10 wt.% barium sulfide, 4-8 wt.% nano titanium dioxide, 11-16 wt.% cellulose base, 6-14 wt.% hydrotalcite, 9-19 wt.% sodium hydrosulfide, 13-19 wt.% silica gel and 5-10 wt.% inorganic acid and water.
27	ZHANG H, FU Y, WANG Y, CHEN Y, DUAN N	2017	CN106753392-A	40-60 wt.% acid-modified sepiolite, 15-30 wt.% phosphate rock powder and 20-30 wt.% calcium dihydrogen phosphate.
28	ZHAO C, HAN J, ZHANG Y	2017	CN106753390-A	sepiolite, calcium magnesium phosphate and manganese(II) sulfide.
29	CHEN M	2017	CN106669617-A	12-16 wt.% sodium hexametaphosphate, 70-80 wt.% sepiolite, 8-11 wt.% sodium bicarbonate, 2-5 wt.% benzotriazole, 3-6 wt.% starch xanthate, 4-7 wt.% n-butyl titanate, 5-8 wt.% citric acid, 2-5 wt.% pentasodium diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA), and 15-18 wt.% polyferric chloride.
30	UNANNOUNCED I	2017	CN106630086-A	2-6 wt.% ferrous sulfate, 3-5 wt.% sodium silicate, 1-4 wt.% diamond powder, 12-23 wt.% modified zeolite powder, 2-4 wt.% sodium sulfate, 6-15 wt.% acrylamide, 1-5 wt.% active carbon powder, 2-11 wt.% glycerol, 10-18 wt.% straw, 3-6 wt.% starch, 2-5 wt.% sepiolite powder, 3-10 wt.% cellulose, 1-10 wt.% strong alkali and 3-14 wt.% butanol.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
31	UNANNOUNCED I	2017	CN106635039-A	23-28 pts. wt. sepiolite, 5-8 pts. wt. Stichococcus bacillaris, 5-8 pts. wt. bare dried sand and 4-7 pts. wt. modified rose; where modified rose is prepared by taking rose, superfine crushing into 5-10 μ m, adding 1.8-2.3 times N-maleamic acylated chitosan, dispersing in 2-3 times of 92-95 wt.% ethanol solution, ultrasonicing at 200-220 W at frequency of 32-34 kHz for 40-45 minutes, decompressing and concentrating, and drying for 2-3 hours at 105-110 degrees C.
32	CHEN S, FENG J, LU T	2017	CN106635031	35-55 wt.% bio-char, 10-20 wt.% sepiolite, 5-10 wt.% water-soluble solid organic acid, 5-10 wt.% calcium dihydrogen phosphate, 10-20 wt.% thiosulfate and the rest amount of natural gypsum.
33	UNANNOUNCED I	2017	CN106630085-A	10-20 pts. wt. humus soil, 2-8 pts. wt. diatomite, 5-10 pts. wt. rectorite powder, 5-8 pts. wt. natural quartz sand, 2-5 pts. wt. sepiolite powder, 4-10 pts. wt. seaweed powder, 10-20 pts. wt. glass micro-bead, 5-10 pts. wt. gamma -alumina, 5-10 pts. wt. activated clay, 5-10 pts. wt. peanut straw, 1-5 pts. wt. mulberry root, 5-10 pts. wt. chitosan, 5-10 pts. wt. lemon peel, 80-200 pts. wt. ethanol and 6-9 pts. wt. Chloris virgata.
34	HENAN SHUIJINGTOU CULTURE MEDIA CO LTD (HENA-Non-standard)	2017	CN106495309-A	10-20 pts. wt. green manure, 2-8 pts. wt. kaolin, 5-10 pts. wt. ritolite powder, 5-8 pts. wt. natural quartz sand, 2-5 pts. wt. sepiolite powder, 4-10 pts. wt. seaweed powder, 10-20 pts. wt. glass beads, 5-10 pts. wt. alpha -alumina, 5-10 pts. wt. activated clay, 5-10 pts. wt. peanut straw, 1-5 pts. wt. mulberry root, 5-10 pts. wt. chitosan, 5-10 pts. wt. lemon peel, 80-200 pts. wt. ethanol and 6-9 pts. wt. rhodes grass.
35	LIU R, ZHANG B, ZOU Y, PAN Y, YU M, DAN B	2017	CN106423112-A	70-95 pts. wt. black water-based ink printing waste liquid extract and 5-30 pts. wt. pumice and sepiolite mixture. The preparation of heavy metal ion adsorbent comprises neutralizing black water-based ink printing waste liquid extract using alkaline substance, adding pumice and sepiolite particles, heating to 50-90 degrees C, hot pressing to less than 50% moisture content, drying, insulating to 350-750 degrees C for 1-5 hours, granulating, spraying 0.05-0.2% wetting agent and mixing.
36	ZHAO T	2017	CN106431751-A	1-2 pts. wt. sodium alginate, 3-5 pts. wt. potassium chloride, 27-30 pts. wt. urea, 40-50 pts. wt. rice husk charcoal powder, 10-12 pts. wt. sepiolite, 1-2 pts. wt. microcrystalline cellulose, 50-60 pts. wt. chicken manure, 2-3 pts. wt. collagen, 30-40 pts. wt. wheat straw, 1-2 pts. wt. aluminum dihydrogen phosphate, 10-13 pts. wt. ammonium dihydrogen phosphate and 0.1-0.3 pt. wt. formamide.
37	UNANNOUNCED I	2017	CN106430509-A	10-20 pts. wt. green manure, 2-8 pts. wt. kaolin, 5-10 pts. wt. marble powder, 5-8 pts. wt. natural quartz sand, 2-5 pts. wt. sepiolite powder, 4-10 pts. wt. seaweed, 10-20 pts. wt. glass micro-beads, 5-10 pts. wt. gamma -alumina, 5-10 pts. wt. activated clay, 5-10 pts. wt. corn straw, 1-5 pts. wt. mulberry root, 5-10 pts. wt. chitosan, 5-10 pts. wt. orange peel, 80-200 pts. wt. ethanol and 6-9 pts. wt. Stellera chamaejasme.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
38	ZHANG Q	2017	CN106396069-A	32-56 pts. polyvinyl alcohol, 36-29 pts. graphene powder, 5-12 pts. modified sepiolite powder, 2-5 pts. modified chitosan, 18-24 pts. sodium tripolyphosphate, 32-36 pts. sodium aluminate, 10-14 pts. Musella lasiocarpa powder, 14-23 pts. phenolic resin and 3-9 pts. sodium lignosulfonate.
39	LIU Y, LI J, LI Q, WEI Y, HAO D, XIE Q	2017	CN106378357-A	modified sepiolite and modified chitosan
40	Unannounced I	2017	CN106379984-A	2-6pts.wt. iron trichloride, 1-4pts.wt. diamond powder, 3-5pts.wt. sodium stearate, 12-23pts.wt. alum, 6-15pts.wt. acrylamide, 1-5pts.wt. activated carbon powder, 2-4pts.wt. sodium sulfate, 10-18pts.wt. hydrated lime, 2-11pts.wt. glycerin, 3-6pts.wt. starch, 3-10pts.wt. cellulose, 2-5pts.wt. pearl powder, 3-14pts.wt. butanol and 1-10pts.wt. strong base.
41	XIA B	2017	CN106350079-A	3-5 pts. wt. organic binder, 1.5-2 pts. wt. reactive activator, 10-15 pts. wt. lime, 3-5 pts. wt. peat, 10 pts. wt. soil, 8-12 pts. wt. sepiolite, 1.3-1.8 pts. wt. calcium dihydrogenphosphate, 3-7 pts. wt. sulfoaluminate cement, 15-18 pts. wt. goethite.
42	ZHONG Y, LIU H, CAI Q, CHEN Z	2017	CN106336094-A	ferrous salt, calcium oxide, sodium hypochlorite, attapulgite, sepiolite and apatite in sludge, uniformly stirring to obtain heavy metal stabilized sludge, and placing for 2-4 days, (b) mixing 3-5 pts. wt. heavy metal stabilized sludge and 1 pts. wt. agricultural organic waste to obtain sludge mixture having carbon/nitrogen content of 27-33, pH value of 6-7.5 and moisture content of 60-70%.
43	LIU H, ZHANG G, YAN P	2017	CN106316686-A	8-12 pts. wt. hydrated lime, 30-50 pts. wt. limestone, 40-60 pts. wt. bentonite, 5-7 pts. wt. sepiolite, 5-10 pts. wt. biological carbon, 2-3 pts. wt. diethylene triamine pentaacetic acid, 2-3 pts. wt. dimercapto propane sulfonic acid, 3-5 pts. wt. lignosulfonic acid, 1-3 pts. wt. cysteine, 1-1.8 pt. wt. potassium sodium tartrate, 1-1.5 pts. wt. phosphate rock and 0-0.5 pt. wt. sodium sulfide.
44	FAN Z	2017	CN106269839-A	mixing sodium dioctyl sulfosuccinate, fatty alcohol polyethenoxy ether sodium sulfate, anionic polyacrylamide and ethyl alcohol in deionized water and stirring to obtain mixture. The mixture is added into contaminated soil, stirred, filtered the mixture to obtain filtrate, followed by adding corn stalk powder and alstonia-leaf powder into filtrate, adding sepiolite powder, disodium hydrogen phosphate and potassium dihydrogen phosphate into mixture and stirring, and determining chromium ions and other heavy metal ions in treated soil.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
45	JIN X, HU H	2017	CN106283901-A	polyaniline, hardwood pulp fiber, xanthan gum, coniferous wood pulp fiber, polyester fiber, sepiolite nanofibers, ferric oxide, titania, magnesium oxide, KH-560 (RTM: gamma -glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane) silane coupling agent, polyoxyethylene aqueous solution, titanate coupling agent DNZ201, isopropanol, styrene-acrylic emulsion and polyacrylate emulsion. The concentration of polyoxyethylene aqueous solution is 0.007-0.01%. The styrene-acrylic emulsion has solid content of 40-50%.
46	ZAN J, LI W, XU P	2017	CN106278695-A	ultrasonically treating domestic sludge, separating the treated sludge to obtain concentrated sludge and supernatant containing humic acid, adding strong base to the concentrated sludge, adding sepiolite and ferric chloride to the mixture, filtering, drying the mixture to obtain mud cake, concentrating the supernatant to obtain humic acid liquid fertilizer, adding superabsorbent polymer to mud cake and humic acid liquid fertilizer, crushing the mixture and uniformly mixing to obtain the product.
47	FAN Z	2017	CN106186496-A	(a) mixing 3-6 wt.% rice hulls, 1-3 wt.% sepiolite, 1-2 wt.% diatomaceous earth, 1-3 wt.% activated zeolite and the wastewater to be treated, stirring at 100-200 revolutions/minutes for 30-40 minutes, filtering and removing the residues, (b) adding 2-5 wt.% beta -diketone chelate resin and 1-2 wt.% salicylic acid-thiourea chelate resin and ultrasonically oscillating the mixture in a ultrasonic oscillator at 300-400 W for 20-40 minutes, (c) adding 3-6 wt.% tea polyphenol to the waste water, stirring at 120-150 revolutions/minute for 20-30 minutes, filtering and removing the residues, (d) adding 1-3 wt.% oyster shell powder, 2-4 wt.% chitin and 1-2 wt.% radix isatidis powder to the wastewater, heating by stirring at 40-60 degrees C for 20-40 minutes, filtering and removing the residues

Composition of sepiolite and other materials

No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
48	LEI C, XUE L, WANG T	2017	CN106147781-A	<p>weighing 120-150 g sepiolite, crushing, sieving to obtain 20-30 mesh sepiolite particles, soaking the sepiolite particles in 25 %mass hydrochloric acid in a solid-liquid ratio of 1:5 at room temperature for 5-7 hours, filtering to obtain a filter residue, washing the filter residues with deionized water until the washing liquid is neutral, drying the washed filter residues into a drying oven at a temperature of 80-95 degrees C for 6-8 hours to obtain acid modified sepiolite, weighing 150-200 g fresh banana peel, cleaning the surface of the banana peel, vacuum drying the banana peel into a vacuum drying box at 70-80 degrees C for 10-12 hours, crushing the dried banana peel to obtain 30-40 mesh banana peel particles, soaking the banana peel particles in 3 %mass sodium hydroxide solution in a solid-liquid ratio of 1:5 for 50-60 minutes, carrying out suction filtration to obtain a filter residue, washing the filter residue with deionized water until the washing liquid is neutral, drying the filter residue in a drying oven at a temperature of 95-105 degrees C for 6-8 hours, putting the dried banana peel particles into a muffle furnace, calcining at 480-520 degrees C for 60-90 minutes, cooling to room temperature, crushing and sieving to obtain 50-60-mesh banana peel activated carbon powder, weighing 50-55 pts. wt. acid modified sepiolite, 20-25 pts. wt. banana peel activated carbon powder, 5-15 pts. wt. red mud, 15-20 pts. wt. hydroxyapatite, 1-3 pts. wt. aluminum oxide powder and 5-7 pts. wt. cow dung, stirring and uniformly mixing to obtain a mixture, adding 60-65 pts. wt. mixture, 12-20 pts. wt. 60-80-mesh perlite powder, 5-10 pts. wt. sodium carbonate, 2-4 pts. wt. zeolite, 8-10 pts. wt. sodium alginate, 3-5 pts. wt. sodium methylsiliconate, 2-4 pts. wt. hydroxybenzenesulfonic acid and 0.1-0.3 pt. wt. sodium dodecylbenzenesulfonate into a dispersing kettle, and mixing at a speed of 100-150 rpm for 1-2 hours to obtain the soil curing agent.</p>

Composition of sepiolite and other materials

No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
49	ZHANG J, LIU P	2016	CN106076276-B	involves dispersing 15-30 pts. wt. kaolin and 20-40 pts. wt. sepiolite in 100-180 pts. wt. solvent, ultrasonically vibrating at room temperature for 1-2 hours, dripping 6-12 pts. wt. quaternary ammonium tetrameric surfactant and 4-8 pts. wt. cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, carrying out modification reaction in a water bath, reacting for 75-85 degrees C for 4-8 hours, modifying, washing, drying, crushing to obtain modified composite powder, adding obtained modified composite powder to 10-15 pts. wt. polyvinyl alcohol and 6-12 pts. wt. chitosan, mixing, stirring, adding mixture to boric acid solution for immobilization and crosslinking, washing the cured product, drying to obtain composite crosslinking adsorbent, adding obtained composite cross-linked adsorbent to 30-40 pts. wt. mixed iron salt solution, and reacting at 40 degrees C for 20-30 minutes under nitrogen protection.
50	HE Q, ZHOU Y, ZHU Y, LIU D, LI X, CHANG H	2016	CN106010562-B	1-4 pts. wt. iron powder, 4-6 pts. wt. chitosan, 4 pts. wt. chicken manure, 4-6 pts. wt. sepiolite and 2-5 pts. wt. lime.
51	ZHAO Z	2016	CN106010573-A	10 wt.% lime, 10 wt.% calcium carbonate, 4 wt.% fly ash, 1.5 wt.% hydroxyapatite, 2 wt.% phosphate rock powder, 8 wt.% dicalcium phosphate, 7 wt.% potassium dihydrogen phosphate, 4 wt.% polyacrylamide, 6 wt.% polyvinyl alcohol resin, 1 wt.% polyacrylonitrile, 1.5 wt.% polypropylene alcohol, 3 wt.% zeolite, 4 wt.% bentonite, 3 wt.% sepiolite, 5 wt.% humic acid, 7 wt.% peat, 6 wt.% polysaccharide, 8 wt.% asphalt emulsion, 5 wt.% peat, 2 wt.% avermectin and 1 wt.% Bacillus polymyxa.
52	TAN J	2016	CN105985165-A	10-40 pts. wt. biological carbon, 10-30 pts. wt. sepiolite, 10-20 pts. wt. black tea, 5-30 pts. wt. lime, and 10-20 pts. wt. common nutwood.
53	OUYANG X, LIU C, JIN R, YANG L, WANG N	2016	CN105964009-B	adjusting the concentration of heavy metal chromium in solution to 180-260 mg/L, adjusting the pH to 2.5-4, adding mixture of polyethyleneimine-modified carboxylated nanocrystalline cellulose and sepiolite in mass ratio of 1:10-20, reacting for 4-10 hours at 15-23 degrees C, centrifuging, and separating supernatant solution.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
54	GUO F	2016	CN105944698-A	(i) crushing medical stone granules, heating and cooling to obtain active medical stone powder, taking 5-30 pts. wt. active medical stone powder and 20-40 pts. wt. sepiolite, dispersing in 100-180 pts. wt. solvent and ultrasonically vibrating at room temperature for 1-2 hours, dripping 6-12 pts. wt. quaternary ammonium salt tetrameric surfactant and 4-8 pts. wt. sodium dodecyl sulfate and carrying out a modification reaction at 75-85 degrees C for 4-8 hours, then washing, drying and crushing to obtain modified composite powder, (ii) adding the modified composite powder to 10-15 pts. wt. polyvinyl alcohol and 6-12 pts. wt. chitosan, mixing, then adding the mixture to boric acid solution for immobilization and crosslinking, washing and drying the cured product to obtain a composite cross-linked adsorbent, and (iii) adding obtained composite crosslinked adsorbent to 30-40 pts. wt. mixed iron salt solution, stirring under nitrogen protection and carrying out reaction at 50 degrees C for 20-30 minutes to obtain the industrial wastewater heavy metal ion adsorbent.
55	FU J, JIANG L, LIN H, MA J, WANG Q, YE J, ZOU P, SUN W, YU Q	2016	CN105906404-B	30-50 wt.% brown algae biological coal, 40-60 wt.% attapulgite, and balance amount of sepiolite.
56	ZHANG Y	2016	CN105859331-A	selecting high-quality montmorillonite and sepiolite minerals, air-drying selected minerals, grinding minerals using vertical roller mill, sieving minerals through 800-1200 mesh sieve, and high-temperature drying minerals at 150-180 degrees C, after naturally cooling, adding 10 wt.% humic acid, 3 wt.% Bacillus subtilis and 10 wt.% rare earth micro-fertilizer and uniformly mixing mixture, and packing mixture into plastic bag and sealing using sealing machine.
57	SONG T	2016	CN105778924-A	providing sepiolite and palygorskite mixture according to ratio of 1:1, dispersing in 80-100 degrees C hot water, high speed stirring at 10000 rotations/minute for 5-10 minutes, forming suspension, then adding modified material of mercapto and amino modified material with mass of 1/3 to 1/4 to make up the mixture, continuing to stir for 10-20 minutes, then using dispersion machine at speed of 2000-5000 rotations/minute, slowly adding potassium dihydro phosphate and urea formaldehyde, after dissolution, stop stirring, mixing and granulating, and drying to prepare the finished product.
58	FAN Z, WANG X, YANG X	2016	CN105731964-B	30-36 pts. wt. gypsum, 24-30 pts. wt. salt, 21-25 pts. wt. alumina, 27-29 pts. wt. plant ash, 19 to 21 pts. wt. sodium carboxymethylcellulose, 9-13 pts. wt. silica, 8-10 pts. wt. ferrous sulfate, 7-9 pts. wt. ligninsulfonate, 23-25 pts. wt. sepiolite powder, 5 to 7 pts. wt. triethanolamine, 21 to 23 pts. wt. calcined soda
59	ZHANG R	2016	CN105731580-A	11-23 pts. wt. activated carbon, 8-16 pts. wt. chitosan, 14-26 pts. wt. epoxy resin, 10-18 pts. wt. sepiolite, 7-13 pts. wt. montmorillonite, 9-15 pts. wt. alginic acid, 6-14 pts. wt. gelatin, 15-25 pts. wt. alum, 5-10 pts. wt. barium sulfate, 8-14 pts. wt. calcium carbonate, 11-16 pts. wt. cellulose base, 4-8 pts. wt. nano titanium dioxide, 6-14 pts. wt. hydrotalcite, 13-19 pts. wt. silica gel and 9-19 pts. wt. sodium hydrosulfide.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
60	DAI X	2016	CN105692771-A	10-20 pts. wt. hydrochloric acid modified sepiolite, 15-25 pts. wt. pyridine quat. ammonium salt cationic polyacrylamide, 5-8 pts. wt. zeolite powder, 3-10 pts. wt. modified attapulgite, 10-15 pts. wt. cellulose xanthate, 2-8 pts. wt. chitosan, 10-25 pts. wt. crosslinked sodium carboxymethyl starch, 5-10 pts. wt. hydroxypropyl cellulose grafted copolymer (preferably hydroxypropyl cellulose grafted 4-vinyl pyridine copolymer), 2-8 pts. wt. ferric sulfate, 1-5 pts. wt. lime powder, and 3-8 pts. wt. active coal powder.
61	WANG Q	2016	CN105693418-A	700-1100 pts. wt. peat, 70-90 pts. wt. rapeseed cake, 0.7-8 pts. wt. microbial inoculant and 180-220 pts. wt. sepiolite.
62	HAO F, LIU P, LUO H, XIONG S, XIONG W, ZHANG W	2016	CN105617981-B	series of different concentration of lead, cadmium, cupric and chromium ion solution, and simultaneously preparing solution containing different concentration of phenol used as working liquid respectively, adding modified sepiolite into working liquid in a mass volume ratio of 1:1-2 g/l, absorbing for 2-8 hours.
63	GE H, LI C, LIU Z, SONG F, WANG Y, ZHAO Z	2016	CN105602568-A	premix powder and on-site mixed liquid composition. The mass ratio of the on-site mixed liquid composition to the premix powder is 3:7-4:6. The premix powder comprises 15-40 mass% biomass activated carbon powder, 10-40 mass% modified sepiolite powder, 10-45 mass% bentonite powder, 10-25 mass% rice hull powder. The on-site mixed liquid composition comprises 10-20 mass% aqueous solution of ammonium bicarbonate.
64	BAO T	2016	CN105565423-A	10-18 pts. wt. Pinaceae plant waste, 9-27 pts. wt. calcium hydroxide, 3-9 pts. wt. aluminum hydroxide, 5-12 pts. wt. sepiolite, 8-11 pts. wt. alginic acid, 4-8 pts. wt. sodium lignin sulfonate, and 20-35 pts. wt. water.
65	PAN H	2016	CN105540809-A	2-8 pts. wt. 1-terpene-8-ol acetate, 6-10 pts. wt. polyethylene glycol, 0.6-1.2 pts. wt. polyoxyethylene glyceryl ether, 6-12 pts. wt. 2-amino-butane, 4-8 pts. wt. 4-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-2-butanone, 8-14 pts. wt. carboxymethylcellulose, 2-3.5 pts. wt. salicin, 10-15 pts. wt. polyoxypropylene diol, 8-16 pts. wt. polyoxyethylene diamine, 0.5-0.9 pts. wt. polyoxyethylene styryl phenyl ether, 7-11 pts. wt. dimerized fatty acid, 4-10 pts. wt. 10-hydroxy-2-decanoic acid and 10-20 pts. wt. sepiolite.
66	CHEN Q; YE R; CHEN K.	2016	CN105504760-B	30-50 pts. wt. methacrylate, 20-30 pts. wt. polyethylene glycol, 10-15 pts. wt. sepiolite, 5.0-7.0 pts. wt. polyvinyl alcohol, 3.0-5.0 pts. wt. humic acid, 0.4-0.6 pt. wt. ammonium sulfate, 0.05-0.10 pt. wt. aluminum sulfate and 0.05-0.10 pt. wt. N,N'-methylene bisacrylamide. The heavy metal-containing wastewater treatment hydrogel material is prepared by taking 10-15 pts. wt. sepiolite and 3.0-5.0 pts. wt. humic acid, adding water, ultrasonic dispersing, forming suspension, adding remaining raw materials, ultrasonic dispersing at 75 degrees C at rate of 400-600 revolutions/minute for 100-120 minutes, filtering, washing with ethanol, and tableting.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
67	CHENG G; ZHONG Y.	2016	CN105419814-A	20-30 pts. dimercaprol, 9-16 pts. cobalt ferrite, 7-15 pts. bismuth phosphate, 2-5 pts. tungsten oxide, 5-14 pts. hexahydroxy sodium antimonate, 3-10 pts. sepiolite, 4-12 pts. oxysophocarpine, 3-9 pts. calcium chloride, 5-10 pts. potassium citrate, 2-7 pts. 1,3-diketone, 6-13 pts. palmitic acid, 5-17 pts. diatomaceous earth and 8-15 pts. glucono- delta -lactone.
68	LI W, WANG L, ZHAO X	2016	CN105273721-A	mixing powder raw materials i.e. 3-15 mass% lime, 8-60 mass% limestone, 3-35 mass% sepiolite, 3-25 mass% vermiculite and 1-20 mass% attapulgite.
69	BAO C, WANG Y	2016	CN105198549-A	15-25 pts. wt. complex microbial inoculants, 9-13 pts. wt. urea, 16-20 pts. wt. monoammonium phosphate, 20-25 pts. wt. potassium sulfate, 10-20 pts. wt. sepiolite, 10-20 pts. wt. activated carbon, 2-5 pts. wt. borax, 2-5 pts. wt. zinc sulfate, and 3-5 pts. wt. magnesium sulfate.
70	LEI X, LEI Z	2016	CN105199737-A	40-60 wt.% calcium oxide, 20-30 wt.% silicon dioxide, 3-10 wt.% magnesium oxide, alumina, and 10-30 wt.% iron oxide mineral-based non-functional element, where the heavy metals content include less than or equal to 5 ppm mercury, 10 ppm less than or equal to cadmium, less than or equal to 10 ppm arsenic, less than or equal to 50 ppm lead, and less than or equal to 50 ppm chromium.
71	CHEN S, JIN J, LIU B, NI X, ZHEN S, LV Z	2016	CN105174686-A	30-50 wt.% Portland cement, 10-30 wt.% fly ash, 10-30 wt.% calcium oxide, 10-25 wt.% raw bentonite and sepiolite and 2-5 wt.% calcium chloride.
72	ZHANG Y, ZHANG B	2016	CN105148858-A	60-80 pts. wt. watermelon peel, 10-15 pts. wt. rice hull, 5-10 pts. wt. sepiolite powder, 5-10 pts. wt. attapulgite, 3-5 pts. wt. calcium chloride, 0.5-1 pt. wt. tannic acid, 3-5 pts. wt. polyethylene glycol, 3-5 pts. wt. sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, 0.1-0.2 pt. wt. polyoxyethylene nonylphenyl ether, 4-6 pts. wt. auxiliary agent, and 40-60 pts. wt. water.
73	ZHANG Y, ZHANG B	2015	CN105152259-A	20-30 pts. wt. durian shell, 5-10 pts. wt. dolomite powder, 3-5 pts. wt. sepiolite fiber, 3-5 pts. wt. light calcium carbonate, 1-2 pts. wt. high aluminum powder, 1-2 pts. wt. white alum, 0.1-0.2 pt. wt. sodium benzoate, 0.5-1 pt. wt. sodium chloride, 0.5-1 pt. wt. sodium alginate, 1-2 pts. wt. sodium polyacrylate and 10-15 pts. wt. bonding additive. The bonding additive comprises 10-15 pts. wt. glutinous rice flour, 0.5-1 pt. wt. agar powder, 1-2 pts. wt. xanthan gum, 1-2 pts. wt. carrageenan, 1-2 pts. wt. water-soluble lanolin, 1-2 pts. wt. maltodextrin, 2-4 pts. wt. polyethylene glycol, 2-4 pts. wt. sucrose

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
74	DENG Y	2015	CN105084485-A	1-9 pts. wt. sodium humate, 1-5 pts. wt. sepiolite, 5-10 pts. wt. polyaluminum chloride, 1-5 pts. wt. polyaluminum sulfate, 3-9 pts. wt. magnesium sulfate, 5-10 pts. wt. polyoxyethylene, 2-8 pts. wt. dimethylamine, 3-9 pts. wt. alginic acid, 3-9 pts. wt. barium carbonate, 5-20 pts. wt. fly ash and 70-100 pts. wt. water.
75	BAO L, LI Y, SUN M, ZHANG Y, ZHONG Z, JING Y	2015	CN105061114-B	20-40 wt.% activated weathered coal, 15-25 wt.% biochar, 10-25 wt.% sepiolite, 10-20 wt.% calcium magnesium phosphate fertilizer, and 10-20 wt.% diammonium phosphate. The activated weathered coal is prepared by taking weathered coal and ammonium bicarbonate at mass ratio of 1:1-5, mixing, activating at 50-70 degrees C for 1-2 days, and ultrasonically activating at 100-300 W for 10-30 minutes.
76	CHENG Y	2015	CN105001493-A	40-50 pts. wt. low-density polyethylene, 6-8 pts. wt. crosslinked starch, 8-12 pts. wt. nano sepiolite, 0.01-0.02 pt. wt. ethylenediamine trisodium disuccinate, 10-12 pts. wt. silica sol with a solids content of 20-25%, 4-5 pts. wt. ethylene-acrylic acid copolymer, 1-1.5 pt. wt. hydroxymethyl chitosan, 0.1-0.2 pt. wt. alkyl glycoside, 0.1-0.2 pt. wt. silane coupling agent, 25-35 pts. wt. water.
77	YU L.	2015	CN105000621-A	100 mass parts magnetic sepiolite powder and 150-180 mass parts polyacrylamide. The magnetic sepiolite powder is prepared by crushing sepiolite ore, mixing sepiolite powder and deionized water, aging for 1.5 hour, removing supernatant and lower layer of sand, centrifuging resultant sepiolite suspension, drying, acid-modifying obtained sepiolite, adding acid-modified sepiolite to ferric ion solution, stirring, adding aqueous ammonia solution, aging, washing, drying, heat-t
78	GAO X	2015	CN104973674-B	(i) adding 35 pts. distilled water into a cylinder, adding 8 pts. beta -cyclodextrin, placing in a centrifuge, centrifuging at 1000-3000 revolutions per minute for 5 minutes, and adding 50 pts. distilled water to obtain beta -cyclodextrin solution; (ii) adding 9 pts. polyacrylamide and 3 pts. carrageenan into 20 ml distilled water, carrying out chelation reaction at 90 degrees C, cooling to room temperature in water bath, adding 50 pts. beta -cyclodextrin solution, and mixing by ultrasonic vibration; (iii) milling 8 pts. sodium humate and 70 pts. sepiolite, passing via 80 mesh sieve, and adding into the mixed solution, to obtain semisolid get blank; and (iv) balling to a diameter of 6-10 mm, for 12 minutes, calcining at 300 degrees C for 30 minutes.
79	ZHOU L, YUAN H()	2016	CN104877688-B	processing the raw material quicklime, zeolite, sepiolite and calcium magnesium phosphatic fertilizer according to proportion uniformly mixing to obtain the product.
80	LI J, JIANG Y, MA Z, LIAN X, MENG F, YANG Y, XI B, XU X, LI M()	2015	CN104874350-B ; US9795942-B2	manganese ore, sepiolite, straw, animal feces, activated sludge, adding active agents, composting the mixture in a compost reactor, turning the material regularly by spraying water and protecting under excellent environment, carbonizing the compost product into a retort at 370-400 degrees C, and cooling the carbonized product, and crushing the carbonized product into granulated particles to an average particle diameter of 1-3 cm.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
81	YUAN H, ZHOU L	2015	CN104861983-B	40-60 wt.% limestone, 5-25 wt.% bentonite, 10-25 wt.% zeolite and 5-20 wt.% sepiolite.
82	YANG S, ZHAO W, SUN J, WEI S, ZHANG D	2015	CN104829397-A	40-50 pts. wt. wheat bran, 70-90 pts. wt. corn flour, 6-9 pts. wt. sepiolite, 3-4 pts. wt. dandelion, 26-30 pts. wt. yeast culture, 8-10 pts. wt. brown sugar, 2-3 pts. wt. zinc sulfate, 4-5 pts. wt. sodium dihydrogen phosphate, 8-10 pts. wt. plant ash, 6-8 pts. wt. urea, 2-4 pts. wt. magnesium vitriol, 2-4 pts. wt. silicate, 4-7 pts. wt. silicon-doped hydroxyapatite and 5-7 pts. wt. auxiliary agent.
83	CAO Y, HANG X, LIANG L, MA G, SHEN P	2015	CN104726104-B	crushing and rolling attapulgite, vermiculite, sepiolite, zeolite, and diatomite through screens respectively to form small particulate mineral mixture. The formed mineral mixture is mixed in water uniformly to get flaky mineral composition. The obtained mineral composition is applied on a sheet stack, and then naturally dried for 48 hours or more to set a moisture content of less than 20 wt.%.
84	DONG Z, LI Y, WU L, ZHAO J, HU P	2015	CN104668281-B	grinding heavy metal contaminated soil to 2-5 mm sieve and filling into the soil column, where the soil thickness is 10-20 cm and bulk density of 1-1.2 gcm ⁻¹ . Ferric chloride solution is poured on top of the soil and an eluent is added to remove most of the cadmium activity soil. Deionized water is poured on top of the soil to remove residual soil cadmium and eluent. The soil is leached, dried and ground, and 0.05-0.2 wt.% quicklime, 0.5-2 wt.% sepiolite, 0.2-1 wt.% commercial organic fertilizer, and 0.02-0.12 wt.% nutrient of nitrogen, phosphorus pentoxide and potassium oxide are added to the obtained soil and harvested to complete the repair.
85	GUO Y, LIANG S, WU Z	2015	CN104587852-B	0-25 wt.% polysulfone, 1-20 wt.% additive, 60-80 wt.% solvent and 1-20 wt.% porogen. The additive is ion-exchange resin, chitosan, sepiolite, mesoporous silica, molecular sieve, attapulgite or bentonite. The solvent is N-methylpyrrolidone, N,N-dimethylformamide, N,N-dimethylacetamide or dimethyl sulfoxide.
86	HE Q, XIE P, YANG X, ZHAN S	2015	CN104531159-B	5-20 pts. wt. trimercaptotriazine, 10-30 pts. wt. phosphate, 15-30 pts. wt. carbonate, 45-60 pts. wt. sepiolite, and 2-5 pts. wt. binder.
87	SUN C	2015	CN104445556-A	50-70 wt.% 1st component and 30-50 wt.% 2nd component in which 1st component comprises 30-50 pts. wt. polyacrylamide, 10-20 pts. wt. polymeric ferric chloride, 15-25 pts. wt. soy protein, 10-15 pts. wt. EDTA, 25-35 pts. wt. sodium humate, 30-50 pts. wt. zeolite particles, 35-45 pts. wt. maifanite particles, 20-35 pts. wt. sepiolite particles, and 30-45 pts. wt. activated carbon and 2nd component comprises 2-5 pts. wt. sodium silicate, 1-4 pts. wt. sodium sulfide, and 3-6 pts. wt. hydrogen peroxide.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
88	WANG L, XU J	2015	CN104437425-A	8-17 pts. wt. sepiolite powder, 5-9 pts. wt. sodium hydroxide, 4-11 pts. wt. aluminum chloride, 9-15 pts. wt. natural zeolite, 2-8 pts. wt. natural fiber, 5-10 pts. wt. ethylenically unsaturated polydimethylsiloxane, 4-9 pts. wt. soybean protein, 4-8 pts. wt. bentonite, 2-6 pts. wt. ferric oxide, 5-9 pts. wt. polyvinyl ester, 3-8 pts. wt. lime and 1-5 pts. wt. cellulose.
89	HUANG Q, YANG B, CHEN R	2015	CN104338742-A	20-30 pts. wt. citric acid, 20-25 pts. wt. EM-type penetrating agent, 10-15 pts. wt. sepiolite, 20-30 pts. wt. lime, 12-26 pts. wt. flocculating agent and 120000-360000 water.
90	GUO H, HAN D, NIE C, MA W, YAN Y	2015	CN104289185-B	adsorbent, additive and binder in pts. wt. ratio of 80-120:7-14:0.5-3; where the adsorbent includes fly ash and zeolite powder or sepiolite in pts. wt. ratio of 50-70:30-50; the additive includes magnesium aluminate hydrotalcite, biochar and magnesium lignin sulfonate in pts. wt. ratio of 5-7:2-6:0.5-1; and the binder is bentonite.
91	WANG X, CHEN Z	2015	CN104293353-A	30-40 pts. wt. sepiolite-based mineral, 10-20 pts. wt. organic plant fertilizer additive and 30-40 pts. wt. seaweed.
92	SUN Y, XU X, CAO Z, LIU Z, XU L, YAO D, ZHENG P, HUANG S, NIU H	2015	CN104230589-A	soil conditioner comprises 110-120 pts. wt. sepiolite powder, 3-4 pts. wt. alcohol ester 12, 4-5 pts. wt. nano-jade powder, 3-4 pts. wt. soapstock, 2-3 pts. wt. ascorbic acid, 3-4 pts. wt. magnesium sulfate, 1-2 pts. wt. lentinan, 3-4 pts. wt. phenyltrimethoxysilane, 3-4 pts. wt. manganese carbonate, 5-6 pts. wt. ferrous sulfate and water (suitable quantity).
93	WANG X	2015	CN104230130-A	adding ferrous salt, calcium oxide, sodium hypochlorite, attapulgite, sepiolite, and apatite in sludge.
94	CHEN Z, LIN Q, LIU J, LAI S, ZHONG S	2014	CN103865543-B	10-50 wt.% diatomite, 10-50 wt.% sepiolite, 4-20 wt.% phosphate rock powder, and bentonite in which amount is total of 3 components.
95	MENG G, TAN Z, WANG R, DI H, GUO Y	2014	CN103772034-B	mixing sepiolite powder and tobacco stems bio-organic fertilizer at mass ratio of 1:(8-10); uniformly stirring; and applying soil improver at 70-100 kg/acre of acidic and cadmium contaminated soil, in which soil improver is used as base fertilizer with potash fertilizer as top dressing.
96	Xi, Yonghui; Wu, Xiaofeng; Xiong, Hao	2014	10.1080/15320383.2014.890168	including cement, lime, montmorillonite, diatomite, sepiolite, and fly ash and their various proportions, were employed to stabilize/solidify artificially prepared Pb-contaminated soils.
97	Guney, Yucel; Cetin, Bora; Aydilek, Ahmet H.; et al.	2014	10.1016/j.wasma n.2013.10.008	The utilization of sepiolite-zeolite materials as a bottom liner material allowed for thinner liners with some reduction in construction costs compared to use of a kaolinite-rich day.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
98	BAEK S	2014	CN103468268-A	selecting high quality montmorillonite and sepiolite group minerals
99	CHEN D	2014	CN103381322-B	15-18 pts. wt. active carbon, 10-12 pts. wt. high density polyethylene, 9-11 pts. wt. propylene glycol, 4-6 pts. wt. polyvinylpyrrolidone, 1-2 pts. wt. sodium selenite, 1-2 pts. wt. silver nitrate, 1-2 pts. wt. zinc sulfate, 8-10 pts. wt. clay, 3-5 pts. wt. silane coupling agent KH550, 8-10 pts. wt. sepiolite powder, 12-14 pts. wt. isotactic polypropylene and 25-35 pts. wt. modified bentonite.
100	XU Y, LIANG X, WANG L, LIN D, QIN X, SUN Y	2014	CN103238440-B	sepiolite and montmorillonite clay minerals and organic fertilizers
101	GUO Y	2013	CN103044140-B	10-40 pts. wt. humic acid, peat, biochemical fulvic acid or sodium fulvate, 0-20 pts. wt. non-metallic nano-mineral material, 0-20 pts. wt. chitin or chitosan, and 0-10 pts. wt. seaweed extract, where plant ash is 0.7-2.5 times of raw material total amount. The non-metallic nano-mineral material is powdered zeolite, sepiolite, bentonite, vermiculite, kaolin, concave-convex rod mineral soil, perlite, protein shale, and/or rectorite ore soil.
102	ZHANG Q; CHEN J; HONG X.	2013	CN102886245-B	Sepiolite is dispersed in water, to obtain sepiolite solution. 0.5 mol/L Hydrochloric acid and aniline monomer are added to sepiolite solution, stirred and mixed for 30 minutes, to obtain aniline monomer solution. An ammonium persulfate solution and hydrochloric acid solution are is dripped slowly to aniline monomer solution for 30 minutes, reacted for 12-24 hours, reaction product is collected, filtered, washed, dried and ground, to obtain polyaniline/sepiolite nanocomposite fiber.
103	Wang, L., Xu, Y., Liang, X., Sun, G., Sun, Y. and Lin, D.	2012	Remediation of Contaminated Paddy Soil by Immobilization of Pollutants in the Diaojiang Catchment, Guangxi Province	sepiolite, lime and phosphate
104	XIAO X, GUO C	2012	CN102513341-B	modifying agent comprises calcium-magnesium phosphates fertilizer, sepiolite, bentonite, red mud, phosphogypsum, phosphate, ethylenediamine tetraacetate (EDTA) and/or citric acid

Composition of sepiolite and other materials

No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
105	LIANG X, QIN X, SUN Y, WANG L, XU Y	2012	CN102274717-B	dispersing natural clay sea bubble stone in deionized water to obtain sepiolite suspension, subjecting suspension to a high speed dispersion machine controlled at 12000-13500 revolutions/minute for 5 minutes to form sepiolite gel, adding mercaptopropyl trimethoxy silane while stirring, stirring further for 20 minutes to form hydrosulfonyl modified sepiolite gel system, drying gel at 80 degrees C for 245 hours, cooling to 65 degrees C, and grinding.
106	ZHOU B, LEI M, CAO X, SHENG L, HUANG D, LUO Z, ZHU Q, LIU S, ZHU C, RAO Z, CHEN Y	2012	CN102180750-B	urea (4.5-11.5), ammonium chloride (2-5.5), ammonium sulfate (2-8), ammonium nitrate (7.5-16), diammonium phosphate (7.5-11.5), phosphoric acid-potash fertilizer (3-15), calcium magnesium phosphate fertilizer (7.5-12.5), potassium chloride (6.5-10), zinc sulfate (0.7-1.5), agricultural rare earth nitrate (0.8-1.5), sepiolite (25-32.5), kaolin (2.1-2.4), bentonite (0.5-0.7) and power plant residue (1.9-2.3).
107	ZHOU B, LEI M, CAO X, HUANG D, LUO Z, ZHU Q, LIU S, ZHU C, RAO Z, CHEN Y	2012	CN102180734-B	urea (4-12.5), ammonium chloride (0.5-14.5), ammonium sulfate (0.5-13.5), diammonium phosphate (8-14.5), phosphorus-potassium nitrate fertilizer (6-19), calcium magnesium phosphate (2.5-12), potassium chloride (7-14.5), zinc sulfate (0.5-1.5), sepiolite (20-32.5), iron-manganese oxide (6.5-10.5), kaolin (2.1-2.4), bentonite (0.5-1.1) and power plant residue (1.5-2.3).
108	ZHOU B, LEI M, CAO X, HUANG D, LUO Z, ZHU Q, LIU S, ZHU C, RAO Z, CHEN Y	2012	CN102180749-B	urea (5.5-12.5), ammonia chloride (2-13), ammonium nitrate (6.0-10.5), diammonium phosphate (13.5-20.5), potassium phosphorus nitrate fertilizer (4.5-11), calcium-magnesium phosphorus fertilizer (2-9.5), potassium chloride (9.5-13.5), sepiolite (25.0-32.5), kaolin (2.1-2.4), bentonite (0.5-0.7) and furnace clinker of electric power plant (1.9-2.3).
109	ZHOU B, LEI M, CAO X, SUN N, HUANG D, LUO Z, ZHU Q, LIU S, ZHU C, RAO Z	2012	CN102174325-B	power plant slag (33-54), sepiolite mineral powder (25-39), and calcined lime (21-28). The power plant slag is waste obtained by completely burning coal of thermal power plant and comprises (%) silicon oxide (60-70); and magnesium oxide, calcium oxide, manganese oxide, and iron oxide (15-20).
110	ZHOU B, LEI M, CAO X, SUN N, HUANG D, LUO Z, ZHU Q, LIU S, ZHU C, RAO Z	2012	CN102174326-B	sepiolite mineral powder (75-90), ferrimanganic oxide (1-24), and quick lime (1-9). The sepiolite mineral powder is obtained by grinding and screening original mineral to obtained water-contained magnesium silicate mineral with large specific surface area. It has silicon dioxide and magnesium oxide content of 54-60% and 21-25%, respectively. The ferrimanganic oxide is obtained by grinding and screening 69% clean red mud and 31% ferribraunite, such that total weight of iron oxide and manganese dioxide is 40-55%.
111	ROMERA LORCA P	2010	WO2010139813-A1	natural-fibrous silicates including bentonite clay, sepiolite, attapulgite, zeolites or calcareous algae or diatoms, or carbonates of alkali metals or alkaline earth metal or its mixture; and graphite.

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
112	Lu, Xiao-Ming; Lu, Peng-Zhen; Chen, Jian-Jun	2015	10.1007/s11356-015-4680-7	combinations of passivators (sepiolite, phosphate rock, and coal fly ash) on the concentration and speciation of Cu in swine manure aerobic compost along with soil to which the compost had been applied.
113	Xu Ming-gang ; Zhang Qing; Zeng Xi-bai	2007		lime, manure, and sepiolite
114	Andrade, L. ; Covelo, E.F.; Vega, F.A.	2005	10.4067/S0718-07642005000100002	sepiolite: montmorillonite (76%); magnesian bentonite: vermiculite (74,4%), aluminic bentonite: smectite (69.1 %) and palygorskite (80%).
115	Murathan, AS	2004		Diatomite, pumice stone and brownish sepiolite were used as adsorbents.
116	SAWYER E W	1977		(a) adding attapulgite or sepiolite colloidal clay particles to the water to absorb the cations, (b) dispersing the particles in the water to form acicular-type needles for electrical attraction of the cations and (c) sep. the needles from the water.
117	Wu Y. et al. 2016	2016		mixture of limestone and sepiolite
118	Sun Y. et al. 2016	2016		sepiolite, bentonite, and phosphate amendments
119	Zhou H. et al. 2014a	2014		Two combined amendments (LS, limestone + sepiolite; HZ, hydroxyhistidine + zeolite) were applied at ratios of 0.2%, 0.4%, and 0.8% (w/w) to paddy soil with multi-metal (Pb, Cd, Cu, and Zn) contamination.
120	Zhou H. et al. 2014b	2014		Two combined amendments (LS, limestone + sepiolite; HZ, hydroxyhistidine + zeolite)
121	Zeng H. et al. 2014	2014		curing agent (limestone plus sepiolite)
122	Xie X. et al. 2018	2018		passivation additives (including humic acid and/or sepiolite) for heavy metal in different amount
123	Deng C. et al. 2018	2018		combination of sepiolite and dehydrated sludge
124	Xie Y. et al. 2018	2018		Many new compositions of six amendments which might include bentonite, phosphate, humic acid, biochar and sepiolite powder

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
125	Cao X. et al. 2018	2018		persistence of natural sepiolite bearing material (NSBM) that contains 15% sepiolite and ground limestone which is equivalent to >98.0% CaO was made for remediation in Cd-contaminated acid soil
126	Shi J. 2018a	2018	CN 108275746 A	40-50 wt. % tetrathioicarbamic acid, 15-20 wt. % dithiocarbamate, 10-15 wt. % starch, 8-10 wt. % polyacrylamide, 6-8 wt. % butyl sodium xanthate, 5-10 wt. % polyvinyl alcohol, 20-30 wt. % filler that constitutes of 40-50 wt. % sepiolite, 10-30 wt. % bentonite, 5-10 wt. % tombarthite and 20-30 wt. % kaolin
127	Shi J. 2018b	2018	CN 108249694 A	cooperates with flocculating agent and placing algae microorganism last
128	Guo Y. et al. 2018	2018	CN 108262350 A	modified sepiolite that was modified by acid and dolomite modification after calcination, followed by mixing fluvic acid and peanut cake, ended by crushing and sieving
129	Huang H. 2018	2018	CN 108246793 A	the raw materials comprises 50-100 wt. % sepiolite, 20-40 wt. % attapulgite, 20-50 wt. % activated sludge, 10-20 wt. % bacterial cellulose, 10-20 wt. % polyvinyl alcohol fiber, 5-10 wt. % medium chain triglyceride, 5-10 wt. % casein and 5-10 wt. % oligomeric lactic acid
130	Wang L. 2018	2018	CN 108249549 A	30-40 wt. % volcanic rock, 10-15 wt. % modified ceramic micro-powder, 5-10 wt. % organic additive material, 10-25 wt. % coal residue, 5-10 wt. % activated carbon, 4-8 wt. % quartz sand, 3-6 wt. % chlorinated polyvinyl chloride, 2-4 wt. % aniline formaldehyde resin, 1-2 wt. % poly- α -methylstyrene resin, 1-2 wt. % nano-sepiolite composite powder, 0.5-1 wt. % C9 petroleum resin, 0.3-0.5 wt. % bis-trifluoromethanesulfonimide and 0.02-0.05 wt. % zinc oxide
131	Gu W. et al. 2018	2018	CN 108246783 A	The water washing additive is composited of 35-40 wt. % shell powder, 30-35 wt. % sepiolite powder, 5-8 wt. % medical stone, 5-7 wt. % copolymer of dimethyl diallyl ammonium chloride and acrylamide, 5-8 wt. % sodium lignosulfonate, 10-15 wt. % modified ferroferric oxide, 3-4 wt. % nano-titanium oxide, 8-10 wt. % attapulgite, 5-18 wt. % polyacrylamide and 0.5-1 wt. % tea saponin.
132	Pan M. 2018a	2018	CN 108219798 A	(i)modified fly ash (ii)gel powder(iii)uniformly mixing 15-30 wt. % pond sludge, 10-30 wt. % peat moss, 3-10 wt.% red mud, 10-30 wt. % sepiolite, 15-25 wt.% activated clay, 8-18 wt. % soy sauce residue, 5-20 wt. % dried bean curd and 20-40 wt.% modified fly ash to made mixture A
133	Pan M. 2018b	2018	CN 107698068 A	mixing wastewater with polyethylene tetrazole-type chelating resin and furfuryl alcohol-modified urea formaldehyde resin, adding filtrate with sulfhydryl-modified sepiolite, diatomaceous opal powder, palygorskite and straw powder, then ultrasonically oscillating, followed by adding walnut powder and rice bran, then stirring and filtering and then adding filtrate with fern powder, buckwheat leaf powder and oyster shell powder

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
134	Xiao M. et al. 2018	2018	CN 108191181 A	32-38 wt. % sodium sepiolite, 15-25 wt. % modified kieselguhr, 40-60 wt. % hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, 10-16 wt. % wood ceramic, 6-10 wt. % saponin, 6-8 wt. % lipoic acid sodium and 10-15 wt. % triethyl citrate. The sodium sepiolite was prepared by adding sepiolite to distilled water in solid-liquid ration of 1g:50ml, which was followed by adding sodium carbonate at mass ration 1:25 of the sodium carbonate to sepiolite
135	Liu Y. & Liu W. 2018	2018	CN 108190974 A	10-20 wt.% sodium bentonite, 8-15 wt. % quartz powder, 5-10 wt. % clay, 10-20 wt. % diatomaceous earth, 2-5 wt. % sawn wood powder, 8-12 wt. % zeolite, 8-10 wt. % discharged manganese, 1-2 wt. % magnet powder, 15-20 wt. % activated carbon, 3-5 wt. % sepiolite and 4-6 wt. % medicinal stone
136	Feng Z. 2018	2018	CN 108192638 A	45-64 wt. % clay mineral, 24-33 wt. % straw, 10-14 wt. % chitosan, 5-8 wt. % alfalfa, 6-9 wt. % polydimethyldiallyl ammonium chloride, 8-15 wt. % water- soluble polyvinyl alcohol, 1.5-3 wt. % guar gum, 4-6 wt. % sodium carbonate, 5-10 wt. % metal oxide and 2-5 wt. % sodium humate, where clay mineral could be one or more than one of those attapulgite, sepiolite, illite, palygorskite, montmorillonite and kaolin
137	Zhu J. et al. 2018	2018	CN 108160688 A	(i) mixing 3-5 mg polyanionic cellulose, 2-5 mg graphene oxide, 2-5 mg activated carbon fiber, 2-4 mg magnetic graphite, 4-7 mg magnetic chitosan, 10-20 ml isopropanol and stirring with 1000-2000 ml deionized water for 10-20 minutes; (ii) adding 250-300 g contaminated soil and stirring for 20-30 minutes at 200-250 rpm rotation speed, filtering and removing the filtrate; (iii) mixing 3-6 mg rice husk ash, 4-6 mg humic acid, 4-8 mg phenolase lignin and 1000-2000 ml deionized water, followed by 5-10 minutes stirring, then was filtered and filtrate removed; (iv) adding 3-6 mg reed straw biological carbon, 3-5 mg chicken manure biological carbon and 4-8 mg walnut biological carbon, followed by heating to 50-60°C and stirring for 15-20 minutes, then filtered and filtrate removed; (v) adding 4-8 mg mushroom bran, 3-6 mg sepiolite and 1-2 mg lychee shell powder, followed by stirring for 10-20 minutes at the speed of 100-200 rpm, then filtered and filtrate removed; (vi) adding 5-10 mg ammonium nitrate, 3-6 mg ammonium oxalate and stirring for 10-20 minutes at speed of 200-300 rpm
138	Qiu X. et al. 2018a	2018	CN 108128906 A	20-25 wt. % active carbon, 10-12 wt. % nano-ferroferric oxide, 45-50 wt. % lipase solution, 5-8 wt. % sepiolite powder, 5-8 wt. % zeolite powder, 5-8 wt. % medical stone powder, 5-8 wt. % vermiculite, 5-8 wt. % perlite, 10-12 wt. % chitosan, 3-5 wt. % humate, 10-12 wt. % sodium carboxymethyl starch, 8-10 wt. % polyaluminium chloride and 0.5-0.7 wt. % tea polyphenol
139	Qiu X. et al. 2018b	2018	CN 107983312 A	23-28 wt. %, preferably 25 wt. % nano-ferroferric oxide, 37-42 wt. %, preferably 39 wt. % lipase solution, 8-12 wt. %, preferably 10 wt. % sodium humate, 10-12 wt. %, preferably 11 wt. % medical stone powder, 11-13 wt. %, preferably 12 wt. % sodium carboxymethyl starch, 10-12 wt. %, preferably 11 wt. % polyaluminum chloride, 5-8 wt. %, preferably 6 wt. % chitosan, 5-8 wt. %, preferably 7 wt. % sepiolite powder, and 5-8 wt. %, preferably 6 wt. % zeolite powder

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
140	Guo M. 2018	2018	CN 107954492 A	5-10 wt. % sepiolite, 25-35 wt. % modified clay, 6-7 wt. % polyacrylamide, 15-20 wt. % bentonite, 20-25 wt. % cross-linked rectorite, 3-6 wt. % chitosan, 5-10 wt. % shell, 1-2 wt. % peanut shell, 2-3 wt. % chestnut shell, 1-2 wt. % peanut shell and 1-2 wt. % macadamia shell
141	Zhang L. 2018	2018	CN 107935334 A	35-45 wt. % diatomite, 7-15 wt. % benzoyl peroxide, 3-7 wt. % 2,2-dimethylolpropionic acid, 11-19 wt. % triethylamine and 28-36 wt. % sepiolite
142	Song W. et al. 2018a	2018	CN 107913681 A	65-75 wt. % straw, 30-40 wt. % acrylic emulsion, 8-12 wt. % nano calcium carbonate, 8-12 wt. % polyethylene glycol, 8-12 wt. % sepiolite powder, 40-50 wt. % 10-15% concentration of sodium silicate solution, 5-10 wt. % crosslinker, 0.2-0.5 wt. % initiator and 0.2-0.5 wt. % dibutyl tin dilaurate
143	Song W. et al. 2018b	2018	CN 107694531 A	60-70 wt. % ramie straw, 30-40 wt. % acrylic emulsion, 8-12 wt. % nano-calcium carbonate, 9-12 wt. % polyethylene glycol, 8-12 wt. % sepiolite, 40-50 wt. % of 10-12 wt.% sodium silicate solution, 6-9 wt. % hydroxyethyl cellulose, 6-9 wt. % crosslinker, 0.2-0.4 wt. % initiator and 0.2-0.4 wt. % dibutyltin dilaurate
144	Zheng B. et al. 2018	2018	CN 107840432 A	60-80 wt. % water, 40-60 wt. % beta-cyclodextrin, 20-35 wt. % polyacrylamide, 20-35 wt. % sodium humate, 15-30 wt. % sepiolite, 10-30 wt. % calcium oxide, 10-20 wt. % magnesium oxide, 5-15 wt. % ferric oxide and 5-15 wt. % Sodium carbonate
145	Mao Z. 2018	2018	CN 107815316 A	biochar, calcium dihydrogen phosphate, sepiolite, lime powder, tartaric acid, malic acid, potassium, chitosan and beans root stalk
146	Unannounced I. 2018	2018	CN 107771451 A	bamboo charcoal, zeolite, sepiolite, litchi fruit peel powder and dairy manure biochar
147	Li C. 2018	2018	CN 107777766 A	activated carbon, alum, calcium hydroxide, ferric chloride, sepiolite, natural clay, magnesium carbonate and calcium aluminate
148	Jiang Y. et al. 2018	2018	CN 107722991 A	30-50% composite adsorbent, 10-30% stable curable adhesive and water. The composite adsorbent comprises grinding triiron tetraoxide, attapulgite, iron phosphate and sepiolite in the weight ratio at 0.8-1:1-1.4:0.8-1:0.5-0.7, while stable curable adhesive comprising mixing cement, sodium and fine sand alginate at 1:0.6-1.2:0.1-0.3
149	Zheng S. et al. 2018	2018	CN 107715832 A	30-70 wt. % kaolin, sepiolite, diatomaceous earth, attapulgite and bentonite, then followed by calcining at 400-700 °C for 1-10 hours, where 10-50 wt. % alkaline solution was added to the mixture and it was heated for 2-8 hours at 65-90 °C, filtering and washing filtrate with water, putting filtering solution with aluminum salt solution, adjusting pH of the mixture to 7.5-9.5 to get gel material, which was mixed with washed filtrate and additives

Composition of sepiolite and other materials				
No.	Inventor/Author	Year	Patent No./doi.	Composition
150	Zhang W. et al. 2018	2018		comprised of more than one of polyacrylamide (PAM), humic acid (HAC), sepiolite, peat, bentonite, sludge compost (SC), lime, and fly ash
151	Guo G. et al. 2018	2018		four amendments (sepiolite(SE), triple super phosphate(TSP), single superphosphate(SSP), calcium magnesium phosphate (CMP)) were respectively combined with one foliar fertilizer (ZnSO ₄).the lowest available concentrations of Cd and Pb were found in the combination of SE and SSP (SE + SSP) as well as SE and CMP (SE + CMP) treatments, respectively. while the reduction of concentrations of Cd and Pb in wheat grain was 20.68~41.38% (SE+SSP mostly reduced the concentration of Cd in wheat by 41.38%) and 23.68~55.26% (SE+CMP significantly reduced the accumulation of Pb in the wheat grains by 55%), respectively
152	Xi Y. et al. 2018	2018		cement, fly ash, quicklime, sepiolite, montmorillonite and their proportions. the curing effect of the combination of cement, quicklime and sepiolite in weight ratio of 2:1:1 is not better those of cement and fly ash in weight ratio of 2:1 or cement, quicklime and fly ash in weight ratio of 2:1:1

Data for Fig. 6.2 in main thesis:

Variation of additives in sepiolite-based composites (in literature reports 1864–2018)

Materials in the composites	sepiolite	modified sepiolite	lime	bentonite	chitosan based	zeolite based	activated carbon	calcium source	straw based	attapulgate clay
Frequencies of material identified	131	20	31	27	25	25	20	19	18	16

Data for Fig. 6.3 in main thesis:

Variation of additives in sepiolite-based composites (in literature reports 1864–2018)

Materials in the composites	fly ash	phosphate-based	modified iron or iron	potassium-based	polyacrylamide	clay mineral	water	humic acid	starch
Frequencies of material identified	15	14	13	12	12	12	12	12	11

Materials in the composites	biochar	calcium-magnesium phosphate	diatomite	cellulose-based	montmorillonite	kaolin	shell
Frequencies of material identified	11	11	11	11	10	10	10

Data for Fig. 6.4 in main thesis:

Variation of additives in sepiolite-based composites (in literature reports 1864–2018)

Materials in the composites	silica-based	carbonate-based	limestone	peat	polyvinyl alcohol-based	humate-based	fruit peel	urea	zinc sulfate
Frequencies of material identified	9	8	8	8	8	7	6	6	6

Materials in the composites	charcoal-based	aluminum-based	ammonium sulfate	vermiculite	manure	alumina	cattle manure biochar	ferrous sulfate
Frequencies of material identified	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Materials in the composites	glass beads	sodium alginate	cement	gamma-alumina	seaweed	palygorskite	polyethylene glycol	other
Frequencies of material identified	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4

Data for questionnaire in main thesis:

Questions	Independent variable	Percentage	Frequency	Distribution
5. Where are the project sites you have worked on?	Southwest	17.76%	19	13.29%
	Northwest	14.95%	16	11.19%
	Central China	22.43%	24	16.78%
	North China	10.28%	11	7.69%
	East China	43.93%	47	32.87%
	South China	20.56%	22	15.38%
	Northeast	2.80%	3	2.10%
	Taiwan, Hong Kong and Macau	0.93%	1	0.70%
				143
6. What type of company do you work in?	Technical service company (consultancy, Planning consultancy, Contracting services)	62.62%	67	45.27%
	Equipment or material services	1.87%	2	1.35%
	state-owned business	16.82%	18	12.16%
	Enterprises of the Composite-Ownership System	4.67%	5	3.38%
	private enterprise	32.71%	35	23.65%
	Higher education and scientific research institutions	8.41%	9	6.08%
	Others	11.21%	12	8.11%
				148
7. What service do your company/organization provide?	Third Party Testing	40.19%	43	19.55%
	Consultancy, Planning consultancy	76.64%	82	37.27%
	Contracting services	32.71%	35	15.91%
	construction	36.45%	39	17.73%
	Equipment or material services	12.15%	13	5.91%
	Others	7.48%	8	3.64%
				220

Questions	Independent variable	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	N/A	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	N/A
8. If your company/organization provide service in Environmental consultancy-Contaminated site assessment/remediation, please estimate the service frequency of the listed sub-service provided in your working experience.	Site investigation	8	8	24	31	23	13	7.48%	7.48%	22.43%	28.97%	21.50%	12.15%
	Chemical expertise and/or laboratory	16	9	18	26	23	15	14.95%	8.41%	16.82%	24.30%	21.50%	14.02%
	Environmental impact assessment	19	16	20	23	12	17	17.76%	14.95%	18.69%	21.50%	11.21%	15.89%
	Hydrology & hydrogeology	30	22	16	13	6	20	28.04%	20.56%	14.95%	12.15%	5.61%	18.69%
	Retrospective (post) evaluation test	22	20	23	12	10	20	20.56%	18.69%	21.50%	11.21%	9.35%	18.69%
	Quality verification and monitoring of key project nodes	21	16	22	17	8	23	19.63%	14.95%	20.56%	15.89%	7.48%	21.50%
	Others	20	7	22	8	7	43	18.69%	6.54%	20.56%	7.48%	6.54%	40.19%
9. If your company/organization provide service in Contaminated Land/remediation-Contracting, please estimate the service frequency of the listed sub-service provided in your working experience.	Phytoremediation	24	23	19	12	1	28	22.43%	21.50%	17.76%	11.21%	0.93%	26.17%
	Bioremediation	25	24	19	9	1	29	23.36%	22.43%	17.76%	8.41%	0.93%	27.10%
	Plant-Microbial Remediation	28	22	19	10	0	28	26.17%	20.56%	17.76%	9.35%	0.00%	26.17%
	Solidification/Stabilization	12	12	17	40	5	21	11.21%	11.21%	15.89%	37.38%	4.67%	19.63%
	Soil washing/jet washing	20	16	29	16	0	26	18.69%	14.95%	27.10%	14.95%	0.00%	24.30%
	Thermal treatment	16	17	21	27	2	24	14.95%	15.89%	19.63%	25.23%	1.87%	22.43%

Questions	Independent variable	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	N/A	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	N/A
	Landfarming/biopiling	25	16	20	18	0	28	23.36%	14.95%	18.69%	16.82%	0.00%	26.17%
	Landfill	19	11	25	27	2	23	17.76%	10.28%	23.36%	25.23%	1.87%	21.50%
	Chemical oxidation/reduction technology	12	14	30	23	4	24	11.21%	13.08%	28.04%	21.50%	3.74%	22.43%
	Others	26	12	18	4	3	44	24.30%	11.21%	16.82%	3.74%	2.80%	41.12%
10. If your company/organization provide service in Contaminated Land/remediation-specialised material, please estimate the service frequency of the listed sub-service provided in your working experience.	Absorbents	22	18	17	19	2	29	20.56%	16.82%	15.89%	17.76%	1.87%	27.10%
	Biological materials	25	22	17	9	2	32	23.36%	20.56%	15.89%	8.41%	1.87%	29.91%
	Chemical materials	20	17	22	14	2	32	18.69%	15.89%	20.56%	13.08%	1.87%	29.91%
	Others	33	16	8	5	4	41	30.84%	14.95%	7.48%	4.67%	3.74%	38.32%
11. If your company/organization provide service in Contaminated Land/remediation-specialised Equipment, please estimate the service frequency of the listed sub-service provided in your working experience.	Monitoring equipment	19	9	20	23	6	30	17.76%	8.41%	18.69%	21.50%	5.61%	28.04%
	Reclamation equipment	29	16	19	7	2	34	27.10%	14.95%	17.76%	6.54%	1.87%	31.78%
	Drilling & piling equipment	18	9	17	32	4	27	16.82%	8.41%	15.89%	29.91%	3.74%	25.23%
	Excavation equipment	23	11	16	23	4	30	21.50%	10.28%	14.95%	21.50%	3.74%	28.04%
	Transportation Equipment	21	12	14	21	5	34	19.63%	11.21%	13.08%	19.63%	4.67%	31.78%
	Other	31	9	13	7	5	42	28.97%	8.41%	12.15%	6.54%	4.67%	39.25%

12.Do you have experience of soil stabilization?		
Yes	52	48.60%
No	51	47.66%
Not sure	4	3.74%
Sum	107	100.00%

13.If you have experience of soil stabilization, what additives/methods do you use?						
	Yes	No	Not sure	Yes	No	Not sure
	Frequency			Percentage		
Clay minerals	39	13	55	36.45%	12.15%	51.40%
Other minerals	23	29	55	21.50%	27.10%	51.40%
Chemical materials	33	19	55	30.84%	17.76%	51.40%
Microbial material	12	40	55	11.21%	37.38%	51.40%
Other	6	46	55	5.61%	42.99%	51.40%

15.If you have experience of applying sepiolite-based material in soil stabilization, what additives/methods do you use?						
	Yes	No	Not sure	Yes	No	Not sure
Sepiolite composited/ modified products	13	1	93	12.15%	0.93%	86.92%
Sepiolite raw mining	6	8	93	5.61%	7.48%	86.92%
Sepiolite processing byproducts	4	10	93	3.74%	9.35%	86.92%
Other	0	14	93	0.00%	13.08%	86.92%

18. Who pays for the costs of the soil remediation project?						
	National special purpose funds	Local government funds	Land developers	Enterprises that are responsible for pollution	The third party sponsor	Other
Yes	62	72	43	64	14	6
No	45	35	64	43	93	101
SUM	107	107	107	107	107	107
	Percentage					
Yes	57.94%	67.29%	40.19%	59.81%	13.08%	5.61%
No	42.06%	32.71%	59.81%	40.19%	86.92%	94.39%
SUM	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

19. What kind of intellectual property are owned or used by your company?										
	Trademark	Patent	Copyright	Trade secret	Other	Trademark	Patent	Copyright	Trade secret	Other
Yes	22	67	21	30	26	20.56%	62.62%	19.63%	28.04%	24.30%
No	85	40	86	77	81	79.44%	37.38%	80.37%	71.96%	75.70%
SUM	107	107	107	107	107	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

20. What is the basis of decision making on the choice of remediation method applied in projects?							
	Remediation target value	Land use nature (for growing crops, for building anything, for fishing)	Government reply	Enterprise investment	Expert opinion	Rules and Regulations	Other
Yes	81	74	48	31	69	54	9
No	26	33	59	76	38	53	98
SUM	107	107	107	107	107	107	107
Yes	75.70%	69.16%	44.86%	28.97%	64.49%	50.47%	8.41%
No	24.30%	30.84%	55.14%	71.03%	35.51%	49.53%	91.59%
SUM	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

21.How important do you feel the following factors are in delivering successful remediation on site?								
	Site background/history investigation	Remediation target value	Technical proposal	Capital guarantee	Performance or experience of similar projects	Corporate environmental awareness	Public opinion cognition	Other
	Frequency							
Unimportant	1	0	2	0	0	0	1	6
Slightly Important	5	3	3	6	5	6	9	10
Moderately Important	3	7	3	4	35	26	29	17
Important	31	39	34	31	41	41	40	24
Very Important	58	49	56	57	15	23	15	4
N/A	9	9	9	9	11	11	13	46
SUM	107	107	107	107	107	107	107	107
	Percentage							
Unimportant	0.93%	0.00%	1.87%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.93%	5.61%
Slightly Important	4.67%	2.80%	2.80%	5.61%	4.67%	5.61%	8.41%	9.35%
Moderately Important	2.80%	6.54%	2.80%	3.74%	32.71%	24.30%	27.10%	15.89%
Important	28.97%	36.45%	31.78%	28.97%	38.32%	38.32%	37.38%	22.43%
Very Important	54.21%	45.79%	52.34%	53.27%	14.02%	21.50%	14.02%	3.74%
N/A	8.41%	8.41%	8.41%	8.41%	10.28%	10.28%	12.15%	42.99%
SUM	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

22.Does the business decision making of remediation project affect the following factors?										
	Land usage	Government request	Social group	Future development of the land	Other	Land usage	Government request	Social group	Future development of the land	Other
	Frequency					Percentage				
Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0	6	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	5.61%
Disagree	3	2	6	1	2	2.80%	1.87%	5.61%	0.93%	1.87%
Undecided	4	14	30	10	18	3.74%	13.08%	28.04%	9.35%	16.82%
Agree	43	38	41	50	22	40.19%	35.51%	38.32%	46.73%	20.56%
Strongly Agree	43	39	15	32	10	40.19%	36.45%	14.02%	29.91%	9.35%
N/A	14	14	15	14	49	13.08%	13.08%	14.02%	13.08%	45.79%
SUM	107	107	107	107	107	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

23.Does following factors causes the competition in different companies on soil/land remediation area?						
	Existing construction means and technology	Performance or experience of similar projects	Service / product price changes	New product/equipment development	Market positioning	Other
	Frequency					
Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	1	1	2
Disagree	1	4	2	1	5	5
Undecided	5	17	11	17	19	16
Agree	56	52	57	49	46	23
Strongly Agree	34	22	26	29	26	9
N/A	11	12	11	10	10	52
SUM	107	107	107	107	107	107
	Percentage					
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.93%	0.93%	1.87%
Disagree	0.93%	3.74%	1.87%	0.93%	4.67%	4.67%
Undecided	4.67%	15.89%	10.28%	15.89%	17.76%	14.95%
Agree	52.34%	48.60%	53.27%	45.79%	42.99%	21.50%
Strongly Agree	31.78%	20.56%	24.30%	27.10%	24.30%	8.41%
N/A	10.28%	11.21%	10.28%	9.35%	9.35%	48.60%
SUM	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

24. Are these factors are used for setting remediation targets?								
	Land usage	Technical means	Capital budgeting	Payback period	National and industrial standards	Government request	Masses appeal	Other
	Frequency							
Strongly Disagree	0	2	4	4	1	1	2	5
Disagree	1	7	6	7	1	3	9	8
Undecided	4	11	9	16	6	8	30	19
Agree	40	41	42	41	38	46	38	20
Strongly Agree	52	34	34	27	51	38	16	6
N/A	10	12	12	12	10	11	12	49
SUM	107	107	107	107	107	107	107	107
	Percentage							
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	1.87%	3.74%	3.74%	0.93%	0.93%	1.87%	4.67%
Disagree	0.93%	6.54%	5.61%	6.54%	0.93%	2.80%	8.41%	7.48%
Undecided	3.74%	10.28%	8.41%	14.95%	5.61%	7.48%	28.04%	17.76%
Agree	37.38%	38.32%	39.25%	38.32%	35.51%	42.99%	35.51%	18.69%
Strongly Agree	48.60%	31.78%	31.78%	25.23%	47.66%	35.51%	14.95%	5.61%
N/A	9.35%	11.21%	11.21%	11.21%	9.35%	10.28%	11.21%	45.79%
SUM	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

25. How important do you feel the following factors in verifying the success of remediation on site?										
	Tested data change	Checkup and acceptance comments	Project operation status	Social benefits	Other	Tested data change	Checkup and acceptance comments	Project operation status	Social benefits	Other
	Frequency					Percentage				
Unimportant	0	1	1	1	3	0.00%	0.93%	0.93%	0.93%	2.80%
Slightly Important	2	3	2	5	4	1.87%	2.80%	1.87%	4.67%	3.74%
Moderately Important	6	6	10	22	18	5.61%	5.61%	9.35%	20.56%	16.82%
Important	38	50	49	42	21	35.51%	46.73%	45.79%	39.25%	19.63%
Very Important	52	38	35	26	8	48.60%	35.51%	32.71%	24.30%	7.48%
N/A	9	9	10	11	53	8.41%	8.41%	9.35%	10.28%	49.53%
SUM	107	107	107	107	107	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

27. Would you like to participate in the follow-up interview?		
	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	41	38.32%
No	56	52.34%
Not sure	10	9.35%
SUM	107	100.00%

Data for Chinese companies in main thesis:

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
1	北京北科欧远科技有限公司	Beijing Beike Ouyuan Science&Technology Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包二级	北京	其他有限责任公司	500-999	http://www.oyst.com.cn
2	北京朗新明环保科技有限公司	Beijing Lucency Enviro-Tech Co.,Ltd.	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	北京	有限责任公司(法人独资)	210+	http://www.china-lucency.com
3	北京国电龙源环保工程有限公司	Beijing Guodian Longyuan Environmental Engineering Co.,Ltd	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级/工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)甲级	北京	有限责任公司(法人独资)	100-499	http://www.lyhb.cn
4	博天环境集团股份有限公司	Poten Environment Group Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	北京	The listed company	500-999	http://www.poten.cn
5	北京高能时代环境技术股份有限公司	Beijing GeoEnviron Engineering & Technology, Inc.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级/工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)甲级,工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)甲级	北京	The listed company	2446	http://www.gnlining.com
6	清大国华环境集团股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	北京	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	www.gohigher.cn
7	北京远浪潮生态建设有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级/工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)乙级	北京	有限责任公司(自然人投资或控股)	100-499	

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/ City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
8	北京建工环境修复股份有限公司	Beijing Construction Engineering Environment Development Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	北京	Ltd.	500-999	http://www.bceer.com
9	北京轩昂环保科技股份有限公司	Beijing Xuan'ang Environmental Protection Technology Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	北京	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.xaep.com.cn
10	中节能六合天融环保科技有限公司	Zhongjieneng Liuhe Talroad (Beijing) Environmental Protection Technology Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	北京	Ltd.	500-999	http://www.lhtr.cecep.cn
11	中科鼎实环境工程有限公司	China state science dingshi environmental engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	北京	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.zkdshj.com
12	北京中电联环保股份有限公司	Beijing CEC Environment Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	-	北京	Ltd.	93+	http://www.ccec-ep.cn
13	北京市勘察设计研究院有限公司	Beijing Reconnaissance Design Research Institute Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	北京	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.bgi.com.cn

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
14	北京金河环保科技有限公司		Yes		工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	北京	其他有限责任公司	50-99	http://www.bjhhqy.com
15	中冶节能环保有限责任公司	MCC Energy Conservation And Environmental Protection Co., Ltd.	Yes		工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 甲级	北京	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.mcczyhb.cn
16	北京北方节能环保有限公司	-	Yes		工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 甲级/环保工程专业承包三级	北京	其他有限责任公司	100-499	http://www.cn gce.com
17	北京永新环保有限公司	Beijing Yongxin Environmental Protection Co., Ltd.	Yes		工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 甲级/环保工程专业承包二级	北京	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.e-e.com.cn
18	北京清新环境技术股份有限公司	Beijing SPC Environment Protection Tech Co., Ltd.	-		环保工程专业承包二级	北京	其他股份有限公司	500-999	http://www.qingxin.com.cn
19	上海同济建设科技股份有限公司	Shanghai Tongji Construction Technology Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	上海	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.tongjionline.net

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
20	上海圣珑环境修复技术有限公司	Shanghai Shenglong Environmet Remediation Technologies Co.,Ltd	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	上海	Ltd.	17+	http://sheng-long1.com
21	上海环境节能工程股份有限公司	Shanghai Environmental & Energy Conservation Engineering Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	上海	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.shhi.com.cn
22	上海龙净环保科技工程有限公司	Shanghai Longking Environmental Protection Co. Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	上海	Ltd.	500-999	http://www.longkingsh.com.cn
23	上海立昌环境科技股份有限公司	Shanghai Lichang Environment Engineering Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	上海	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.china-lichang.com
24	上海兴东环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	上海	Ltd.	50-99	-
25	上海环境卫生工程设计院有限公司	-	Yes		工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)甲级/环保工程专业承包二级	上海	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.huanke.com.cn
26	湖南百舸水利建设股份有限公司	Hunan Baige Dredging Co., Ltd.	Yes		环保工程专业承包三级	湖南	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	100-499	hunanbestall@vip.sina.com

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/ City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
27	湖南楚峰园林建设有限公司	Hunan Chufeng Horticulture Landscape Design Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	875093413@qq.com
28	湖南瑞元建设工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.hnryjs.com
29	湖南顺联建设工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	1464922162@QQ.COM
30	长沙中联重科环境产业有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级	湖南	Ltd.	1000-4999	http://www.zoamlion-enviro.com
31	长沙矿冶研究院有限责任公司	Changsha Research Institute of Mining & Metallurgy Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.crimm.com.cn
32	赛恩斯环保股份有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	其他股份有限公司	100-499	http://www.seshb.com

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
33	湖南中发环保科技有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	71+	www.hnzfjs.cn
34	航天凯天环保科技股份有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	股份有限公司（非上市、国有控股）	1000-4999	http://www.kaitiangroup.com/
35	永清环保股份有限公司	Yonker Environmental Protection Co.ltd.	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	The listed company	967	www.yonker.com.cn
36	湖南凯迪工程科技有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	www.hnkajs.cn
37	湖南湘牛环保实业有限公司	Hunan Xiangniu Environmental Protection Industrial Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.xniu.com

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
38	湖南亿康环保科技有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级, 工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.yk-hb.cc
39	湖南省园林建设有限公司	Hunan Horticulture Construction Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	85+	-
40	湖南艾布鲁环保科技股份有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	-	湖南	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	50-99	http://www.air-bluer.cn
41	湖南中车环境工程有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	-	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	www.nfyhbj.com
42	湖南碧蓝环保科技有限责任公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级, 工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.hn-bl.com

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43	湖南新九方科技有限公司	Hunan NewWorld Science and Technology Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）甲级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）甲级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.hnnewworld.com
44	常德德益环保工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	-	-
45	长沙华时捷环保科技发展股份有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	www.cshsj.com
46	湖南省和清环境科技有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）甲级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）甲级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	www.hunanheqing.com
47	湖南奇立建设工程有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	90	-

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48	湖南净源环境工程有限公司	Hunan Jingyuan Environmental Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes		工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级, 工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.hn-iy.net
49	湖南钦杰环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	-
50	湖南爱一环保科技有限公司	-	湖南爱一环保科技有限公司	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级, 工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.hnayhb.com
51	湖南源源生态工程集团有限公司	Hunan Huayu Water Resources & Hydropower Construction Engineering Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.yuanyuaneco.com
52	长沙奥邦环保实业有限公司	Changsha Aobang Environmental Protection Industry Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	43+	http://www.aobanghb.com

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53	湖南嘉洋工程设计有限责任公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)乙级,工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	www.ifdesign.com.cn
54	中湘环保股份有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)乙级,工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	40+	http://www.zhongxianghb.com
55	湖南高华环保股份有限公司	Hunan Gaohua Environmental Protection Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	29+	http://www.ghhbgf.com
56	湖南美源环保股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	23+	http://www.meiyuanhb.com
57	湖南华钰环保实业发展有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.hnhuayu.com
58	湖南恒凯环保科技投资有限公司	Hunan Hengkai Environmental Protection Technology Investment Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)甲级,工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)甲级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	http://cnhengkai.com

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59	湖南省煜城环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	http://qy.58.com/41150467
60	湖南中扬环保科技有限公司	-	yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	-
61	湖南北控威保特环境科技股份有限公司	Hunan Bg Well-point Environmental Science&technology Co.,Ltd.	yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	www.bkwbt.cn
62	湖南沃邦环保科技有限公司	-	yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	www.hnvauban.com
63	湖南蓝天环保科技有限公司	-	yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)乙级,工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	-
64	湖南智水环境工程有限公司	-	yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	<50	http://www.wisdomwater.cn

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65	湖南中南水务环保科技有限公司	-	yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级, 工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	http://znsz.msdi.cn
66	湖南三友环保科技股份有限公司	-	yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	https://www.sanyouep.cn
67	湖南上林环境景观工程有限公司	-	yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.sland.com.cn
68	湖南新典环境工程有限公司	-	yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	湖南	Ltd.	9+	http://www.hnxindian.com

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69	湖南中冶长天节能环保技术有限公司	-	yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）甲级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）甲级/环保工程专业承包三级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	www.zyctnh.com
70	湖南亿康环保科技有限公司	-	yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.yk-hb.cc

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71	湖南博世科环保科技有限公司	Hunan Huahong Municipal Engineering Design Co., Ltd.	yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）甲级/工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.bosscoco.com
72	湖南金旅环保股份有限公司	Changsha Jinlv Environmental Protection Technology Engineering Co., Ltd.	yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	湖南	股份有限公司（非上市、自然人投资或控股）	50-99	http://zhiyuqy.com
73	湖南正明环保股份有限公司	-	yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖南	股份有限公司（非上市、自然人投资或控股）	50-99	http://www.hnzmhj.com
74	湖南葆华环保科技有限公司	-	yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	湖南	Ltd.	<50	=
75	湖南润万环保科技有限公司	-	yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	湖南	Ltd.	<50	http://www.runwanhuanbao.cn

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76	湖南博一环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	湖南	Ltd.	<50	http://www.hnbyhb.cn
77	湖南泰谷生态工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	湖南	其他有限责任公司	100-499	http://www.taigugroup.com/
78	湖南中核环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	-
79	湖南现代环境科技股份有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	湖南	其他股份有限公司	100-499	http://www.hnxdhj.cn

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80	湖南长重环保科技有限责任公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	湖南	其他股份有限公司	<50	-
81	湖南本农环境科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	湖南	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.benotech.com/
82	湖南安淳高新技术有限公司	-	Yes		工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）甲级	湖南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.hnanchun.com
83	中国轻工业长沙工程有限公司	China CEC Engineering Corporation	Yes		工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）甲级	湖南	Ltd.	1000-4999	http://www.cccchina.com
84	东珠生态环保股份有限公司	-	Yes		环保工程专业承包三级	江苏	股份有限公司(上市)	100-499	http://www.jsdzjg.com
85	江苏方诚环保科技有限公司	Jiangsu Fangcheng Environmental Protection Technology Co., Ltd.	Yes		环保工程专业承包二级	江苏	Ltd.	<50	www.jsfctech.com

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86	江苏一环集团有限公司	Jiangsu Yihuan Group Co., Ltd.	Yes		环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	>1000	
87	江苏大地益源环境修复有限公司	Jiangsu Dadi Yiyuan Environment Rehab Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级, 工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.jsdbs.com
88	江苏安识环境科技有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	18+	http://as-hj.com
89	江苏天马环保科技集团有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	30+	http://www.tmhb.cn
90	江苏英凡伦环保工程有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	20+	http://www.china-environ.com
91	南通华新环保设备工程有限公司	-	Yes		环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	183+	http://www.hxhuanbao.com
92	江苏金环环保设备有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	50+	http://www.jinhuanep.com

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/ City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
93	江苏新光环保工程有限公司	Nanjing Xinguang Environmental Protection Technology Engineering Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	100-499	www.jsnewcon.com
94	南京国电环保科技有限公司	Nanjing Guodian Environmental Protection Equipment Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.njgdhb.com
95	南京万德斯环保科技股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.njwds.com
96	江苏永威环境科技股份有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	50-99	www.yongweihuanjing.com
97	江苏金润环保工程有限公司	-	Yes		环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.jsjrep.com
98	上田环境修复有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.stxfjs.com

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99	江苏海容热能环境工程有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	100-499	www.jshrrn.com
100	江苏鹏鹞环境工程设计院有限公司	Jiangsu Pengyao Environmental Engineering Design Institute	Yes		工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级	江苏	Ltd.	<50	-
101	鹏鹞环保股份有限公司	Penyao Environmental Protection Co., Ltd.	Yes		环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	The listed company	920	www.penyao.com.cn
102	江苏艾特克环境工程有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	30+	http://www.jshdhj.com/class.asp?id=28
103	江苏环球环境工程集团有限公司	Yixing Huanqiu Water Treatment Equipment Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	50-99	http://jshuanqu2009.cnal.com
104	科盛环保科技股份有限公司	Nanjing Kesheng Environmental Protection Technology Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.njkshb.com
105	凌志环保股份有限公司	Lingzhi Environment Protection Co. Ltd	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	股份有限公司 (台港澳与境内合资、未上市)	500-999	http://www.lzhb.com.cn

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106	江苏盖亚环境科技股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	50-99	http://qy.58.com/45937487
107	苏州上善环境科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	100-499	-
108	江苏菲力环保工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.philip.com.cn
109	江苏港峰环境科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.jsghj.com
110	荣诚环保工程有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	<50	www.rcjtchina.com
111	苏州市宏宇环境科技股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	50-99	http://www.szfzhb.com
112	鸿灌环境技术有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	江苏	Ltd.	50-99	www.chinahghj.com
113	江苏长三角环境科学技术研究院有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	<50	www.csjhjy.com

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
114	江苏普泽环境工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	<50	-
115	江苏中电创新环境科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.ceiet.com
116	江苏沃天环保科技有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	<50	www.jswthb.com
117	南京稷之朗环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	-	-
118	苏州城投环境科技发展有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	<50	-
119	镇江市中运城市环境治理有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	-	-
120	江苏华太生态环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	-	-

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121	江苏海智环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	-	-
122	江苏融景环境修复有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	江苏	Ltd.	-	
123	江苏峰业科技环保集团股份有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/ 环保工程专业承包二级	江苏	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	www.fengye.com
124	苏州同和环保工程有限公司	Suzhou Tonghe Environmental Engineering (Suzhou) Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	江苏	Ltd.	50-99	www.sthee.com
125	深圳市如茵生态环境建设有限公司	Shenzhen Ruyin Environment Construction Co., Ltd.	yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	广东	Ltd.	100-499	www.szruyin.com
126	广东环科院环境科技有限公司	Guangdong Provincial Academy of Environmental Science Environmental Technology	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	广东	Ltd.	<50	-

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127	广州应达环境工程设备有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	广东	Ltd.	<50	http://www.yingdahj.cn/
128	深圳文科园林股份有限公司	Shenzhen Wenke Gardening Industry Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	广东	股份有限公司 (上市)	1000-4999	http://www.wkyy.com
129	广东绿德园林环保工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	广东	Ltd.	-	-
130	广州市怡地环保有限公司	Guangzhou Yidi Environmental Protection Industry General Company	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	广东	Ltd.	<50	http://www.gzydjh.com
131	深圳市粤昆仑环保实业有限公司	Shenzhen Yuekunlun Environmental Protection Industry Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包二级	广东	Ltd.	100-499	
132	佛山市腾源环保科技有限公司	Foshan Shunde District Tengyuan Environmental Protection Water Co., Ltd.	-	-	环保工程专业承包二级	广东	Ltd.	100-499	www.fstyhb.com
133	广东莞绿环保工程有限公司		Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	广东	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.dgglyhb.com

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134	深圳市朗坤环境集团股份有限公司	Shenzhen Langkun Environmental Technology Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	广东	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	100-499	http://www.leoking.com
135	浩蓝环保股份有限公司	CNHOMELAND Environmental Co.,Ltd.	-	-	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	广东	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	100-499	hl@cnhomeland.com
136	广东开源环境科技有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	广东	ltd.	50-99	www.gdkyhj.com
137	岭南生态文旅股份有限公司	Lingnan Horticulture Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	广东	the listed company	1000-4999	www.lnlandscape.com
138	中兰环保科技有限公司	Shenzhen Gad Environmental Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	广东	股份有限公司	100-499	http://www.gad.net.cn
139	中际环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	广东	ltd.	-	-
140	广东中科碧城环境技术有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	广东	ltd.	<50	

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141	广东敦诚环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	广东	ltd.	100-499	http://www.gduncheng.com
142	广州四海同泰环境修复有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级	广东	ltd.	<50	∞
143	广东中轻工程设计院	Guangdong Zhongqing Engineering Design Institute	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级	广东	全民所有制	-	∞
144	广东东日环保股份有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	广东	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	50-99	http://www.dongnigricn.com
145	广东绿日环境科技有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	广东	其他有限责任公司	50-99	∞
146	广州富生源环保工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	广东	ltd.	100-499	http://www.fsyhb.com

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147	广州市金龙峰环保设备工程股份有限公司	Guangzhou jinlongfeng Environmental Protection Equipment Engineering Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级, 工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	广东	股份有限公司	100-499	-
148	广州资源环保科技股份有限公司	Guangzhou Resource Environmental Protection Hydroelectric Engineering Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	广东	其他股份有限公司	500-999	http://www.rcnep.com/
149	广州草木蕃环境科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	广东	ltd.	50-99	http://www.camufan.com
150	深圳市前海东江环保科技服务有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	广东	ltd.	-	-
151	广东瑞星环境科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	广东	ltd.	-	http://www.rxhj.com.cn

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152	广州市适然环境工程技术有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	广东	ltd.	50-99	www.gzshiran.com
153	广东省环境保护工程研究设计院有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 甲级	广东	ltd.	-	http://www.geeein.com.cn
154	广州市环境保护工程设计院有限公司	GuangZhou EP Environmental Engineering Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	广东	其他有限责任公司	500-999	http://www.gzep.com
155	广东寰球广业工程有限公司	Guangdong Huanqiu Guangye Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级	广东	ltd.(国有控股)	100-499	http://www.gpedi.com.cn
156	深圳市汇清科技股份有限公司	Shenzhen Huiqing Technology Co., Ltd	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	广东	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	500-999	www.sz-huiqing.com
157	浙江博华环境技术工程有限公司	Zhejiang Bohua Environment Technology Engineering Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	浙江	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.zjbohua.com
158	浙江深度能源技术有限公司		Yes	-	环保工程专业承包二级	浙江	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.zjsdny.com

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
159	浙江大学能源工程设计研究院有限公司	Zhejiang University Energy Sources Engineering Design Research Institute	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级	浙江	Ltd.	<50	-
160	浙江德创环保科技股份有限公司	Zhejiang Tuna Environmental Science & Technology Co. Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	浙江	the listed company	500-999	http://www.zi-tuna.com
161	浙江菲达环保科技股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	浙江	the listed company	1000-4999	www.feidaep.com
162	浙江卓锦环保科技股份有限公司	Zhejiang Zone-King Engineering & Technology Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	浙江	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	100-499	http://www.zone-king.com
163	中节能大地 (杭州) 环境修复有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	浙江	ltd.	100-499	-
164	中国电建集团环境工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	浙江	其他有限责任公司	<50	-

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165	浙江博世华环保科技有限公司	Zhejiang Boshihua Environmental Technologies Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级, 工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	浙江	其他有限责任公司	100-499	https://www.bestwa.com
166	浙江蓝天求是环保股份有限公司	Zhejiang Lantian Qiushi Environmental Protection Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	浙江	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.zjaep.com/
167	天津市绿通环保工程设备开发有限公司	Tianjin Lvtong Environmental Protection Engineering Equipments Development Co.,	-	-	环保工程专业承包二级	天津	ltd.	50-99	http://www.lthbao.com
168	天津建昌环保股份有限公司	Tianjin Jianchang Environmental Protection Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	天津	股份有限公司	50-99	http://www.tjjchb.com
169	九洲环境科技 (天津) 有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	天津	ltd.	50-99	-

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170	天津中润环境工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	天津	ltd.	-	-
171	天津水泥工业设计研究院有限公司	Tianjin Cement Industry Design & Research Institute Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)乙级	天津	ltd.	500-999	http://www.sinoma-tcdri.cn
172	天津市联合环保工程设计有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	天津	ltd.	100-499	http://www.tuee.com.cn
173	河北德龙环境工程股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	河北	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	www.delonghb.com
174	河北宁泊环保股份有限公司	Ningpo Environmental Protection Co., Ltd.	-	-	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	河北	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	100-499	-
175	河北高科环保集团有限公司	Hebei High-Tech Environmental Protection Group Co.,Ltd.	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	河北	ltd.	50-99	http://www.gk-hbjt.com

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176	中铁城际规划建设有限公司	Zhongjiao Road & Bridge (Hebei) Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	河北	其他有限责任公司	100-499	www.ztcjit.com
177	河北鑫泰节能环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	河北	ltd.	50-99	-
178	东方同华环保工程有限公司	Tangshan Bokai Environmental Protection Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	河北	ltd.	100-499	-
179	煜环环境科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	河北	ltd.	50-99	http://www.hebeiyuhuan.com
180	河北九州环保设备工程有限公司	Jiuzhou Environmental Protection Equipment Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	河北	ltd.	-	http://www.hbjzcc.cn

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181	河北中科威德环境工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	河北	ltd.	100-499	0
182	承德市正通环境工程设计有限责任公司	Chengde Zhengtong Environmental Engineering Design Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级	河北	ltd.	<50	-
183	山西长清环境工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包三级	山西	ltd.	<50	-
184	山西晋浙环保科技有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	山西	ltd.	<50	www.sxjzhbki.com
185	山西新唐工程设计股份有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级	山西	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.xtgcsj.com
186	太原核清环境工程设计有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级	山西	ltd.	50-99	www.tyhqhb.com

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187	山西清泽阳光环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	山西	ltd.	50-99	-
188	山西尚风科技股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	山西	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	100-499	http://www.chinadfq.com
189	山西华通蓝天环保有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	山西	ltd.	<50	http://www.sxhtlt.com
190	山西青山环保工程有限公司	Shanxi Qingshan Environmental Protection Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	山西	ltd.	<50	http://www.qshb.com
191	山西智德安全技术股份有限公司	Shanxi Zhide Safety Engineering Technology Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	山西	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.zdaq999.com
192	中化二建集团有限公司	China Chemical Engineering Second Construction Corporation	-	-	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	山西	ltd.	1000-4999	www.ccescc.com

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193	吉林东北煤炭工业环保研究有限公司	-	-	Yes		吉林	ltd.	100-499	http://www.jldmhb.com
194	沈阳化工研究院设计工程有限公司	Shenyang Chemical Industry Research Institution Design Office	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级	辽宁	ltd.	1000-4999	www.syricide.com
195	辽宁北方环境保护有限公司	Liaoning Beifang Environmental Protection Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	辽宁	ltd.	100-499	http://www.lnbfb.com
196	沈阳风景园林股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	辽宁	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.fjgarden.com
197	营口市环境工程开发有限公司	Yingkou Environment Engineering Development Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	辽宁	ltd.	100-499	http://www.ykfbgs.com
198	辽宁中科环保股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	辽宁	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	<50	http://www.zkfb.com

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199	辽宁辽河泰达土壤修复有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	辽宁	ltd.	<50	-
200	大连金禹环境工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	辽宁	ltd.	50-99	www.jinyuhuanjing.cn
201	沈阳赛思环境工程设计研究中心有限公司	Shenyang Saisi Environmental Engineering Design & Research Center	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）甲级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）甲级/环保工程专业承包三级	辽宁	ltd.	50-99	http://www.rengongshidi.com
202	中国能源建设集团辽宁电力勘测设计院有限公司	Liaoning Electric Power Reconnaissance & Design Institute	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）甲级/工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级	辽宁	ltd.	100-499	http://www.lepdi.ceec.net.cn

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
203	辽宁北四达生态环境科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程) 乙级	辽宁	ltd.	<50	-
204	辽宁华孚环境工程股份有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	辽宁	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	500-999	http://www.huafuep.com
205	中煤科工集团沈阳设计研究院有限公司	Shenyang Design & Research Institute of Sino-coal International Engineering Group	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	辽宁	ltd.	500-999	http://zmsyy.com
206	黑龙江库恩环境修复工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	黑龙江	ltd.	100-499	-
207	哈尔滨庆华市政工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	黑龙江	ltd.	<50	www.qinghua0451.com
208	安徽亚泰环境工程技术有限公司	Anhui Yatai Environmental Engineering Technology Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包二级	安徽	ltd.	100-499	http://www.ahytee.cn

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209	安徽久吾天虹环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	安徽	其他有限责任公司	-	http://www.thlz.cn
210	安徽国祯节能环保科技股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	安徽	ltd.	500-999	http://www.gzep.com.cn
211	安徽省通源环境节能股份有限公司	Anhui Tongyuan Environmental Energy Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	安徽	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	100-499	http://www.ah tongyuan.com
212	安徽水韵环保股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	安徽	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	<50	http://www.ahsyep.com
213	安徽蓝鼎环保能源科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	安徽	ltd.	50-99	http://www.ahldhb.com
214	泓诚建设集团有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包二级	福建	ltd.	50-99	-
215	福建园景城建生态科技有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包二级	福建	ltd.	100-499	http://www.yuanzhijing.com

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216	福建格瑞恩工程设计有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	福建	ltd.	<50	-
217	福建天普发展集团有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	福建	ltd.	50-99	http://www.tp-fzjt.com/index.htm
218	福建开天建设有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	福建	ltd.	100-499	-
219	福建龙净环保股份有限公司	Fujian Longking Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	福建	The listed company	1000-4999	http://longking.com.cn
220	中铁海峡建设集团有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	福建	其他有限责任公司	50-99	http://zthx.crc.cn
221	中联环股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	福建	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.cue-cu.com
222	福建省环境保护设计院有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	福建	ltd.	100-500	http://www.hbsiy.com

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223	厦门市颖艺景观工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包二级	福建	ltd.	100-500	http://www.xmyvig.com
224	江苏通达园林工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	江西	ltd.	<50	-
225	江西金达莱环保股份有限公司	Jiangxi JDL Environmental Protection Co., Ltd.	江西金达莱环保股份有限公司	-	环保工程专业承包三级	江西	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	www.jdlhb.com
226	中佳环境建设集团股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江西	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	50-99	http://zjhjst.com
227	格丰科技材料有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	江西	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.gfitem.com
228	江西盖亚环保科技有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	江西	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.gaiyahb.com
229	山东立德环境工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包二级	山东	Ltd.	<50	http://www.sdlidhb.com

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230	山东英群环境工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	山东	Ltd.	50-99	-
231	山东杨帆环保工程股份有限公司	Jinan Yangfanjie Water Equipment Engineering Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	山东	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	50-99	http://www.yangfanep.com
232	山东山大华特环保工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	山东	Ltd.	1000-4999	http://www.witec.cn
233	青岛华拓科技有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	山东	Ltd.	100-499	www.cnhuatuo.com
234	中广核宏达环境科技有限责任公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	山东	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.cgnhongda.com
235	山东沃能环保工程科技有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	山东	Ltd.	<50	www.sdwnhb.com

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236	山东省蓬勃安全环保服务有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	山东	其他有限责任公司	<50	www.sdpb.com.cn
237	黄河勘测规划设计研究院有限公司	Huanghe Surveying Planning & Designing Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	河南	Ltd.	1000-4999	http://www.yrec.cn
238	绿建景观设计工程有限公司	Lvjian Landscape Design Engineering Co.,Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	河南	Ltd.	500-999	http://www.leajan.com
239	郑州恒博环境科技股份有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包二级	河南	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	50-99	http://www.zzhbgs.com
240	中南金尚环境工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包二级	河南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.lshb.cn
241	河南哲东环保科技有限公司	Henan De'an Environmental Protection Equipment Co., Ltd.	-	Yes		河南	Ltd.	<50	http://www.cnzhedong.com

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242	河南同生环境工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	河南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.ts-scl.cn
243	郑州同济环保工程有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	河南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.hn-tjhb.com
244	开源环保(集团)有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	河南	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.ky-epe.cn/cn
245	河南强洁环保工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	河南	Ltd.	<50	www.hnqjhb.com
246	河南省地质环境规划设计院有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级	河南	Ltd.	<50	http://www.hn-dhs.com
247	武汉昌宝环保工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	湖北	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.changbaochina.com
248	武汉华德环保工程技术有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖北	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.huadet.com
249	武汉华柏环保科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖北	Ltd.	50-99	-

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250	武汉中科水生环境工程股份有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 甲级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖北	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.zkhbe.com
251	武汉森泰环保股份有限公司	Wuhan Sentai Environmental Protection Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖北	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	www.sentaihbc.com
252	湖北水云润环保工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	湖北	Ltd.	<50	http://www.syjkj.com
253	武汉市方远新技术发展有限责任公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	湖北	Ltd.	50-99	-
254	葛洲坝中国科技股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖北	股份有限公司 (非上市、外商投资企业投资)	100-499	http://www.gzbly.ceec.net.cn
255	武汉美佳源环境工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖北	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.miyhb.com

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256	中冶南方都市环保工程技术股份有限公司	China City Environment Protection Engineering Limited Company	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 甲级,工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 甲级/环保工程专业承包一级	湖北	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	500-999	http://www.ccep.com
257	武汉天源环保股份有限公司		Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	湖北	股份有限公司 (上市、自然人投资或控股)	500-999	http://www.tianyuanhuanbao.com
258	路德环境科技股份有限公司	Wuhan Lude Technology Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	湖北	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.road-group.com
259	湖北建科国际工程有限公司	Hubei Jianke Construction Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 甲级	湖北	其他有限责任公司	100-499	http://www.hbjkit.cn
260	武汉沃田生态科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级	湖北	Ltd.	<50	http://www.woteameco.com

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261	武汉瑞景环境修复工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	湖北	其他有限责任公司	50-99	www.rjrem.com
262	武汉景弘生态环境股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	湖北	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	50-99	http://www.kinghome.com.cn
263	中石化节能环保工程科技有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级	湖北	ltd.	100-499	-
264	广西博世科环保科技股份有限公司	Guangxi Bossco Environmental Protection Technology Co.,Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	广西	股份有限公司 (上市、自然人投资或控股)	1000-4999	http://www.bosscoco.com
265	广西益江环保科技股份有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	广西	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	<50	http://www.gxyjhb.com

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266	广西恒晟水环境治理有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	广西	Ltd.	500-999	http://www.gxhsshjzl.com
267	中国轻工业南宁设计工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级	广西	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.zqnn.cn
268	重庆华地资环科技有限公司	Chongqing Huadi Engineering Investigation Designing Institute	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	重庆	Ltd.	500-999	www.cqkcpjy.com
269	重庆图强工程技术咨询有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级	重庆	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.cqtqzx.com
270	重庆顶邦环保工程有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	重庆	Ltd.	-	-

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271	中煤科工集团 重庆设计研究 院有限公司	CCTEG Chongqing Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工 程) 乙级/工程设计环境工 程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级	重庆	Ltd.	5000- 9999	http://www.cqmsy.com/
272	国家电投集团 远达环保工程 有限公司	CPI Yuanda Environmental- Protection Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环 保工程专业承包一级	重庆	Ltd.	500- 999	http://www.yuandaep.com
273	招商局生态环 保科技有限公 司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项 (污染修复工程) 乙级/环 保工程专业承包二级/环保 工程专业承包三级	重庆	Ltd.	100- 499	www.cqscrc.com
274	重庆三峰卡万 塔环境产业有 限公司	Chongqing Sanfeng Covanta Environment Industry Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工 程) 甲级	重庆	Ltd.	100- 499	http://www.sancov.com

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/ City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
275	四川省科学城天人环保有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	四川	Ltd.	100-499	-
276	少伯环境建设有限公司	Chengdu Shaobo Virescence Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.wushaobo.com/index.html
277	四川美富特环境治理有限责任公司		Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	四川	Ltd.	50-99	-
278	四川恒泰环境技术有限责任公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	四川	其他有限责任公司	<50	http://www.entech.com.cn
279	四川君和环保股份有限公司	Sichuan Junhe Environmental Protection Company Limited	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.scihhb.com
280	四川铸坤建筑工程有限责任公司	Chengdu Wenjiang District Construction Co., Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	Ltd.	50-99	-

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/ City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
281	四川深蓝环保科技有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	Ltd.	100-499	http://sc-db.com
282	四川蜀望生态环保科技有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.swthb.com
283	四川航空工业大汉生态建设有限公司	Chengdu Dahan Industry Development Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	其他有限责任公司	50-99	http://www.avicdhst.com
284	四川信耀环保科技有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	Ltd.	50-99	-
285	四川光洁环境工程有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	其他有限责任公司	<50	-
286	四川正升环保科技有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	Ltd.	50-99	www.zsfangshen.com
287	四川同润环境治理有限责任公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	Ltd.	-	-
288	中海生态环境科技有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	Ltd.	2+	http://www.zhstkj.com/

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
289	四川时代绿洲环境修复股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	四川	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	-	-
290	四川环美工程设计有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程) 乙级	四川	Ltd.	<50	-
291	晨越建设项目管理集团股份有限公司	Chengdu Chenyue Construction Project Management Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程) 乙级	四川	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	100-499	http://www.cd-cy.cn
292	四川长虹格润环保科技股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级,工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	四川	股份有限公司(台港澳与境内合资、未上市)	100-499	http://www.ge-runzs.com

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
293	宏福环保技术有限公司	-	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	四川	Ltd.	<50	-
294	成都德菲环境工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	四川	Ltd.	<50	www.cddfjy.com
295	四川山水林生态环保工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	四川	Ltd.	<50	-
296	四川宜可环保技术有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级	四川	Ltd.	<50	http://www.scyikehb.com

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/ City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
297	四川新开元环保工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	四川	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.scxky.com
298	成都之和环保科技有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	四川	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.cdzhwater.com
299	贵州贵深环境工程有限公司	-	Yes	-	环保工程专业承包一级	贵州	Ltd.	100-499	-
300	贵州中大环境科技有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	贵州	Ltd.	50-99	-
301	云南海达新生态环境建设有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包三级	云南	ltd.	100-499	http://www.ynhdlh.com
302	云南协力环境科技有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级,工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级	云南	ltd.	-	-

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/ City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
303	银发环保股份有限公司	Yinfa Environmental Protection Corp.,Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	云南	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.ynyf.cn
304	圣清环保股份有限公司	-	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	云南	股份有限公司 (非上市、自然人投资或控股)	100-499	http://www.sqep.com
305	昆明理工大学设计研究院	-	Yes	=	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)乙级,工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)乙级	云南	全民所有制	100-499	http://www.kmustdri.com.cn
306	西南有色昆明勘测设计(院)股份有限公司	Xi'nan Non-ferrous Kunming Reconnaissance Design (Academy) Co.,Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程)乙级	云南	股份有限公司 (非上市、国有控股)	500-999	=
307	中国能源建设集团云南省电力设计院有限公司	Yunnan Electric Power Design Institute	Yes	=	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程)乙级	云南	ltd.	500-999	=
308	西安益众环保产业有限公司	-	Yes	=	环保工程专业承包二级	陕西	其他有限责任公司	<50	=

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/ City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
309	陕西标远环保科技有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	陕西	ltd.	50-99	www.sxbroadway.com
310	陕西环保集团水环境有限公司	Shaanxi Zhongxing Bailv Environmental Protection Engineering Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包三级	陕西	其他有限责任公司	100-499	http://www.sxhbjtshj.com
311	陕西蔚蓝节能环保科技集团有限责任公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项（污染修复工程）乙级, 工程设计环境工程专项（固体废物处理处置工程）乙级/环保工程专业承包一级	陕西	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.wilnlife.com.cn
312	陕西太阳景环保科技有限公司	Shaanxi Taiyangjing Environmental Protection Technology Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	陕西	Ltd.	50-99	http://www.susight.net.cn/

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/ City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
313	陕西秦邦环保科技股份有限公司	-	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项(污染修复工程) 乙级	陕西	其他股份有限公司(非上市)	100-499	-
314	中联西北工程设计研究院有限公司	China United Northwest Institute for Engineering Design & Research Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级	陕西	Ltd.	1000-4999	http://www.cuced.com/main.html
315	中铁一局集团市政环保工程有限公司	Municipal and Environmental Protection Engineering Co., Ltd. of China Railway First Group	-	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	甘肃	一人有限责任公司	1000-4999	http://szhb.crfecb.cn
316	新疆环境工程技术有限责任公司	Xinjiang Environment Engineering Technology Co.,Ltd.	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包一级	新疆	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.xjhjgc.com
317	新疆德安环保工程有限公司	-	Yes	Yes	环保工程专业承包二级	新疆	Ltd.	50-99	-
318	西藏国策环保科技股份有限公司	Tibet Guoce Environmental Protection Engineering Co., Ltd.	-	Yes	工程设计环境工程专项(固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级/环保工程专业承包二级	西藏	股份有限公司(非上市、自然人投资或控股)	5000-9999	-

No.	Company Chinese name	English name	Waste management	Soil remediation	Lisence	Province/ City	Company type	Scale	Homepage
319	内蒙古城市规划市政设计研究院有限公司	Inner Mongolia Urban Planning Municipal Design Institute Co., Ltd.	Yes	-	工程设计环境工程专项 (固体废物处理处置工程) 乙级	内蒙古	Ltd.	100-499	http://www.nmghy.com

Appendix II

Debriefing Form

An investigation of models used in commercial decision making and influence on the delivery of environmental improvement projects

Thank you for taking part in this research. This study is part of my PhD studies that I am undertaking at the University of the West of Scotland. The aim of the research is to gain an understanding of models used in commercial decision making and influence on the delivery of environmental improvement projects in the land/soil remediation sector in China and Scotland. More specifically, I am interested in whether the method and decision of methods applied is associated with budget, experience of professionals, their ways of balancing budget and aim of project, influence in terms of company abilities to meet challenges and succeed in achieving project objectives.

Previous research on soil remediation has mainly focused on the conventional physical and chemical remediation technologies which require much of resource input and energy and further lead to loss of land functionality or soil properties and secondary pollution (Song et al. 2019). Biological remediation is environmentally friendly, least destruction and of cost efficiency, which however is time consuming and valid to low-to-moderate levels of contamination. Combined remediation could reduce the limitation of any single technology used alone, but it requires more complex operation (Gong et al. 2018). To treat soil contaminated by mercury, the cost of full-scale thermal desorption procession is US\$834/m³ for treatment at the optimized operation situation(3h&750 °C) (Chang and Yen 2006). The current study is concerned more with the models used in commercial decision making and impact on the delivery of projects on the ground. The financial model that fits better with project in commercial decision making will promote the delivery of projects on the ground compared with the financial model that doesn't fit with project or fits badly with project in commercial decision making.

The goal of the current project, the first in a range of studies linked to this PhD, is to (i) consider potential changes in commercial decision making over various projects and (ii) explore the potential links between commercial decision making model and impact on the delivery of projects on the ground; these are explained in more detail below:

(i) Change in commercial decision making over various projects:

The study was survey based and focused on collecting data on the commercial decision making in projects of companies. The current research will use the original survey tool (questionnaire and interview) and data sets. This might allow for the establishment of commercial decision making model amongst various projects and for some consideration of change between commercial decision making.

(ii) Links between commercial decision making model and impact on the delivery of projects on the ground: These may mediate any potential impact of commercial decision making model and this study seeks to explore the relationship between commercial decision making (decision support tools, stakeholders etc.) and types of technology, coping strategies in projects.

If you would like more information about this study once it is completed, please contact the researcher, Na Song [REDACTED] or my supervisor, Prof. Andrew [REDACTED]

If you are interested in this area of research, you may wish to read the following references:

Chang, T. C., & Yen, J. H. (2006). On-site mercury-contaminated soils remediation by using thermal desorption technology, *128*, 208–217. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2005.07.053

Gong, Y., Zhao, D., & Wang, Q. (2018). An overview of field-scale studies on remediation of soil contaminated with heavy metals and metalloids: Technical progress over the last decade. *Water Research*, *147*, 440–460. doi:10.1016/j.watres.2018.10.024

Song, Y., Kirkwood, N., Maksimović, Č., Zhen, X., O'Connor, D., Jin, Y., & Hou, D. (2019). Nature based solutions for contaminated land remediation and brownfield redevelopment in cities: A review. *Science of the Total Environment*, *663*, 568–579. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.01.347

If you want to complain about this study, you can contact my Direct of Study. The contact details are as follow:

Professor Andrew Hursthouse (School of Computing, Engineering & Physical Sciences, University of the West of Scotland, Paisley PA1 2BE, UK)

Personal details withheld.

Participant Information Sheet

An investigation of models used in commercial decision making and influence on the delivery of environmental improvement projects.

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to gain an understanding of the models used in commercial decision making which influence the delivery of environmental improvement projects in the land/soil remediation sector in China.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a professional worked in land/soil remediation in China or Scotland. Your company was selected from research of published websites:

<http://www.mohurd.gov.cn/><https://www.qichacha.com>.

Do I have to take part?

No, it is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to participate you are still free to withdraw until your submission of the questionnaire by not completing the hard copy and returning the questionnaire to the researcher or by simply closing the browser online. After submission, individual participants cannot be identified, and it is therefore not possible to withdraw from the study following submission.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to complete a questionnaire or online survey or face to face interview where you will be asked about your experience on projects, brief introduction of company, typical ways of coping with pollution challenges in your area. The survey will take about 20minutes to complete.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no obvious risks or disadvantages associated with taking part however, there is the possibility that some of the questions of the survey might highlight some

issues about how well you think the process has been delivered. If this raises concern you can clarify with the researcher.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no direct personal benefits to taking part however, you will be providing information that may help to improve an understanding of how treatment professionals or companies' remediation methods influence the decision of remediation strategies on contaminated sites. Your feedback will also support the collection of academic research and presented anonymously to benefit academic understanding.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cuckow(ONLY) and she can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you.

Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this, and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. Or we will anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide by 1 week after the study and all data will be anonymised when analysed.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The data from the study will be published (anonymised) as part of a PhD thesis and may contribute to academic conference presentations and/or journal publications.

Who has reviewed the study?

CEPS (School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences) Research Ethics Committee

Contact for further information

If you require any further information, please contact:
Researcher:

In addition, you can contact Director of Studies:
Professor Andrew S Hursthouse,
University of the West of Scotland,
High Street,
Paisley,
Renfrewshire, Scotland.
PA1 2BE,
School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences,
Division of Environmental Geochemistry,

Personal details withheld.

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project:

Ethics Approval Number:

An investigation of models used in commercial decision making and influence on the delivery of environmental remediation projects.

Investigator(s):

Please read the following statements and, if you agree to participate this study, please tick the corresponding box at the end to confirm following all agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw up the point where I submit my questionnaire either online or by hard copy.

I consent to the processing of my personal information for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication or presentation resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Yes, I agree to participate.

No, I don't agree to participate

Personal details withheld.

Name of researcher (block capitals) NA SONG

Date

Signature: Na Song

12/12/2019

Dear Na Song,

Your application 9441: An investigation of models used in commercial decision making and influence on the delivery of environmental improvement projects, submission 7769, has been approved by the Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Hughes

Industry Situation Survey Questionnaire

1a What is your age?

- (1) 16-25
- (2) 26-35
- (3) 36-45
- (4) 46-55
- (5) 56-65
- (6) >65

1b What is your gender?

- (1) Male
- (2) Female
- (3) Other

1. What service do your company/organization provide:
(Please select all that apply)

- (1) Environmental consultancy-Contaminated site assessment/remediation
- (2) Planning consultancy-Land remediation/brownfield sites
- (3) Contaminated Land/remediation-Contracting services
- (4) Contaminated Land/remediation-Equipment services
- (5) Other professional services

(please specify) _____

2. If your company/organization provide service in Environmental consultancy-Contaminated site assessment/remediation, please estimate the service frequency of the listed sub-service provided in your working experience.

For each of the sub-services below, circle the response that best characterizes how you feel about the

frequency, where: 1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, and 5=Always.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
(1) Chemical expertise and/or laboratory	1	2	3	4	5
(2) CQA/Verification & Monitoring	1	2	3	4	5
(3) Environmental impact assessment	1	2	3	4	5
(4) Hydrology & hydrogeology	1	2	3	4	5

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
(5) Remediation design & supervision	1	2	3	4	5
(6) Remediation planning & management	1	2	3	4	5
(7) Site investigation	1	2	3	4	5
(8) Soil/groundwater investigation	1	2	3	4	5
(9) Sustainability appraisal	1	2	3	4	5
(10) Toxicology/risk analysis	1	2	3	4	5
(11) Waste management licensing/legislation	1	2	3	4	5
(12) Other (please specify)	1	2	3	4	5

3. If your company/organization provide service in Contaminated Land/remediation-Contracting, please estimate the service frequency of the listed sub-service provided in your working experience.

For each of the sub-services below, circle the response that best characterizes how you feel about the frequency, where: 1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, and 5=Always.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
1. Bioreactors/sludge treatment	1	2	3	4	5
2. Chemical addition/reaction	1	2	3	4	5
3. Containment	1	2	3	4	5
4. Dredging &reclamation	1	2	3	4	5
5. Electrolysis/electroremediation	1	2	3	4	5
6. Groundwater analysis or treatment	1	2	3	4	5
7. Hydrofracture/injection	1	2	3	4	5
8. In-ground barriers/mixing	1	2	3	4	5
9. In-situ air sparging/venting	1	2	3	4	5
10. In-situ bioremediation/injection	1	2	3	4	5
11. In-situ heating/steam injection	1	2	3	4	5
12. Incineration (off-site)	1	2	3	4	5
13. Laboratory analysis	1	2	3	4	5
14. Landfarming/biopiling	1	2	3	4	5
15. Landfill	1	2	3	4	5
16. Leachate control/storage and removal	1	2	3	4	5
17. Magnetic/chemical separation	1	2	3	4	5
18. MNA (monitored natural attenuation)	1	2	3	4	5

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
19. Permeable reactive barriers	1	2	3	4	5
20. Phytoremediation	1	2	3	4	5
21. Pump & treat (bioslurping)	1	2	3	4	5
22. Site/project management	1	2	3	4	5
23. Site engineering and contracting	1	2	3	4	5
24. Soil sampling & analysis	1	2	3	4	5
25. Soil vapour extraction/DVE (Dual)	1	2	3	4	5
26. Soil washing/jet washing	1	2	3	4	5
27. Solidification/Immobilization	1	2	3	4	5
28. Stabilisation ex-situ (cover layers)	1	2	3	4	5
29. Thermal treatment plant	1	2	3	4	5
30. Vitrification	1	2	3	4	5
31. Other (please specify)	1	2	3	4	5

4. If your company/organization provide service in Contaminated Land/remediation-Equipment, please estimate the service frequency of the listed sub-service provided in your working experience.

For each of the sub-services below, circle the response that best characterizes how you feel about the frequency, where: 1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, and 5=Always.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
(1) Absorbents	1	2	3	4	5
(2) Biological materials	1	2	3	4	5
(3) Chemical materials	1	2	3	4	5
(4) Containment	1	2	3	4	5
(5) Dredging & reclamation	1	2	3	4	5
(6) Drilling & piling	1	2	3	4	5
(7) Earthmoving equipment	1	2	3	4	5
(8) Excavation	1	2	3	4	5
(9) Geomembranes/linings	1	2	3	4	5
(10) Geosynthetics/geotextiles	1	2	3	4	5
(11) Groundwater analysis	1	2	3	4	5
(12) Groundwater treatment	1	2	3	4	5
(13) Laboratory analysis	1	2	3	4	5
(14) Monitoring equipment	1	2	3	4	5
(15) Other (please specify)	1	2	3	4	5

5. Do you have experience of soil stabilization? Yes No

If yes, which additives/methods do you use?

(Please select all that apply)

- (1) Cement materials
- (2) Sepiolite modified products
- (3) Sepiolite composited products
- (4) Sepiolite raw mining
- (5) Sepiolite processing byproducts

Other (please specify) _____

6. What criteria are used in selecting soil remediation techniques?

7. For the projects you have been involved with, what are the typical budgets X?

(Please select all that apply)

- (1) $X < \text{£}5000$
- (2) $\text{£}5000 \leq X < \text{£}50,000$
- (3) $\text{£}50,000 \leq X < \text{£}500,000$
- (4) $\text{£}500,000 \leq X < \text{£}5000,000$
- (5) $X \geq \text{£}5000,000$

Other (please specify) _____

8. Who pays for the costs of the soil remediation project?

(Please select all that apply)

- (1) Government
- (2) Company/Organization who will use the site
- (3) Company/Organization who caused the contamination

Other (please specify) _____

9. What kind of intellectual property are owned or used by your company?

(Please select all that apply)

- (1) Trademarks
- (2) Patents
- (3) Copyrights
- (4) Trade secrets

Other (please specify) _____

10. What is the basis of decision making on the choice of remediation method applied in projects?

(Please select all that apply)

- (1) Government approval
- (2) Business investment/Enterprises Investment
- (3) Professional opinion
- (4) Normative system
- Other (please specify) _____

11. How important do you feel the following factors are in delivering successful remediation on site?

For each of the factors below, circle the response that best characterizes how you feel about the importance, where: 1=Unimportant, 2=Slightly Important, 3= Moderately Important, 4=Important, and 5=Very Important.

	Unimportant	Slightly Important	Moderately Important	Important	Very Important
(1) Site background/histories investigation	1	2	3	4	5
(2) Technical measures	1	2	3	4	5
(3) Design plan	1	2	3	4	5
(4) Funding guarantee	1	2	3	4	5
(5) Technical skill and/or capability of engineering technicians	1	2	3	4	5
(6) Corporate environmental awareness	1	2	3	4	5
(7) Social opinion	1	2	3	4	5
(8) Other (please specify)	1	2	3	4	5

12. What is likelihood do you think the following factors causes the competition in different companies on soil/land remediation area?

For each of the factors below, circle the response that best characterizes how you think about the likelihood, where: 1= Definitely not, 2=Probably not, 3=Possibly, 4=Probably, and 5=Definitely.

	Definitely not	Probably not	Possibly	Probably	Definitely
(1) Price of service/product	1	2	3	4	5
(2) Technology improving	1	2	3	4	5
(3) Market position	1	2	3	4	5
(4) Other (please specify)	1	2	3	4	5

13. Are these factors are used for setting remediation targets?

For each of the factors below, circle the response that best characterizes how you feel about the statement, where: 1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3= Uncertain, 4=Agree, and 5=Strongly Agree.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
(1) Capital budgeting	1	2	3	4	5
(2) Technical skills	1	2	3	4	5
(3) Social results	1	2	3	4	5
(4) Economic benefits	1	2	3	4	5
(5) Payback period	1	2	3	4	5
(6) Engineering Standard	1	2	3	4	5
(7) Government requirements	1	2	3	4	5
(8) Public requirements	1	2	3	4	5
(9) Other (please specify)	1	2	3	4	5

14. How important do you feel the following factors in verifying the success of remediation on site? For each of the factors below, circle the response that best characterizes how you feel about the importance, where: 1=Unimportant, 2=Slightly Important, 3= Moderately Important, 4=Important, and 5=Very Important.

	Unimportant	Slightly Important	Moderately Important	Important	Very Important
(1) Change in value of land pre-treatment and post-treatment	1	2	3	4	5
(2) Acceptance report and opinion	1	2	3	4	5
(3) Government approval	1	2	3	4	5
(4) Engineering operation feedback	1	2	3	4	5
(5) Social results	1	2	3	4	5
(6) Economic benefits	1	2	3	4	5
(7) Rate of return on investment	1	2	3	4	5
(8) Other (please specify)	1	2	3	4	5

15. Company or organization contact information

Name: _____ Mobile (Optional): _____

Email: _____ Department: _____

Job Title: _____ Company Name: _____

行业情况调查问卷

感谢您参与这项研究，这项调查是宋娜在西苏格兰大学攻读博士学位研究中的一部分。研究的总体目标是找出国内土壤修复项目中的商业决策模型以及该模型对修复项目执行的影响，以更好地为项目决策过程提供信息并实现修复场地的可持续利用。

以下问卷内容是用来调查国内土壤修复过程中的商业决策模型对项目的影响。该项研究结果被用来探索项目预算、专家经验、项目预算与项目目标的平衡。这项问卷需要您大概 5 分钟完成。

在开始调查之前，请阅读以下内容

您的姓名和联系方式完全自愿提供，只有在您同意与您联系进行后续访谈时才会使用。该调查产生的任何数据与分析都将被匿名化来实现个人及组织信息保密。如果您对调查或操作有任何疑问，请致电：宋娜，15197363112。

该研究的数据将作为博士学位论文的一部分发表（匿名），并可能用于学术会议报告和/或期刊出版物（匿名）。

1. 您的年龄是？

- (1) 16-25
- (2) 26-35
- (3) 36-45
- (4) 46-55
- (5) 56-65
- (6) >65

2. 您的性别是？

- (1) 男性
- (2) 女性
- (3) 其他

3. 您的最高学历是？

- (1) 高中或职高
- (2) 本科或大专
- (3) 硕士
- (4) 博士
- (5) 其他

4. 您的土壤修复项目经验多少年？

- (1) ≤3 年
- (2) 4-6 年
- (3) 7-9 年

(4) 10-12 年

(5) ≥13 年

5. 您经历过的项目场址所在位置？

(请选择所有适用条件)

- (1) 西南地区 (包括四川、云南、贵州、西藏、重庆)
- (2) 西北地区 (包括宁夏、新疆、青海、陕西、甘肃)
- (3) 华中地区 (包括湖北、湖南、河南、江西)
- (4) 华北地区 (包括北京、天津、河北、山西、内蒙古)
- (5) 华东地区 (包括山东、江苏、安徽、浙江、福建、上海)
- (6) 华南地区 (包括广东、广西、海南)
- (7) 东北地区 (包括辽宁、吉林、黑龙江)
- (8) 台港澳地区 (包括台湾、香港、澳门)

其他 (请写明) _____

6. 您公司是一家：

(请选择所有适用条件)

- (1) 技术服务公司 (咨询与设计、施工或总承包服务)
- (2) 设备材料供应商
- (3) 国有企业
- (4) 混合所有制企业
- (5) 民营企业

其他 (请写明) _____

7. 公司/组织提供的服务有：

(请选择所有适用条件)

- (1) 第三方检测服务
- (2) 咨询服务或设计
- (3) 总承包服务
- (4) 污染场地施工
- (5) 专业材料/设备服务 (例如药剂)

其他服务 (请写明) _____

8. 贵公司/组织如提供第三方检测服务，以下各项服务所需频率是？

	从不	很少	有时	很多	总是
(1) 场地调查	1	2	3	4	5
(2) 化学专业知识和/或实验室检测	1	2	3	4	5

	从不	很少	有时	很多	总是
(3) 环境影响评价	1	2	3	4	5
(4) 水文和水文地质	1	2	3	4	5
(5) 回顾性(后)评价检测	1	2	3	4	5
(6) 项目关键节点质量核实 与监测	1	2	3	4	5
(7) 其他(请写明)	1	2	3	4	5

9. 贵公司/组织如提供总承包服务, 以下各技术方法应用频率多少?

	从不	很少	有时	很多	总是
1. 植物修复	1	2	3	4	5
2. 微生物修复	1	2	3	4	5
3. 植物/微生物联合修复	1	2	3	4	5
4. 固化/稳定化	1	2	3	4	5
5. 土壤淋洗	1	2	3	4	5
6. 热脱附	1	2	3	4	5
7. 土地耕作法/生物堆层法	1	2	3	4	5
8. 填埋	1	2	3	4	5
9. 化学氧化/还原技术	1	2	3	4	5
10. 其他(请写明)	1	2	3	4	5

10. 贵公司/组织如提供专业材料服务, 以下各项服务所需频率是?

	从不	很少	有时	很多	总是
(1) 吸附剂	1	2	3	4	5
(2) 生物材料	1	2	3	4	5
(3) 化工材料	1	2	3	4	5
(4) 其他(请写明)	1	2	3	4	5

11. 贵公司/组织如提供专业设备服务, 以下各项服务所需频率是?

	从不	很少	有时	很多	总是
(1) 监测设备	1	2	3	4	5
(2) 复垦设备	1	2	3	4	5
(3) 钻孔和打桩设备	1	2	3	4	5
(4) 挖掘设备	1	2	3	4	5
(5) 运输设备	1	2	3	4	5
(6) 其他(请写明)	1	2	3	4	5

12. 您有土壤固化的经验吗? 是 否

您使用过哪种添加剂？。

(请选择所有适用条件)

- (1) 黏土矿物
- (2) 其他矿物
- (3) 化工材料
- (4) 微生物材料

其他 (请写明) _____

13. 您有使用海泡石土壤固化的经验吗? 是 否

如果是，您具体使用过哪种添加剂？

(请选择所有适用条件)

- (1) 海泡石复合/改性产品
- (2) 海泡石原矿
- (3) 海泡石加工过程中的副产物

其他 (请写明) _____

14. 在项目经验中，您有使用以下哪些土壤修复相关标准? 在何阶段使用？

请估计并圈出最能反映您对此标准使用阶段的看法，其中：1 =从不，2 =在初始风险评价阶段使用，3 =在整个项目决策中反复使用。(请选择所有适用条件)

	从不	在风险评估阶段使用	在整个项目决策中反复使用
(1) 《建设用地土壤污染状况调查技术导则》(HJ 25.1-2019)	1	2	3
(2) 《建设用地土壤污染风险管控和修复监测技术导则》(HJ 25.2-2019)	1	2	3
(3) 《建设用地土壤污染风险评估技术导则》(HJ 25.3-2019)	1	2	3
(4) 《建设用地土壤修复技术导则》(HJ 25.4-2019)	1	2	3
(5) 《污染地块风险管控与土壤修复效果评估技术导则》(HJ 25.5-2018)	1	2	3
(6) 《污染地块地下水修复和风险管控技术导则》(HJ 25.6-2019)	1	2	3

	从不	在风险评估阶段使用	在整个项目决策中反复使用
(7)《环境影响评价技术导则土壤环境（试行）》(HJ 964-2018)	1	2	3
(8)《建设用地土壤污染风险管控和修复术语》(HJ 682-2019)	1	2	3
(9) 地方性标准	1	2	3
(10) 其他 (请写明)	1	2	3

15. 在工程经验中，您有使用以下哪些土壤修复相关标准？在何阶段使用？

请估计并圈出最能反映您对此标准使用阶段的看法，其中：1 = 从不，2 = 在初始风险评价阶段使用，3 = 在整个项目决策中反复使用。（请选择所有适用条件）

	从不	在风险评估阶段使用	在整个项目决策中反复使用
(1)《中华人民共和国土壤污染防治法》	1	2	3
(2)《国务院关于印发土壤污染防治行动计划的通知》(国发【2016】31号)	1	2	3
(3)《污染地块土壤环境管理办法》(环保部令第42号)	1	2	3
(4)《工矿用地土壤环境管理办法（试行）》(生态环境部令第3号)	1	2	3
(5)《建设用地土壤环境调查评估技术指南》(环保部公告2017年第72号)	1	2	3
(6)《土壤环境监测技术规范》(HJ/T 166-2004)	1	2	3
(7)《土壤环境质量 农用地土壤污染风险管控标准（试行）》(GB15618-2018)	1	2	3

	从不	在风险评估阶段使用	在整个项目 决策中反复 使用
(8) 《土壤环境质量 建设用 地土壤污染风险管控标准 (试行)》(GB36600- 2018)	1	2	3
(9) 地方性标准	1	2	3
(10) 其他 (请写明)	1	2	3

16. 常见土壤修复项目费用来源？

(请选择所有适用条件)

- (1) 国家专项资金
- (2) 地方政府资金
- (3) 开发商企业
- (4) 污染责任企业
- (5) 第三方出资

其他 (请写明) _____

17. 您的公司使用或者拥有知识产权种类有哪些？

(请选择所有适用条件)

- (1) 商标
- (2) 专利
- (3) 版权
- (4) 商业秘密

其他 (请写明) _____

18. 国内一般修复方案决定依据？

(请选择所有适用条件)

- (1) 修复目标值
- (2) 用地性质
- (3) 政府批复
- (4) 企业投资
- (5) 专家意见
- (6) 规范制度

其他 (请写明) _____

19. 在场地修复实施过程中，您认为以下因素有多重要？

对于以下每个问题，请圈出最能反映您对重要性的看法，其中：1 =不重要，2 =轻微重要，3 =一般重要，4 =重要，5 =非常重要。(请选择所有适用条件)

	不重要	轻微重要	一般重要	重要	非常重要
(1) 场址背景/历史调查	1	2	3	4	5
(2) 修复目标值	1	2	3	4	5
(3) 技术方案	1	2	3	4	5
(4) 资金保证	1	2	3	4	5
(5) 同类项目业绩	1	2	3	4	5
(6) 企业环保意识	1	2	3	4	5
(7) 社会舆论认知	1	2	3	4	5
(8) 其他 (请写明)	1	2	3	4	5

20. 您同意项目商业决策会对以下因子产生影响的看法吗？

其中：1 =完全不同意，2 =基本不同意，3 =不确定，4 =基本同意，5 =完全同意。（请选择所有适用条件）

	完全不同意	基本不同意	不确定	基本同意	完全同意
(1) 地块用途	1	2	3	4	5
(2) 政府要求	1	2	3	4	5
(3) 社会群众	1	2	3	4	5
(4) 地块未来发展	1	2	3	4	5
(5) 其他 (请写明)	1	2	3	4	5

21. 您同意以下因素会影响土壤修复公司优势的看法吗？

其中：1 =完全不同意，2 =基本不同意，3 =不确定，4 =基本同意，5 =完全同意。（请选择所有适用条件）

	完全不同意	基本不同意	不确定	基本同意	完全同意
(1) 现有施工手段与技术	1	2	3	4	5
(2) 同类项目工程业绩	1	2	3	4	5
(3) 服务/产品价格变化	1	2	3	4	5
(4) 新产品/设备研发	1	2	3	4	5
(5) 市场定位	1	2	3	4	5
(6) 其他 (请写明)	1	2	3	4	5

22. 您同意以下因素会影响项目修复目标设定的看法吗？

其中：1 =完全不同意，2 =基本不同意，3 =不确定，4 =基本同意，5 =完全同意。（请选择所有适用条件）

	完全不同意	基本不同意	不确定	基本同意	完全同意
--	-------	-------	-----	------	------

(1) 用地性质	1	2	3	4	5
(2) 技术手段	1	2	3	4	5
(3) 投资预算	1	2	3	4	5
(4) 投资回收期	1	2	3	4	5
(5) 国家及行业标准	1	2	3	4	5
(6) 政府要求	1	2	3	4	5
(7) 群众诉求	1	2	3	4	5
(8) 其他 (请写明)	1	2	3	4	5

23. 为验证场地修复的效果，您认为以下因素有多重要？

请圈出最能反映您对其重要性的看法，其中：1 =非常不重要，2 =不重要，3 =不确定，4 =重要，5 =非常重要。（请选择所有适用条件）

	非常不重要	不重要	不确定	重要	非常重要
(1) 检测数据变化	1	2	3	4	5
(2) 验收意见	1	2	3	4	5
(3) 工程运行情况	1	2	3	4	5
(4) 社会效益	1	2	3	4	5
(5) 其他 (请写明)	1	2	3	4	5

24. 在场地修复项目中，请您使用 1、2、3 对以下因素对项目商业决策重要性进行排序？

修复目标值

资金保证

现有技术与手段

25. 请问您愿意参与后续的访谈吗？

愿意 不愿意

26. 姓名/电话：

Appendix III

Publication outputs from this thesis:

N. Song, A. Hursthouse, I. McLellan, Z. Wang, “Decision Support Models for Site Remediation: An Evaluation of Industry Practice in China,” published. *Sustainability* (2022) 14(19):

11811. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141911811>

N. Song, A. Hursthouse, I. McLellan, Z. Wang, “Treatment of environmental contamination using sepiolite: current approaches and future potential,” published. *Environ Geochem Health* (2021)

43(7): 2679–2697. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10653-020-00705-0>

N. Song, I. McLellan, W. Liu, Z. Wang, A. Hursthouse, “The waste ban in China: what happened next? Assessing the impact of new policies on the waste management sector in China,” published.

Environ Geochem Health (2023) 45: 1117–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10653-021-01101-y>

Supplementary materials for Appendix III

Appendix A

Figure A1. Amount of hazardous solid waste generated of PRC in 2000-2017.

Figure A2. Amount of hazardous solid waste generated and disposed of PRC in 2011-2016 and their disposal rate.

Figure A3. Remediation projects' location distribution.

Figure A4. Technology used in respondents' experience.

Figure A5. Frequency of each material applied in stabilization or solidification.